

WOMENFOLK IN YORÙBÁ VIDEO FILM INDUSTRY

BY

Olufadekemi ADAGBADA

B.Ed (Hons) Yorùbá (Ado-Ekiti). M.A. (Ibadan)

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ABSTRACT

The Yorùbá video film is still a relatively new area in Yorùbá studies, hence the paucity of materials in that field. The few ones in existence are basically on how women are portrayed in Yorùbá videos. No thesis, to our knowledge, has been written, prior to this study, on what women have contributed to the development of video film since its advent. The intention in this study, therefore, is to examine the various sectors of the film industry where women are employed and what women's contributions are, and to analyse the contents of their productions.

The major source of data for this study is content analysis of the Yorùbá home video films produced by women and those produced by men wherein women have taken part as members of the production crew, as post-production workers and as actresses. Furthermore, some of these female producers, artistes and artists were interviewed, so as to complement the content analysis. Womanism is the theoretical base on which the study anchors, so as to explicate the contributions of the female gender to the Yorùbá the video film industry. Besides, the theory was applied to highlight the level at which their sex influences them as a work force.

This work shows that women have transcended their earlier historical role as mere choruses in dramatic performances. They now take active roles in different spheres of film production such as producers, script writers, musicians, costumiers and make-up artists, in spite of the fact that they are constrained to operate in a gender-biased society. It is revealed in the study that they are both

creative and re-creative artistes and artists and not mere objects of spectacle, which they used to be. Thematically, the study shows that while earlier film production of the womenfolk tends to sustain the patriarchal ideology, in recent times, a few of them are beginning to challenge it.

This work has brought to the fore women's creative ingenuity in the video film industry. The implication of this study, therefore, is that film production is for both female and male. Within the ambience of our new social reality, female filmmakers should be able to explore and exploit their creative and re-creative skills to an advantage, as they have ample opportunity, like their male counterparts, to assert their self-esteem in the film industry.

Key words: Womenfolk, Yorùbá video film industry, Re-creative artistes.

Word Count: 372

DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated to the baby of my family,
Adédòtun Olúgbémiléké Àkàndé ADÁGBÁDÁ.

Èsò oríta, ègìrì òkè
Ọmọ arúngbàdo làde
Ọmọ ajoba líjọ Ìjerò ríhun je
Adágbádá-má-lókòó
Àbèntè baba ijà

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Olúfadékèmi Adágbádá
Department of Linguistics & African Languages
University of Ibadan
Ibadan

CERTIFICATION

viii

I certify that this work was carried out by Olúfadékémi ADÁGBÁDÁ of the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.

 15-09-05

Supervisor

Durotoye A. ADELEKE
BA Ed. (Hons) (Lagos), MA, PhD (Ibadan)
Senior Lecturer
Department of Linguistics & African Languages
University of Ibadan,
Ibadan

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CHAPTER ONE

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Drama is a branch of literature which implies the imitation of an action or of persons in action. The ultimate objective of drama, in the words of Ojá Rótímí (1968), is to "entertain or edify". We wish to add that drama can also be used for protest. Drama mirrors the aggregate of the sociological set-up of a society. It reflects not only a people's beliefs, hopes and attitudes, but also their religion, economy and politics.

Basically, drama implies having two sets of persons, one acting, while the other watches the actions. The media through which both sets of people can come into contact have over the years broadened. This has been made possible by an improved theatrical technology. In earliest times, both actors and audience had to have physical (live) contact, with the former on the stage or at special arenas, as the case may be, while the latter had to stand or sit not too far away, to watch. With the advent of sound waves picked through the radio, the audience (now listeners) can stay in the comfort of their homes to enjoy the recorded voices of actors and actresses¹. The television is an improvement over the radio. With it, not only can sound waves be picked, the moving pictures of the artistes can also be seen on the screen. Further improvements are the cinema projectors, motion pictures on celluloid, with the latest being motion pictures on video films for theatrical and home use.

The development, or rather the metamorphosis of the Yorùbá drama, as we have it today, has been from traditional festivals to *Eégún Aláré* (masque dramaturgy) (Ogundeji 1988) to the Ogunde Dramatic Movement and Tradition which presented live stage theatrical shows, radio and television (recorded) shows, photo-play magazines and theatrical celluloid films. As of now, the literature of the Yorùbá people has joined the global theatrical technological advancement, for the Yorùbá films, too, can be watched on video tapes either in the theatres and film houses, or at home. It is difficult, however, to pinpoint categorically when a previous stage in the developmental process highlighted above gave way to a new and more modern one. This is because the extinction or end of the popularity of each of them dovetails into the beginning of the one that developed from it and/or alongside with it (Adeleke 2003). Today, however, the *Eégún Aláré's* performance is rare to come by; if there is anywhere in Yorubaland where they still perform, it must be in very remote villages where access to electricity and roads is nil. The Ogunde Dramatic Movement, in travelling troupes, on radio, in photoplay magazines and on celluloid theatrical films, is fast becoming a thing of the past. Only very few (private) television stations broadcast their plays, too. What the Yorùbá drama is virtually left with, for now, are the traditional festivals and films shot on video for theatrical shows and the home video films.

In the history of drama during the earliest times, men were known to be dominant among the cast of characters when acting. Feminine roles in

Shakespearean and the *Eégún Aláré* period, for instance, were acted by males costumed and made-up as females (Adédéji 1969). Such 'actresses' talked in strained, sonorous voices like females and walked with female-like gaits. (Dialogues were absent in *Eégún Aláré* displays.) In present times, things have changed. Both males and females now take part in the characterization of dramatic shows, in such a way that mirrors their immediate society and the universe as a whole. The question, however, is the extent to which each gender has contributed (and is contributing) to the growth, development and sustenance of drama in a given society under the existing norms and values.

1.1 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Universally, people's general view of the female sex bequeaths her an inferior status when compared with the opposite sex. (This includes most women themselves, too, at least until recently.) The Yorùbá society is a patriarchal one which enhances the male status, making the females to live in the shadows of their male counterparts. The Yorùbá refer to women as '*obinrin atèyintò*' (women, human beings who urinate from the rear). This implicitly means that women have very shallow brains. It is also believed that *Egungun ihà mésàn-án lókùnrin ní, méje pére ní tobinrin* (Males have nine rib bones, while females possess merely seven). This means, in essence, that women are also physiologically inferior to men. However, there abounds, in our society, women who have excelled even more than their male counterparts both physically and

intellectually². Despite formidable achievements and self-actualization of women as engineers, pilots, doctors, architects, lawyers and technicians, to mention just a few professions of present times, and as an indispensable gender in various Yorùbá genres (Oyesakin 1998:35), the impression persists that they (women) are second class citizens. The Yorùbá patriarchal society still looks at women as beings whose primary assignment is to stay at home, producing babies and doing household chores.

Society is known to be dynamic; its culture evolves, hence, a lot of changes for improvement keep coming up to make man's existence on the surface of the earth more convenient and meaningful. One of such aspects of development in our society today, as far as the entertainment industry is concerned, is the emergence of pictures on celluloid – the film. While the first film ever made (*Workers Leaving The Factory*) was shown in Paris on the twenty-second of March, 1895 (Tompson and Bordwell 1994:9), Nigerians never watched a film until the twelfth of August, 1903, when the film of the coronation scenes of Edward VII was shown at the Glover Memorial Hall in Lagos (Mgbejume 1989:69-70). This began the influx of different types of (foreign) films into Nigeria. These films were plotally and thematically alien to the African culture (Adesanya 1997:13). They portrayed the life-styles of the West-full of sexual, barbaric, vulgar and violent scenes.

The first indigenous Nigerian feature film on celluloid was not shot until 1970 by Francis Oládélé who produced *Kongi's Harvest*. This aroused the interest

of other film producers like Olá Balógun who produced *Ajàní Ogún* – the first Yoruba film on celluloid (Adesanya 1997: 14, Alamu 1991) in 1976. The unaffordable high cost of production, however, sent motion pictures on celluloid into recess in Nigeria around 1994 (Adesanya 1997:15). This led to the cheaper use of video tapes for film recording. *Igí Dá* (1990) by Olátúndé was first the Yorùbá video film (Alamu 2003:9).

Film is set to totally achieve what the written drama has not – to effect the purported changes that the playwright desires in the society on the page. Feature films can be seen as the literature which walks and talks (Boulton 1960); a form of literature that has life. Film transcends educational and language barriers, unlike texts, it appeals to both literates and non-literates. Even when the audience does not understand the language used in a film, the sequential actions are at most times explicit enough to drive home the message. It can also be seen that film, apart from being a means of relaxation, is also a medium for passing across to the populace the expectations from the society.

The purpose of this study is to look critically into the place of women in commercializing the drama aspect of the Yorùbá Literature via the Yorùbá Home Video (henceforth to be referred to as YHV) industry. Like most well established profit-oriented ventures, the YHV industry also has various divisions of labour. We shall, therefore, examine the womenfolk in the creative force as producers, directors, script writers and film track singers, and as re-creative artists in costuming and make-up. In this way, we shall be able to highlight the present

position of women as a work force in the entertainment industry of a patriarchal/patrifocal society.

Many scholars have worked on the different aspects of the film. These include Hyginus Ekwuazi (1984), who studied the context of production of the film in Nigeria, Onyero Mgbejume (1989), who examined the development, problems and promise of Nigerian films. Olágòkè Alamu (1992) examined the trends in the development of Yorùbá films, while Dúrótoyè Adélékè (1995) studied audience reception of Yorùbá films. Kèmi Okéowó (1999) studied the portraits of women in Yorùbá theatre; the burden of Olágòkè Alámú (2002) is on the aesthetics of the Yorùbá video film and Olabùnmi Olújìnmí (2004) has, primarily, the portrait of the female as a literary character in Yorùbá video films as the crux of his research. Most of these studies are historical surveys, reviews, audience reception analysis, studies of portrayals, and an examination of developmental stages. None of them, to the best of our knowledge, has actually studied the division of labour and what it implies, as it relates to women in the economy of the Yorùbá literature via the home video industry. This gap we have set out to fill in this study.

1.2 Significance of Study

The study focuses basically on gender issues, and because gender issues are out to effect a complementary effort from both sexes, the study is sociologically based. It is specifically to examine the achievements or otherwise

of women in the areas of video film production, script writing, costuming, make-up and film music.

The study will be of immense value to researchers not only in Womanism and the sociology of literature, but also to those working on film production in Nigeria and beyond. Our work will also be, hopefully, of great value to both male and female producers, script writers and directors of films, because we are set to highlight, in great details, the strength and shortcomings of the gynocentric films already in the market.

This study will also be beneficial to government agencies like the Nigerian Film Corporation, as it will add to the already existing documents in their libraries. Above all, we intend to open up avenues for future studies on other gender issues relating to the study of films as a part of the entertainment industry; an aspect of the sociology of the video film.

1.3 Methodology

The method employed in carrying out this study was by conducting oral interviews with both male and female Yorùbá home video artistes and artists concerning their career. We also watched and analyzed many Yorùbá home video tapes, more especially those produced by women and also those produced by men wherein women are script writers, actresses, costumiers, (executive) producers, track singers or make-up artists. Our analysis was based on the Womanism theory. To make the analysis comparative, we also gynocritically

examined the thematic components of YHV produced by both males and females.

1.4 Yorùbá Home Video Films (YHV): A Definition

To state categorically which film may be called a 'Yorùbá home video film' may not be easy, the reason being that certain issues have to be considered. On one hand, video films wherein the major, if not all characters and the culture that are reflected are predominantly that of Yorùbá, irrespective of the language medium in which the film is produced, can be referred to as Yorùbá films. If this method is employed, video films like *Ẓàngó*, *Òdúdúwà*, *The Ndakobas* and *Which Man Dey Mess* would qualify to be referred to as YHV films. On the other hand, one may define Yorùbá home video films as films wherein the medium of communication is the Yorùbá language³ - that is, considering it linguistically. In this sense, any film in which the medium of communication is Yorùbá such as *Nnkan Obinnin*, *Aṣéwó Kano*, *Ẓaworo Ide*, *Abéré Alhaja*, *Teni Qlá*, *Folájiyo*, *Ìdè*, *Fomisólá*, *Ètò Mi*, *Sweet Bannana*, *Ìbínú Olukoso*, *Alábàárú*, *Òrùka*, *Abèké Alámàlà*, *Ibi Ayé Bá Mi Dé*, *Ayé Àwa Obinnin*, or *Àlámú Ẓèniyàn*, will qualify. For this study, we employed the use of the second definition; that is, all home video films wherein the medium of communication is basically Yorùbá.

1.5 Definition of Terms

Some terms are used in this study which have their own peculiarities as far as the study is concerned. These are listed and explained below: YHV – as an abbreviation of 'Yorùbá Home Video'. ARTISTES – used to refer to professional entertainers like actors, actresses and musicians. ARTISTS – used to refer to the professionals who are in charge of make-up for artistes. They (the artists) also design and arrange for the costumes used by the artistes or initiate aspects of production like directing, stage management, and lighting.

1.6 Delimitations

When Yorùbá video films are produced, in order to break even on the cost of productions before pirates and home video rental operators lay hands on them and as a means of advertisement to would-be home-version buyers, some producers exhibit their films in film theatres and cinema houses. They eventually dub such films into home video cassettes and compact discs. This study is limited to Yorùbá video films in home video cassettes or compact discs, irrespective of whether they were exhibited in theatres and cinema houses or not.

As there are no less than one thousand of such Yorùbá home video films in the market to date⁴, it is not possible to study all of them if the study is to be thorough, in-depth and meaningful. We have therefore limited it basically to Yorùbá home video films produced or written by women and those produced by

men where women have expert roles like costumiers, make-up artists or music-track singers to play. We will, however, need to make references to films produced solely by men, for comparative reasons.

Our study scope does not extend to religious video films like *Ewu Ìgbà Ìkeyin*, *Agbára Nlá*, *Omọ Májèmú* or *Àpótí Èrí*, as the study is basically on secular Yorùbá home video films.

NOTES ON CHAPTER ONE

- 1 Such programmes can also be transmitted live.
- 2 Modúpè Òsíkòyà and Mary Onyali were popular sprinters who many men might not be able to compete with. Mrs Elizabeth Àniké Williams, a sixty year-old woman from Ìjèbù North Local Government Area in Ogun State, is a public transporter. Àniké Williams plies the Ìbàdàn-Ìjèbù route in her Datsun Urvan bus (Registration number OGUN XA 668JGB) daily. Mrs Sandra Emokpaye – interviewed by Mrs Jàre Kólá-Kúforíjì on the 29th of September, 2002, on the African International Television (AIT) programme, Emotan, is a motor mechanic based in Lagos. Sandra has a garage with many male apprentices. She is happily married with children.
- 3 The Yorùbá language meant here includes both the standard form (for official use) and its varieties like Ègbá, Èkítì, Ìjèbù, Rẹ̀mọ̀, Ègbádò, Ìgbóminà, Òyó or Ifẹ̀ dialects.
- 4 An information supplied us by Diméjì Òtúyẹ̀mí, an employee of Jofod Video Club, Ìjèbù-Òde in an interview on the twentieth of April, 2001.

CHAPTER TWO

ISSUES ABOUT WOMANISM AND YORÙBÁ DRAMA

2.0 INTRODUCTION

The fact that the female gender is denigrated and thus oppressed by the opposite gender appears to be universal. In almost all the nations of the world, the male dominates the society in virtually all aspects. This is why Patai (1997) is of the opinion that the female has been conceptualized in various ways as merely the bearer of human beings or as a special specimen of the human race or as the chattel of men, whose purpose is to work and bear children. She is also regarded as the source through whom kingship and succession is determined, or as the powerful pivot which "presents the picture of weakness both in the home and society" (Akintan 2002:1)

In the African society, for instance, polygamy is permitted. The customary gauge of a man's wealth is an estimate of his wives (Ling Roth 1968:33) and only he has the exclusive right of divorce. The woman can be divorced on flimsy excuses like not cooking well, sexual non-satisfaction or refusal to accept newly married co-wives. Apart from these, women are largely excluded from, or severely marginalized in high status occupation and from positions of power. This should not be so, for women are not one of a number of isolable units, but half a totality, the human species. Women are fundamental

to the human condition, yet, in their economic, social and political roles, they are marginalized.

Aristotle, cited by Mitchell (1966:64), commenting on the status of women, says "...woman as it is, is an impotent male, for it is through a certain incapacity that the female is female". The incapacity usually referred to by most men like Aristotle is often woven around physiology and intelligence. A woman's fragile physiology must be so because nature has bestowed upon her the duty of procreation for the continuous corporate existence of the human species on earth. However, in as much as we agree that women are denigrated under patriarchy, we disagree with Ojá-Àlùkò (2002:20) that "the mother – role is a cultural construction". This is because, biologically, it is the woman who possesses a womb, a physiology that can bear a foetus, mammary glands and natural instincts for child nurturing, protection and welfare⁴. We will want to say that these roles should be appreciated in the woman rather than being used as a weapon against her freedom and integrity.

Intellectually, if a female is exposed to the same training as her male counterpart, there is the possibility of her performing equally satisfactorily as him or perhaps better. However, the world is patrifocal and, as such, the female lives in the shadow of the male. In the Yorùbá socio-cultural set up, a female is socialized into a culture of female subordination. She is not only subordinate to her husband and the men in her own family of birth, she is also subordinate to

the members of her husband's family – male and female (Olá-Àlùkò 2002:19). August Babel, as cited by Mitchell (1966:24), is right to say that:

... from the beginning of time, oppression was the common lot of the woman and the labourer.... was the first human being that tasted bondage. Woman was a slave before slavery existed.

Under patriarchy – a culture that is slanted so that men are valued a lot and women valued less; or in which men's prestige is up and women's prestige, down (Gray 1982:19), a woman's achievement is mostly likely to be judged in relation to her being one man's wife or daughter. There seems to be an understanding that she is nothing without a man. Socio-cultural indoctrination has made the woman to accept the 'imbalance' in gender status as natural. This is why "even educated and privileged women remain in violent and abusive relationships..." Fiorenza (1996:45). In any case, a society that sets women in secondary position to men, oppresses women, whether or not the women recognize their oppression or attempt to do anything about it (Bossman 1994), is not a desirable one.

2.1 Theorizing The Position of the Female

The *raison d'être* for subjugating the female gender to the position of a second fiddle has been widely theorized by gender scholars. This is because patriarchy is a system of social stratification and differentiation based on sex,

providing material advantages to males, while simultaneously placing severe constraints on the roles and activities of the females (Aina 1998:6).

Philosophers like Aristotle (cited by Mitchell 1986) and Jean Jacques Rousseau (cited by Grimshaw 1986: 9-10), both based a woman's supposedly inferior status on her physiology. 'She is a weaker vessel' (Aristotle), a delicate object to be handled with care like a china ware, but at the same time to be "tamed" (Rousseau). La Bruyere, as cited by Reiss (1989:13), too, refers to women as "either children or ornamental objects existing for men's titillation".

Many religious based theorists claim that God 'Himself' (a supposed male) ordained men's superiority over women because 'He' made Eve out of Adam's ribs. To Adam, too, was given the prerogative power to name all other things created by God. Adam, therefore, named her 'Eve', meaning "she was taken out of man" (Genesis 2:23). Daly (1973:47) is of the opinion that this singular act (of supposedly being a man that named the woman) will make women remain powerless until they themselves exercise the power of naming. Another point worthy of note here is that a note of quality is first hinted in Genesis. We are made to understand that God created man (referring to human beings generally) in His own image, "male and female He created them" (Genesis 1:27), only to be told in the second chapter of Genesis that it was from Adam that He formed Eve (Genesis 2:21-22). But then, does the fact that Eve was "made" from Adam mean that Adam is superior? To this Mitchell (1966:64), citing Mary Astell, responds that:

For the Earthly Adam's being form'd before Eve, seems as little to prove her Natural subjection to him, as the living creature, Fishes, Birds and Beasts being formed before them both, proves that Mankind must be subject to these animals.

We are of the opinion that if A is first created/made, and B is fashioned out of A, then B is likely to be of a finer nature, an overall improvement over the creation of A. The patriarchal world has, however, never seen women as having a more refined nature/trait than the men. One then begins to doubt the 'divine inspiration' through which the early clerics claimed to have written the Bible. It appears to be a deliberate chauvinistic means to dominate the opposite gender, putting on masks to play God through self-appointment, in order to maintain a prestigious life. They went ahead to prescribe the silence of women, prohibiting women's authority over men by claiming that it was Eve, and not Adam, that was deceived by the serpent and as such became a transgressor (I Tim 2:11-15). As such, the Bible claims that God said:

I will greatly multiply thy sorrow and thy conception;
in sorrows thou shalt bring forth children and thy
desire shall be to thy husband and he shall rule over
thee.

As Idumwonyi (2002:92) has rightly said, "this socialization of men, to perceive women as the origin of their moral downfall, led to the development of antiwoman

sentiments." Today, the lot of most women is still as Luke 13:10-13 paradoxically paints them – their 'backs' are still bent, not only physically, but also mentally. They are also mentally bent in their attitudes to life (Awe 2002:118) due to the religio-social acculturation they have been exposed to.

Simone de Beauvoir (1953:16), as cited by Ruthven (1989:41) opines that 'alterity' as a fundamental category of human thought resulting from a duality of SELF and OTHER as primordial as consciousness itself, has led men to see women as lesser beings. de Beauvoir is of the belief that whatever the pair, one (self) sees itself as being superior, while the 'other' is the subordinate. This subordinate is viewed as/or made to feel apart from the whole, rather than part of it and as such ends up being oppressed and subjugated. de Beauvoir's opinion here is that man had always viewed himself as 'self' and the woman as the 'other'. This had resulted into 'self' treating the 'other' as a supplement to himself or regarding the 'other' as a threat. Ruthven (1989:83-84) says:

Male's aggression against the female is capable of being displaced either into language ... as vituperation, or into art-forms ... as objects of sadistic humiliation, especially in pornography, undisplaced, it results in rape and murder of women ... There is no shortage of explanations as to why men behave so aggressively towards women ... many of these are that men abuse women to disguise the fact that they fear them in some way. So if a man feels sexually inadequate, for instance, he may disguise his fear of sexually

matured women as disgust at their 'insatiability' and invent 'nymphomania' as a female sexual disorder.

Ruthven goes on to say that a man's fear that his own sexual desires are normal, may result in the construction of women as "temptresses" whose 'degrading' behaviour needs to be punished. Otto Weininger, cited by Hilary Simpson (1982:90-91), calls the male's fear of women "the unknown, the deepest fear which is fear of unconsciousness, the alluring abyss of annihilation". In conclusion, Ruthven, cited above, says that the guilt women have in these cases is their "failing to comply with male specifications of what they ought to be" (p. 84).

Engels (1940:69) opines that the physiology of the woman is the primary cause of her oppression. To him, the inability to work is the cause of her inferior status and that only public productivity can liberate her. In agreement with Engel's (cited above) opinion, Mitchell (1966:23) says:

The emancipation of women becomes possible only when women are enabled to take part in production on a large scale and when domestic duties require their attention to a minor degree.

2.2 The Beginning of the Struggle for Emancipation

In times past, due to cultural socialization, women all over the world condescended to existing as second rated citizens, compared with their male counterparts. This made women's denigration and oppression by men to go untrammelled for a very long time. Change, however, which is an inevitable aspect of the society, is making women to question why they are/have been so rated.²

The struggle by the female gender to resist oppression in all its forms and ramifications has a very long history. In fact one cannot accurately date the exact period, as there are no known archeological nor anthropological evidences for non-textualized struggles. However, feminism as a self-conscious movement began in England in the seventeenth century. It had a conglomeration of precepts and a series of demands by "women who saw themselves as a distinct sociological group ... completely excluded from the tenets and principles of the ... society" (Mitchell 1966:63). It was ideology in revolutionary England of the seventeenth century, which brought about the notion of equality. That, coupled with the era of enlightenment of the eighteenth century, and the French Revolution, that really sparked off women's struggle for liberation in the Western part of the globe. Explicitly, it was due to the change in the society, which came at the end of feudalism and the beginning of capitalism. However, the feminists during this period were the new bourgeois (middle-class) women, who could not

imagine themselves being left out in their male counterparts' struggles against tyranny and the striving for freedom and equality.

Grimshaw (1986:9) has also argued that the Industrial Revolution and the growth of egalitarian political ideas were the two things which made possible "the more systematic emergence of a tradition of feminist thinking in the eighteenth century".

Mitchell (1966) has stressed three aspects of the seventeenth-century feminists' arguments which made it doubtless that the period was the beginning of political feminism. According to her, the first reason is that, in rejecting women as naturally different from men, they have defined women as a distinct social group with its own socially defined characteristics. Secondly, as a result of this, women see that men as a social group oppress women as a social group. (It is not that the women are against men per se, they are against the social power of men.) Lastly, while desiring to be let into men's privileged spheres, they want men, too, to learn something from the women, for the feminization of men is as important as the masculinisation of women (Mitchell 1966:65).

It was around this period that Mary Wollstonecraft wrote her very popular book, *A Vindication of the Rights of a Woman* (1792). The book must have been a response to early chauvinistic philosophers like Edmund Burke and (especially) Rousseau. In an earlier book, *Emile*, written by Rousseau (cited by Grimshaw 1986:10), he highlights what education to be given to both male and female youth should look like. *Emile*: the boy should have his independence of mind

and spirit preserved. His virtues were to be those of hardihood of body and mind; independence of judgements and opinions of others, and a carefully nurtured autonomy and self-sufficiency. As for Sophie, the female youth, who is to be Emile's companion, she must be educated with the sole aim of pleasing Emile. What she is to learn must make her a pleasing, compliant and obedient companion. Her ability to reason was only important as long as it contributed to pleasing Emile. It was "this idea that Wollstone-Craft rejected" (Grimshaw 1986:10). To her, "sex and gender should be seen as accidental or contingent factors which are irrelevant to becoming fully human".

Although times have changed, the context in which early feminist struggles like those of Wollstone-Craft, Mary Astell, John Stuart Mills, Simeone de Beauvoir and Kate Millet, to mention just a few, wrote, and the issues to which they chose to give priority, are now just part of the feminists' discussions. Moreover, they have been criticized in many quarters as agitating for women of their own social class. We are of the opinion, nevertheless, that their works were truly revolutionary. The tradition of liberal, egalitarian thinking in which their works were entrenched has been and remains pivotal to the cause of feminism.

The subordination of the female gender and the need for liberation became more recognized in the nineteenth century by many socialist thinkers. The medical advancement which makes it more convenient for a woman to limit and space her pregnancies as she wishes and the improved kitchen technology

which makes her house-chores less cumbersome, time-consuming and tasking, now enable her to rub shoulders with the male gender in social productivity.

The result, however, is that despite her new status as a fellow-contributor to overall productivity, the woman continues to be marginalized. Her being anatomically smaller and weaker (though this is not true for all women), makes her to appear to the patriarchal world a less useful member of the work force. What has to be realized, anyway, is that a woman's physiological adaptation, as we mentioned earlier, is for the role she has to play in the human's continuous existence on earth; production, sexuality and socialization, which makes corporate and cohesive existence possible. Mao Tse Tung (cited by Mitchell 1966:92-93) had this to say on the duality and symbiosis of dual sex types:

Why is there identity between war and peace and none between war and stone? Why can human beings give birth only to human beings and not to anything else? The sole reason is that the identity of the opposite sex exists only in necessary conditions...

This means that one sex is the condition for the existence of the other. Women appear to be inferior merely because they have been subjugated; they are not subjugated because they are inferior. This being so, it means, then, that women should be given equal opportunities with men in as much as each woman can cope. After all, in primitive, ancient, oriental, medieval and capitalist societies, the volume of work performed by women has always been

considerable. According to Mitchell (1966:27), "It is only the form that is the question, domestic labour, even today, is enormous if quantified in terms of productive labour". In a short note written by Judith Brown for the *American Anthropologist*, Mitchell (1966:82) quotes her to view the relativity of women's domestic labour to productive economic activity in this light:

Nowhere in the world is the rearing of children primarily the responsibility of men, and only in a few societies are women exempted from participation in the subsistence activities. If the economic role of women is to be maximized, their responsibilities in child care must be reduced or that it can be carried out concurrently with child care.

Equality, in its reasonable totality, has, however, remained a principle and not a practice as popular as it appears to be in the political ideology of democracy and egalitarianism, even in the twenty-first century. Nevertheless, feminists, irrespective of race, colour, gender or political inclination, continue to strive for liberation from patri-focal ethos through various means and for different forms of liberations in perspective of their socio-cultural inclinations. The feminist struggles thus appear to be the likely longest revolution.

skeptical about the tag "Feminism" as a philosophy or ideal. Buchi Emecheta, in an interview with Marie Umeh (cited in Kolawole 1997:11), reflects such fears.

She said:

I am a feminist with a small 'f'. I love men and good men are the salt of the earth. But to tell me that we should abolish marriage like the capital F (feminist) women who say women should live together and all that, I say No. Personally, I'd like to see the ideal, happy marriage. But if it doesn't work, for goodness sake, call it off.

We do not see Emecheta as being against women's struggles for emancipation, what she is opposed to are certain aspects/types of feminism which stress the abolition of family-centred social set-up, applaud lesbianism and accept bi-sexualism. All these are comparably anomalous to the average African or Asiatic woman, unlike what they are to the Americans or Britons. To the African woman, for instance, social life has always been family-oriented. In fact, single-parent hood, lesbianism or bisexualism will sound offensive to such (African) women in rural Ìjèbù, Àbèòkútà, Èkìtì, Ońdó, Òyó, Rémọ or Ìbàdàn typical Nigerian towns.

We are not contending here that the African woman does not need liberation from patriarchal denigration; that will be over-romanticizing the idea that the African woman has not been voiceless. What we are saying is that it was not the West that 'instituted' feminist struggles. Feminism, to us, is an inevitable

reaction which has to take place in all (dynamic) societal (gender-marked) set-ups. We quite agree with Kóláwólé (1997:10) that all over the continent, there are areas of women "marginalization that call for a re-ordering of the social order". It is because of those "areas" that black sisters like Awa Thiam (1978), Irene D'Almeida (1994), Siga Jajne (1995) and Carole Boyce-Davies, (cited in Kóláwólé 1997:8), called/and are still calling, on fellow African women to 'break their silence and throw in their voices,' on their oppression by the men. Bólánlé Awé (1992), Mọlárá Ògúndípè-Leslie (1994), Chinkwenye Okonjo Ògunyemí (1985) and other women like them, argue that the African woman had never been silent about her patriarchal ordeals, if one cares to search for her voice. Ògúndípè-Leslie (1994:10) says that:

We neither look for their voices where they utter them,
nor do we think it worthwhile to listen to their voices.

Kóláwólé (1994) points out that as far back as the nineteenth-century, which was a volatile period in African history, women groups had become formidable threats to colonialists. They also struggled against slave raiders. Kóláwólé (1994) goes on to enumerate the earliest forms of women's resistance and struggles between 575 and 702 AD. Examples of these are the resistance of Kahina of Maghiels in North Africa against colonialists, and the reign of splendour of Queen Candace of Meroe. In Nigeria, there were also women who held active leading positions like the female Magajiya dynasty of Daura, of which Queen

Zaria (Queen Amina's junior sister) was very popular. Queen Inkpi was another female ruler among the Igala people during the seventeenth century. It was she who led her people to ward off the Nupe invasion of 1851. Among the Yorùbá tribe, Ilè-Olújì (Ondo State) had a political structure which accorded women of the town a great political recognition and participation. There was a male Ọba (king) as the head of the town, but the governing council consisted of both male and female chiefs. While there were male chieftaincy title holders like high chiefs Lisà, Jomọ, Ọdunwò, Ọsama and Ọsàsééré, there were their equivalent female title holders as high chiefs Lisà-Lòbùn, Ọdunwò-Lòbùn, Ọsàsééré-Lòbùn and Jomọ-Lòbùn (Zulu Ọfọlá 1994:13). In Ọgbómòşo, too, women are known to hold the title of *baálé* (village heads). "These women were the torchbearers of their family heritage of rulership" (Oyèrónké Oyèwùmí 1997:xiv).

Zulu Ọfọlá (1994) is of the opinion that it was from this high level chieftaincy position that powerful women have emerged in their own right as astute politicians to become Ọba (king) in Yorùbá towns. Examples of these are Ọọni Lúwo – a female king of Ilé-Ifẹ (Ọfọlá, Zulu 1994:13). Others like her, were kings Ọrómọtòniyùn, Jomijomi and Jepojepo who reigned in Ọyó (Fálétí 1972:59).

Late Madam Olúfúnmiláyò Ransome-Kúti was another great female leader among the Ègbá people of Yorubaland. She agitated and was able to dissuade the Ègbá Native Government from collecting tax from women (who were not government employees). Ransome-Kúti also formed the Nigerian Women's

Society in 1963 (Mba 1992). Bólánlé Awé (1992) has also pointed out that Lady Oyínkán Àbáyòmi, too, formed a women's political party in 1944 and that Charlotte Olájùmòké Obádán was another woman to be recognized, for she championed women's rights to a great extent.

Foreign infiltration in form of Islamic and Christian religions, which led to political domination (by males), however, caused havoc to the former political stance of Nigerian women. We say this because these two religions have male-dominating tenets. For instance, the colonial administrative set-up allowed for the establishment of a male house of traditional (African) rulers, but not for their female counterparts. (Bateye 2002:86-88). Examples of these are the Sole Native Authority (SNA) system in South-West Nigeria, the warrant chiefs system in the South-East of Nigeria and the Local Township Government in Lagos colony. Under the Sole Native Authority system in Abéòkúta, "no woman was ever a member of the advisory...council" (Nina E Mba 1992:139). The Aláké of Ègbáland never consulted the women, even when matters affecting them were being discussed. This was what enraged the Women's Union and led to the upheavals by the Ègbá women in 1948 (Bateye 2002:88), which was similar to the Aba Riots of 1929 in Igboland.

Peggy Sunday (1981:36) has revealed, too, that before the advent of Islam in Hausaland (which came as a result of the 1804-1810 Jihad), Hausa women had a measure of independence. They owned farms and were self-

employed. However, intensive Islamization has rendered the women voiceless, for they were relegated to servitude in Kulle (purdah).

What we are saying, in essence, is that African women did not learn self-assertion from the West as Oyeronkẹ Oyewumi (1997:ix) will want us to believe. Apart from that, the diversity in the mode of focus of the African women's struggles from that of the West can only be understood within (the highlighted) cultural contextualization. Also, colonialism, post-coloniality and Third-World or developing countries issues, also influence the differences. Most of the African women live in nations that are still experiencing political unrest, instability and poverty. It is this exigency that has shapened the African woman's consciousness, making her mobilization to be quite different from that of the Western woman.

2.4 Nomenclature of Feminine Struggles

People (not necessarily women alone) who are in pursuit of feminine liberation and self-assertion are generally referred to as 'feminists'. While some African women are contented with the tag, most of the others are not. Abena Busia is quoted by Kóláwọlé (1997:8) to have said:

I am comfortable with the term 'feminism'. If we concede the term feminism, we've lost a power struggle. As a strategy, we might be conceding grounds that we shouldn't Feminism is an ideological praxis that gives us a series of multiple

strategies ... what those strategies have in common is that the woman matters.

Busia here believes that any attempt to redefine 'feminism' by any means for any purpose, will lead to the loss of power struggle. In our own opinion, the struggle to unify the differences of groups of women from different cultural backgrounds, in the light of their reason for demanding their rights and exercising self-assertion, in order to bring about affinities among all women, will be in vain.

Women like Madhu Kishwa (1994:22-29), Mọlará Ògúndípè-Leslie (1994:11) and Chikwenye Okonjo Ògúnyẹmi (1985) are of the opinion that the tag to be given the African woman's struggle from patriarchal oppression and denigration must portray the African identity and cultural background. Madhu Kishwa (1994:23), for instance, says, "I resist the label 'feminism' because of its overclose association with the Western women's movement". This Indian woman finds feminism, as appropriated and defined by the West, a tool of cultural imperialism. She thus makes a distinction between nomenclatures which are "time-specific" and those that are "culture-specific". Time-specific nomenclatures, she claims, emanate under the pressures of the specific challenges of their time. Such nomenclatures come to be identified with the name of a particular thinker or political idealist like Marxism, Leninism, Maoism and Gandhism. Such philosophies, however, die with their leaders' demise or reify after achieving some of their immediate aims. After this, the philosophies

become mere ritual chants with deadening formulae used by their votaries to justify their own actions which may not even be logically related to the original ideology. "Nomenclatures that are culture-specific," Kishwa (1994) says, are "those that pervade many different movements in the form of an idea or tendency". Examples of these are anarchism, humanism and feminism. Feminism, to Kishwa (1994), was an outgrowth of the eighteenth century humanist thought in Europe and America, reinforced by philosophers who were utilitarianists and Marxists.

Despite an argument which, to us, is laudable, Kishwa (1994) has not come up with any nomenclature in spite of the fact that she identifies with the struggles against women's oppression and denigration, and claims to "have an ideology" of hers. We are of the opinion that to make a case for one's view, perspectives or policy, it is important not just to take a stand, but more essentially to choose an appropriate name for it, to aid recognition. It is laudable if a person or group of people can evolve an independent view if such an exercise is not merely for self-aggrandizement.

Recognizing African cultural idiosyncrasies, one of which is the fact that the family unit is the bedrock of other social relations, some African women have given tags like "Black Feminism" or "African Feminism" to the struggles of African women against patriarchy. However, the word 'feminism', with whatever attached tags, makes them unacceptable still. Alice Walker's (1983:xii)

definitions of both feminism and 'Womanism' call one's attention to some "salient ambiguities" (Kólawọle 1997:21). Walker says:

Feminism is the political theory that struggles to free all women: women of colour, working-class women, poor women, lesbians, old women – as well as white, economically privileged, heterosexual women. Anything less than this vision of total freedom is not feminism, but merely female self-aggrandizement.

A further reading of Walker's (1983) *In Search Of Our Mother's Garden* shows her classic definition of 'Womanism', as it portrays racial focus and specificity. Walker is seen to have taken cognizance of Nancy Leis (1974) and Nancy Tanner's (1974) recognition of African women's collective bonding and mobilization as unique traits. She (Walker 1983:3) goes further to describe a womanist as:

A black feminist or feminist of colour ... who loves other women sexually or asexually ... committed to survival and wholeness of entire people ... Womanist is to feminism as purple is to lavender.

Chikwenye Okonjo Ógúnyemí (1985) defines womanism as a global ideology for African women, embracing racial, gender, class and cultural consciousness. She says:

Black womanism is a philosophy that celebrates Black roots, the ideals of black life, while giving a balanced presentation of black womanhood. It concerns itself much with the Black sexual power hassle as with the world power structure that subjugates Blacks.

Madhu Dubey, according to Kōlawōle (1997:24), accepts the tag 'Womanism' as put forth by Walker. Dubey says:

The term Womanism coined by Walker ... as an attempt to integrate Black nationalism into feminism ... shares ... the objective of Black nationalist ideology.

Ògúndipè-Leslie (1994), too, has rejected the tag 'feminism'. To her, the tag is a 'kind of red rag to the bull of African men ... hegemonic ... somehow threatening.' She therefore found it expedient to adopt a "conciliatory position". She says:

I have since advocated the word "STIWANISM" ... My acronym for Social Transformation Including Women in Africa. (p.3)

If Ògúndipè-Leslie's ideal transformation of the African society includes women, or has them as central to the transformation, her tag can also be seen in the light of WOMANISM.

The African women, in the light of being mostly products of multiple subjugation, colonialism, tradition, neo-colonialism, patriarchy and gender imperialism, have advocated WOMANISM as a tag for their striving against oppression and denigration. To us, however, the *raison d'être* for African women's views is largely (apart from whatever other reasons) due to their conviction that the closely knit African family unit, as we mentioned earlier, is basic to their societal set-up. This societal set-up is, however, androcentric (to the detriment of these women) and they want a change whereby the family unit and its cultural idiosyncrasies (which need change, too) remain. The structuralist theory that the law of contradiction in things (Adeleke 1986:20) precipitates growth, development and progress in the society is evident here. Mao Tse-Tung (1966/67) as quoted by Adeleke (1986:20) a Marxist, says in his structuralist notion that:

Changes in society are due chiefly to the development of the internal contradictions in the society.

2.5 Gender and Socio-Economic Activities Among the Yorùbá

Whatever the state's ideology or level of economic development, women never control the ruling apparatus ... Women generally work in the worst paid, least skilled, most unsecured jobs. They exist on the economic margin of society, often surviving through

back-breaking, poorly paid labour in the informal sector or casual labour. (Parpat, J. 1989:25)

The Yorùbá society is predominantly an agrarian one wherein subsistence and cash-crop farming are practised (largely) with the aid of crude farm implements like cutlasses and hoes. Only recently has mechanized or perhaps semi-mechanised farming begun to be practised, and this is virtually limited to a small percentage of the society – the lettered farmers. There are basically three categories of farmlands in the Yorùbá agrarian set-up. The *oko etilé* (not too distant farm) where crops like vegetables, cooking condiments and ingredients are planted. In few cases, major food items like cocoyams and maize are also planted here, but because domestic animals like goats, sheep, rams and fowls can destroy them, such crops are cultivated near home only if there is a fence round the garden, otherwise the crops will not thrive very well. The second type of land cultivation is the *oko àrójẹ* (farm for subsistence crops). This type of farm is usually a few kilometers from the town or village. Here crops like yam, maize, beans, melon or plantains are planted. The third type of farmland is the *oko-egàn* (jungle farmland). Usually, cash crops like kolanut, rubber, coffee, cocoa and cotton are planted here. Food crops meant for sales or preservation for home use when out of season are also planted in *oko egàn*.

Being a job for which a lot of physical energy is exerted, coupled with the fact that women's impact concerning preparation of farmland (especially the *oko egàn*) for the planting season is not much, it is generally believed that farming is

a male-dominated job. The fact, however, is that, even if their physiology will not allow them to clear the bush, make mounds or weed them, the lot of haulage from the farm to the house and/or market, preservation (in the case of perishable produce), storing, processing and sales of these farm commodities, fall on the women after they might have single-handedly harvested them or joined the men in doing so. Perishable items that remain after subsistence consumption, and those that are originally planted for sales, are taken by the women to markets near and far away from the homes. Apart from these, women have to process some of the produce before they could be sold. This is why Yorùbá women engage in jobs like *epo fifò* (palm-oil making), *irú wíwé* (locust beans fermentation), *oṣe dúdú sise* (making local black soap) and *àdí sise* (making oil from palm kernels).

Apart from tilling the soil and as means of relaxation, the Yorùbá people usually have *àbòṣé* (part-time jobs) like leather works, gold smithing, calabash decorations, sculpturing, hair braiding, weaving or plaiting and cloth dyeing. Additional income is generated from engaging in these jobs, but more importantly, they are media through which the Yorùbá people express their inner-most feelings or emotions of joy, sadness, fear, expectations, beliefs and awareness. According to Ìrèlè (1991:53), these expressive arts "are capable of evolving a response, not merely communicating something". He (Ìrèlè) goes on to classify arts into three basic categories: literary, plastic and musical. The literary art, which could be oral or written, in form of prose, drama or poetry,

uses language as its means of expression. The plastic art is expressed by making use of solid materials, wood, stone and even the human body. Sound (organized into patterns) is the means of expression in the music arts.

Works in the art industry can be considered in the light of the sophistication of the equipment and technology used for their production or expression. Thus, we have traditional and modern arts, wherein both genders in the Yorùbá society have made and are making their contributions. We have, essentially, therefore, looked into women's role in traditional and modern art industries.

2.5.1 Women's Role in the Traditional Art Industry

The female gender's creative ability and aesthetic prowess in traditional literary, plastic and musical arts have been widely discussed by both male and female scholars. Scholars like Babalola (1966), Fáníyi (1975), Adéwoyè (1980), Àjàyí (1986), Oyèsakin (1989), Kóláwole (1997) and Sheba (1999) have discussed at length the various aspects of literary creativity of women, to the effect that several oral genres of the Yorùbá traditional literature belong solely to women. Among these are *Orin Ìrẹmọ* (lullaby), *Orin Ìyá Ìbeji* (the twins' mother's songs), *Orin Obítun* (maidens' songs during initiation to womanhood in Oñdó), *Ekún Ìyáwó* (the bride's nuptial chant), *Alámò*, *Olele* and *Àgò* (a dirge peculiar to the Òkà and Àkókó women). The functions of these songs and their peculiar features suit women. There are, however, some other known types of

poetry practised by both men and women but wherein "women are preferred to men" (Oyèsakin 1998:35). *Ràrà*, which is a type of social chant that demands a sonorous voice that suits women more than it does men – is a very good example. The general belief is that women do not play active roles in sacred cult literature. The works of scholars like Òpádòtun (1983), Ilésanmí (1989:81; 1991a; 1991b; and Ògúndípè-Leslie (1994:11) point to the fact that women play predominantly active roles in poems, songs or verses associated with Yorùbá gods, goddesses and legendary heroes and heroines, viz: *Sàngó Pipè*, *Èsè Ifá*, and *Oya Pipè*. Àjàyí (1986) and Oyèsakin (1992), cited in Oyèsakin 1998:34-47), point out the fact that there abound many Ifá priestesses in Òyó town and most of all that "Mópéénú, the legendary wife of Orò, was a reputed chanter of *Orò-Pipè*" – a chauvinistically guided secret. Women also render the *Èsà* (masquerade poetry), dance and sing (to interpret the mimetic sketches and revues) during the performance of *egúngún aláré* (masque dramaturges).

Women have also left, and till today they continue to leave their footprints on the sands of time in traditional secular music of the Yorùbá people. Examples of such women are late Olori Comfort Omógè of the Àsíkò music fame, Bàtìlì Àlàké and Sàlàwà Àbèni of Wàkà fame and Ìyá Aládùké, who has modified Dadakúàdà (of Ilorin origin) into a new dimension – *Seweḽe*.

The plastic arts, the field of Art where one is able to express the natural impulse to decorate and help to make beautiful the physical environment, is another area where women have been/are very active. The male gender is

known to use coarse, hard or rough materials for plastic arts. This is why they are found in fields like wood carving, stone shaping, metal fabrication, blacksmithing and furniture making. The females, on the other hand, use softer, smoother and lighter solid materials for their own plastic arts. Examples of these are pottery, cloth weaving, dyeing, bead-making, hair weaving, braiding or plaiting and yarn making. Women also make use of the human body itself in plastic arts as in the case of tattooing and body colouration with camwood or other types of dyes. While women's plastic arts like designing beautiful hair styles, tattooing and body colouration are done generally in almost all the different local areas of the Yorùbá society, it is worth noting here that some of these traditional vocations are peculiar to certain specific areas of Yorùbáland. For instance, *Àdirẹ* (cloths dyed with patterns) is most common among women in Abéòkúta and Òsogbo, cloth weaving (*aṣo-òkè hihun*) is popular with Òyó women, while women from Ìdófè in Ijèbú-Òde area and Ilorin, are known for pottery.

Women's roles in cultural art creativity have been undermined largely in the usual male/positive – female/negative attitude (Kóláwọlé 1997:64-69) of the patriarchal society. However, we are of the opinion that the women's oral genres in literary arts, their music and plastic arts are pointers to their creative ingenuity and dexterity in physical manipulative technology. Their oral genres, which are very rich in semantic and linguistic innovations, have been pointed out as weapons of self-expression and assertion which had a lot of power in making

women instrumental to defining the ethics and aesthetics around which the world operates (Micere Mugo, cited in James 1990:93). This implies, in essence, that the creative and re-creative ability of women has a very great impact in formulating the ethos that guides the corporate existence and interaction of both genders in the society.

2.5.2. Women in the Modern Art Industry: the Print Media

The modern art industry encompasses those aspects of art works which depend largely on scientific techniques for their performance, of which the print media is one. The media, among other things, include textbooks and information materials like dailies, weeklies, monthlies or bi-monthly newspapers and other written reports. Our major concern in this study is the literary materials of prose, poetry and drama in printed forms, using the Yorùbá language.

The Yorùbá language was reduced to writing around 1820 (Adéèboyèjé 1985:41). The first Yorùbá text, *Yorùbá Hymns*, was written by a male – Henry Townsend in 1848. Comparatively, it took the womenfolk over a hundred and thirty years after *Yorùbá Hymns* to write any literary piece; a play by Joláadé Fáwálé titled *Tení N Tení* in 1982. Although Joláadé Fáwálé followed her debut in quick succession with another play titled *KúSORÓ* in 1983, she is yet to write any other literary text again apart from these two. She, however, paved the way for women's participation in literary text publication. *Íyágbò I* and *Íyágbò II* were

also written by Ọmọ̀sùnlọ́lá Johnston in 1985. Today, we have literary texts like *O Sẹ̀yí Tán* (1995) *Ewí Àtátà* and *Ìgbà Lonígbàákà* by Olúyémisí Adébòwálé, *Eyin Àparò* (1998) and *Ròòó Re* (2002) by Àrìnpé Adéjùmò (2002) *Ta La Rí Bá W* (1990) by Délé Adégbèmi and *Hábà! Ojúolápe* (2002) by Fadékémi Adágbádá. Women also have few poems in recent anthologies³ like *Wáá Gbó* (2001) and *Kíké Olóbùró* (2003). While there abound many male prolific writers like D.O. Fágúnwà, Adébáyò Fálétí, Akínwùnmi Ìṣòlá, Ọlátúnjí Ọ̀pádòtun and Láwuyi Ogunniran, only Ọmọ̀sùnlọ́lá Johnson, Jọláadé Fáwálé, Olúyémisí Adébòwálé and Àrìnpé Adéjùmò have written as many as two or more literary texts. This lag, in terms of quantity rather than quality, has been attributed to the heavy burden of domestic activities coupled with the woman's official duty in the private or public sector, "the vulgar social out-look" (Oyesakin 1998:42) and the non-promotion of Yorùbá creative writings by social organizations. We wish to add that the negative patrifocal ethos in the old Yorùbá society, about females acquiring western education, also militated against their achievement in the print media. The general belief then (and even now, in some quarters) was/is that the parent gains nothing from sending females to formal schools, since such a girl will eventually end up in another man's household or "kitchen", as it were. Another reason is (patriarchal) oppression on the part of the book publishers. There are several cases of women (and fewer men, too) being deprived of their royalties and who may want to shy away from legal tussles. Apart from this, pirates find it easier to make illegal copies of books by female authors than those by males.

These issues, coupled with the fact that women appear to find it more difficult than men, to secure loans for use in the literary arts, print or electronic media enterprises (or in other business endeavours, for that matter)⁴, are enough to put a woman off creativity in the print or electronic media. We shall discuss this in details below, as we examine Táíwo Akinwándé as a case study for how female YHV producers raise capital.

2.5.3 Yorùbá Women in the Electronic Media: Yorùbá Home Video

Electronic media here imply the use of radio, television sets, the cinematographic screen, projectors, audio and video cassettes or compact discs for expressive arts like stage plays and feature films.

The Yorùbá women feature prominently in the Ogunde Dramatic Tradition. They co-acted with male artistes in television and radio drama series, playing the roles of mothers, wives, sisters, daughters, traders, queens, economic chieftaincy title holders, witches or prostitutes – all portraying the virtues and vices attributed to the female gender in a patriarchal setting. The dramatic tradition (the Ogunde's) also features women as members of their casts in films shot on celluloid and projected to cinematographic screens in cinema houses and halls. When the economy of Nigeria dwindled in the mid 70's, celluloid films (as we shall discuss later) went into recess, but the period coincided with the arrival of a new electronic technology-feature films shot on video for theatrical and home use. The contemporary era of video films for use

in the home heralds an avenue for women to show their filming ingenuity and musical prowess. There are no less than "eight hundred Yorùbá video tapes in the market today"⁶, a sizeable percentage of which were produced or co-produced and written by women. Apart from these, we found out in the course of this study that certain aspects of home video production are dominated by women. Some of these are film music, costuming and make-up. It is these female-dominated economic frontiers of Yorùbá literature, of which film is an aspect, that we attempt to explore in this study.

2.6.0 **Up-date on Women's Place in Yorùbá Drama**

Women have had to play very significant roles at the different stages of the startling rapid development of the Yorùbá drama. Where they were not the major anchor at these stages, they have had to substantially complement the efforts of the male gender. However, they (the women) have not been accorded, in our findings, their deserved space in the contemporary discourse on Yorùbá drama and, in fact, in other literary genres.

Under this section, we highlight the place of women at the different stages in the development of Yorùbá drama from its earliest period to the present times. This is, in effect, to foreground their place in the entertainment industry.

2.6.1 Traditional Festivals

Traditional festivals are periodic celebrations in honour of divinities and the commemoration of past heroes (Ògúndèjí 2002:4) and heroines, of which masquerading (a cult of the ancestors) is one. Other examples include Òsun festival, Ògún festival, Mọ̀rèmi festival, Ìgogo festival, Orósùn festival, Òkèèbàdàn festival, Òkòsí festival and Ońmòkà festival. All these festivals are celebrated among the various ethnic groups in Yorubaland.

During these festivals, the women are the ones who take care of the special delicacies to be eaten. In some cases, these women are even exempted from eating any of such dishes. Esibi festival in Àkúré where the women who prepare food for Olúáyé's (a god) sacrifice, but must not taste it (Sheba 1999:38-39), is an example of such festivals. The women also dance during these festivals. In most cases they go round the town dancing and singing as in Ìjá festival in Àkúré. The songs they sing in their more sonorous voice (if compared with that of men) are usually composed by these women (Ilésanmí 1991a and 1991b; Oyèşakin 1998; Sheba 1991:31-40). Examples of these are the Edi festival songs in Ilé-Ifè and the Òsun festival songs in Òşogbo. Art works like pottery, painting and decoration of the shrines for festivals are also done mostly by women. Most importantly, women also act as *arugbá* (she-who-carries-the-calabash) during some of these festivals. Here, she becomes a fortune-teller when the spirit of the ancestor, god or divinity being worshipped descends on her and she falls into a trance. In this trance-state, she foretells

the future to the devotees and relays messages to them. During this period, she is accorded all the awe, recognition and reverence due to the ancestral spirit she stands to represent.

2.6.2 Masked Dramatists

The Yorùbá masked dramatists known as *Alárinjò* – roving dancers (Adédèjì 1969), *Eégún Apidán* – masked magicians (Götrick 1984) and *Eégún Alaré* – performing masquerades (Ògúndèjì 2000) were itinerant masked performers who went about Yorubaland singing, dancing, displaying acrobatics, chanting and performing magical acts, as entertainment to spectators for their sustenance. We are adopting the tag *eégún alaré* for this study because it encompasses all the acts of the masked dramaturge mentioned above, as different forms of *eré* – the Yorùbá generic name for “performance and play” rather than *apidán* or *alárinjò*, which connotes mere magical performance and dancing respectively, alone. Apart from this, Adédèjì (1973a) has observed that his initial label – *alárinjò* (a person of easy virtue who goes about dancing) is derogatory and used by people who looked down on the performers.

The *Eegún-alaré* theatre, as opined by Adédèjì (1969) developed from the sacred cult of *egúngún* (an ancestral worship) during the reign of Aláàfin Ògbólú around 1590 as a result of a political crisis. At the initial stage, it was used for the purposes of satirizing and moral teachings to reprimand the members of the Òyómèsi ruling council for ganging up against the incumbent Aláàfin Ògbólú

when the latter sought their support for the relocation of Òyó town. In the later development of the theatre, it moved out of the palace court, to being performed in the village and town squares and market places of Yorubaland, becoming a means of entertainment for both the rich and the poor and as their (the performers') means of sustenance.

The troupe usually consisted of the actors (en masque), Bàtá instrumentalists, acrobats and the chorus. Initially, the royal wives (Olori), who were restricted to the palace, formed the chorus. When the theatre became a means of entertainment used round the towns and villages, the royal wives ceased to be singers, the role then fell on the wives, sisters or daughters of the troupe-leaders, who dominated the art (of chorusing), although the men, too, sang and chanted the *èṣà* – the egúngún poetic genre. This was imperative, for the troupe-leaders' female singers acted mostly as the chorus because other females were not joining the troupes as they were seen as jobless 'rogues and sturdy beggars' (Adédèji 1969:91).

The singers played a very vital role in the troupe – that of using songs to interpret and/or explain the performances or drama sketches of the masked entertainer to the spectators, without which such sketches might be misinterpreted (as most of the displays were mimetic), thereby losing their aesthetic values. In one show by the Ajóféèbó (he-who-dances-for-the-whites) troupe, two masked actors – one dressed as a woman and the other as a male-were presented. The 'man' brought out his (outrageously huge wooden carved)

manhood and pointed it at the 'woman' (with whom he had earlier on played romance and to whom he had given money). The woman was properly seen as a cheat rather than a novice when the chorus rendered the song below:

(From the 'woman')
 Mǎ rí mi fín o e
 Mǎ rí mi fín
 Èmi kíi segbé mà má rẹ
 Mǎ rí mi fín.

Do not insult me, hear
 Do not insult me
 I'm older than your mother
 Do not insult me

(From the 'man')
 'Gba to nígba pòùn-pòùn
 Ta lo ké sí?
 O wa níse he-he-he
 Okó tóbi

When you were collecting the pounds
 Whom did you call?
 Now, you are hollering
 Penis is too big

(Adédèjì, 1969:243)

Many of the troupes⁶ became very popular for their songs, which, in most cases, were led by female chorus leaders. An example of such is the case of Foyèké Àyòkà Àjàngilá of the famous Àjàngilá Troupe, whose chorus attracted a

lot of spectators to watch the performances of the troupe (Adédèji 1969:323). The wives of Ejòńgboro – another popular masked dramaturg from Ìkirè, were also other women who brought fame to their troupes for rendering beautiful choruses and who acted as interlocutors between the actors and the spectators.

2.6.3 The Ogunde Dramatic Tradition

This dramatic tradition is that founded by late Hubert Ogunde – a policeman turned itinerant dramatist, in 1946. Ogunde had his inspiration from having followed *Eégún aláré* like *Dáramójó Atètè* and *Èkùn Oko* in his childhood days all about the suburbs of Ìjèbú-Òde (Clark 1980:x), for Ogunde was from Òsòsà, a village of about five kilometers from Ìjèbú-Òde in Ogun State. Ogunde popularized his founded tradition that had the singing of an opening glee with acrobatics, staging feature plays that were initially religious but later secular and closing up with closing glees, as his *modus operandi*. This is a replica of the salute (Ìjúbà), sketches and revues (Idán) and closing displays (Idán àparelé) of the *Eégún Aláré*. Ogunde was soon joined in his itinerant mode of staging drama by other theatre practitioners like Kólá Ògúnmólá, Dúró Ladipò, Oyin Adéjobí, Ìṣòlá Ògúnṣolá, Moses Oláiyá Adéjùmò and a host of others. During this period, women continued to take care of the feeding and welfare of all the members of the troupes. Apart from this, women once again became more active in stage shows like they did/and are still doing, during the traditional festivals, unlike what occurred in *Eégún Aláré* troupes where they were mere

welfare officers and chorus singers. Although initially, Ogunde had problems in recruiting female performers due to the impression that people had of itinerant dramatists in those days, he was later able to employ "charming young girls as lady clerks" rather than as "paid actresses" (Clark 1980:4). His female performers needed not have worn masks carved with (pronounced) female features (as 'females' did in the *eégún alare* performances); they acted naturally, it no longer appeared a taboo for females to go on stage – they needed no *èkú* or *agò*⁹ to act. These women were given *cliché* roles of daughters, mothers, sisters or wives to act in most cases, although they sometimes played major roles⁹. They also continued with their former roles as welfare officers and singers (of opening and closing glees).

Two major things are worthy of note about women in the Ogunde Dramatic Tradition. The first is that, for the first time, women were paid for acting. This is because the late Hubert Ogunde paid the actresses he employed, salaries. Secondly, women made a great landmark in self-actualization as far as the entertainment industry is concerned; one woman dared to establish a troupe, when even men in the profession were given little or no recognition. The woman in question is the late Olúfúnmiláyò Ajayi. She was the proprietress of the Fúnmiláyò Ranco Travelling Theatre. Fúnmiláyò had both male and female employees in her troupe.

SIMBIAT ŞÓWQLÉ (EWÉDOYIN)

2.6.4 The Celluloid Film

Indigenous Nigerian (Yorùbá) celluloid films started with folkloric *Àjàní/Ògún* in 1976 by Olá Balógun (Ekwuazi 1981; Àlámù 1991; Adéléké 1995; Adésanya 1997). Women participated more than ever before in the production of Yorùbá films. This is made possible by the fact that once a film is shot at different locations, an actress can stay back at home (where it is patrilocally viewed as her proper place in the society), while the film is being exhibited in cinema houses or halls. She, however, played roles which were similar to those stage shows in the films. An error of oversight made by many scholars who have carried out studies on Yorùbá theatres and which we have discovered is the fact that they have not acknowledged that there is a female who produced a reversal film. She is Mrs Simbiat Sówolé – a trained catering and hotel Manager. Simbiat released *Ewédoyin* in 1990. It was produced by Zeros Film Production in London.

2.6.5 Home Video

In the contemporary video film era, the Yorùbá woman has cut a new image for herself. She is now seen acting roles which mirror her present social status and place in the national work force. Unlike in the past when most of the roles she played in casting were those of mothers, daughters, wives or traders, the present century is witnessing her as top-flight managerial executive, lecturer, medical personnel, judicial executive, engineer, senior technologist and

sometimes sole bread winner of the home-on the screen. Nevertheless, she still maintains her former roles as singer (now in film tracks) and welfare officer, as she did in the past. She is also found to be in charge of costumes, make-up and properties (props) in the course of producing YHV.

NOTES ON CHAPTER TWO

- 1 This is not peculiar to the human specie alone. The same applies to lower animals like goats, dogs, sheep, birds and fishes.
- 2 There are now many organizations founded by females in most countries of the world that are seeking liberation from the patriarchal ethos that has for long subjugated women. Examples of these are Women In Nigeria (WIN), The Nigerian Circle of Concerned Women Theologians, Tostan Organisation in Senegal, Association for the Advancement and Rights of Malian Women and the National Committee Against Excision in Burkina Faso.
- 3 There is no single poem by a female poet in all the poems contained in *Ewi Ìwòyí* (edited by Adeagbo Akinjogbin), the first Yorùbá anthology of poems. This is due to the fact that the very few women who were lettered then were not given the encouragement to submit their own poems.
- 4 See Òsobà (1990) on women in small-scale enterprises' access to credit.
- 5 An information given by Akindele Thomas of Vineyard Video Club, Ilishan-Remo.
- 6 Some of such troupes are the *Agbégijó* troupe from *Òsogbo*, *Olúfalé* from *Ìkirè*, *Àjànikorodùgbè* from *Òtà*, *Ajóféébó* from *Òyó*, *Akéréburú* from *Ìnìsà*, *Eléégún l'Áwé* from *Ìlorin*, *Lébé*, also from *Òyó* and *Eyèbà* from *Ibadan*. (Adédèjì 1969).

- 7 It is a taboo for a woman to wear these garbs of the masquerade, whether for cultic or entertainment purposes. A woman therefore has never been an *egúngún ará òrun kinkinkìn* (the being from far away heaven) or an *eégún alare* (the performing masked dramatist).
- 8 Females play major roles in plays like Dúró Ladipo's *Oba Kòso* and *Móremí*. They acted the roles of 'Òya', 'Òbà' and 'Òsun'.

CHAPTER THREE

WOMEN IN THE CREATIVE FORCE OF THE YORÚBÁ HOME VIDEO INDUSTRY

3.1.0 Creativity

Producing new and original ideas of things which may be imaginative or inventive is an inherent ability in all human beings. With their creative ability, things or ideas that are from newness of thought or expressions are made.

The ability to create things is not exclusive to any gender; it depends on the kind of training to which a person has been exposed, under what conditions and circumstances and the intelligence, the fortitude and the ability with which such a person is naturally endowed.

In the Yorùbá society, women are thought of as being creative in very limited areas like cooking, pregnancy and child care. In the preceding chapter, we have highlighted women's roles in farming and in the arts. In this chapter, we shall look at their creative contributions in the Yorùbá video film industry as film musicians and film producers. The various features of these areas of creativity are anatomized.

3.1.1 Women in Film Music

Songs accompanied by the various music ensembles like drums, guitar, piano, gong, bell, violin or percussion, make music. All these ensembles work

together to produce rhythm, melody and harmony. Music can, however, be made without singing vocally; using only musical instruments, as in the case of Jazz – and still be enjoyed. Music is synonymous with entertainment, although there are times when music is used for dirges and lamentations. In film production, music performs both psychological and aesthetic functions. As noted by Kracauer (1960:33), it has been suggested in some quarters that film music was used in early times to drown the noise of the film projectors used. This explanation seems untenable, because even when noiseless projectors replaced the noisy ones, film music has continued to be used. Kracauer (1960), however, opines that the sheer presence of music considerably increases the impact of visual images. It is not just an element of film itself; its vital function was to adjust the spectator psychologically to the flow of images on the screen. Aesthetically, Hanns Eisler says:

Picture and music, however indirectly or even antithetically, must correspond to each other ... besides serving as commutative or accompaniment ... is ... used as actual music and as the nucleus of films.

(cited by Kracauer 1960)

In essence, songs in films enliven the picture by evoking the more material aspects of reality. Kracauer (1960) has highlighted 'commentative', 'actual' and 'nucleus' as the three types of film music in existence.

Although films can be partially or totally mimetic and still be enjoyable (for silence at times can be used to create an effect on the audience), a good film in present times needs to attain a meaningful level of synchronization between

images and sound in order to arrest the total attention of the audience, "to establish association of ideas and carry on the development of thought ... to intensify the incidence of climax and prepare for further dramatic action" (Kurt, cited in Kracauer (1960). Meki Nzewi (1981) is therefore right to see music in theatre practice as a substructural frame-work for acting, that dramatizes the actions and celebrates the conclusion of the entire presentation or its episodes.

Ogundeji (1988:181ff) identifies two types of songs in theatre performance as *non-dialogised* and *dialogised*. While non-dialogised songs are used in creating atmosphere and are an integral part of the atmosphere, dialogised songs are used to highlight situations, thus giving room for reflection (on the part of the audience) at the climax of such situations.

Adeleke (1995:55-58) is of the opinion that film music or audio composition is of two types; *actual* (naturalistic) and *commentative* (non-naturalistic). That which emanates directly from the images in a film, which synchronizes and complements the action of the performers at a particular time, is the actual or natural sound. The natural sound is that which is heard as dialogues, songs, dirges, poems or chants by the performers in a film. Commentative sound, on the other hand, is the sound which emanates outside the action in the film and not directly from any of the cast. This type of sound is usually contrapuntal and asynchronous – it is not natural. Narration from a non-participating commentator (usually at the background in a film), and track-music laced into a film after

shooting, are examples of asynchronous sound. Such songs are usually relevant to the situation at hand.

Commentative sounds in form of songs, laced into a recorded film (Adeleke 1995:57), and non-dialogised songs in a theatrical performance (Ogundeji 1988) can be said to perform the same function – that of giving the viewer, or audience, as the case may be, a forum to reflect upon the climax of a situation or episode to which his or her attention is being drawn. Yorùbá theatrical performance in opera form is fast becoming history. As mentioned earlier, all that virtually remained of Yorùbá dramatic performances for now are films shot on video and traditional festivals.

Although there are a few times when songs can be used as dialogues in romantic YHV like *Yemi My Lover*, or used in trading words in films themed on co-wives' rivalry like *Agbo Òdájú* or *Ilé Olá*, what is in vogue for production of YHV is lacing them with songs by professional (film) musicians after film shooting and editing.

The quest under this section is to examine the commentative sound produced in YHV by women – popularly known in filming parlance as 'sound tracks'. This is an aspect of the film industry where we have discovered in the course of this study that women are making great landmarks like they did with songs in traditional festivals, in the Eégún Alàré shows and the stage-plays. Tèmitópé Obáyomí Àlàbí, Solá Ilòrí, Salome Èkétúndé, Ayò Ewebiyi, Tóyin Yomi-Ògúnmólá, Kíkè Wèmímó, Ayò Májèmú, Tópé Lawal and Aminat Adégúnjú are

some of the women well known for Yorùbá film music. However, of all these film singers, Temitope Obáyomí Àlàbí is the most popular. When we made enquiries about music in YHV films from viewers and artistes, her name was always the first to be mentioned, and they refer to her as 'Tópé Àlàbí-Oore tí ò common'¹.

3.1.2 Tópé Àlàbí's Film Music as a Case Study.

We found out in the course of this study that Tópé Àlàbí documents her songs, for she made available to us some exercise books wherein most of the songs she sang were written. Going through them, we found many versions of some film music songs written, cancelled and re-written until they must have reached her desired perfection (see appendix V). She said:

Mo máa n kọ àwọn orin mi sílẹ̀. Tí ìmísí orin kan bá ti wá, iyẹn léyìn tí mo ti ka script yẹn dáadáa, máà wá máa ẹ̀ àtúnṣe tó bá yẹ síi titi ...

I write down my songs. As soon as the inspiration comes after I must have studied the script of a film in-depth then I make the necessary corrections and adjustment still

**SELF WITH THE ÀLÀBÍS
GOING THROUGH TQPÉ'S MANUSCRIPTS.**

She then takes the written songs to a recording studio where she sings and has the songs recorded in audio tapes. It is the recorded audio cassette tapes that she sells to the producer of a YHV film for an agreed amount. The minimum number of music tracks in most YHV films, according to Tópé, is five, and she charges an average of ten thousand naira (N10,000) per track. Tope claimed to have sung into about one hundred and fifty-two (152) YHV as at June, 2003.

3.1.2.1 Caption Songs

To begin a feature film, songs are usually sung to attract the attention of the audience or viewers, a reminiscence of the opening glee of the Ogunde Dramatic Tradition. However, unlike what Ógúndéjì (1988:181) points out, these types of songs are intrinsically part of the plots of the YHV; giving a gist of what is likely to be the major theme of the poem.

Tópé calls such film music – caption songs. We found out that she uses them in almost all the films into which she had sung, and, as it is, it is usually the first music track in the film. In *Enikan ò Layé* (no one can monopolise life) written and produced by Rótímí Mákíndé, the caption song goes thus;

Eré àwòkógbón gbòde o
 A gbé tuntun dé
 E fara balè ké e wòran ayò
 Ará ilé
 A gbéré aláyò de ò
 ENIKAN Ò LAYÉ

A gbéré aládùn de ò
ENÌKAN Ò LAYÉ

An educative play is here
We have brought something new
Relax and watch a joyous play
People at home
We have brought a joyous play
ENÌKAN Ò LAYÉ (No one can monopolise life)
We have brought an interesting play
ENÌKAN Ò LAYÉ (No one can monopolise life)

The second person plural pronoun 'e' in line three indicates that the film has the viewers' enjoyment 'in mind'. The viewers are asked to relax and watch the film – "an educative one." Another example of a caption song is the first music track in the YHV – *Iséjú Marun*, written and produced by Bóláji Amusan (Baba Latin). The song is a beacon to men who run after ladies to come and learn a lesson:

Olójú kòkòrò
Olójú kò-mù-ò-lọ
Wáá gbó
E jé kí tilé oge
Kò tógée je

You, the greedy type
You, who must hold unto all you see
Come and hear this
Be contented with
What you have at home

The third line is a direct call to the viewers to come, watch, enjoy and learn from the film – a film though intended to be watched by all, but more especially for 'he who must hold to all he sees'.

3.1.2.2 Thematic Songs and Social Comment

What usually follow Topé's caption song are commentative thematic songs. They are somewhat introductory in nature in that they are comments that give hints on what the major theme of the YHV being watched is likely to be. In *Enikan ó Layé*, she says:

Enikan ò layé
 Sée mò pènikan ò layé
 Àbí ẹ ò gbà pènikan ò layé
 Àbùrò tó lówó sebí torí ègbón ni
 Egbón tó bá dára fún
 Torí àbùrò ni
 Bó bá ń dára fún un yín o
 Torí ẹbí yín ni

No one can monopolise life
 Don't you know that no one can monopolise life
 A junior one is made rich because of his senior
 A wealthy senior is made so for the benefit of his juniors
 If you are making it in life
 It is because of the members of your family

This track gives the viewers a hint that there is likely to be a rich man who is likely to be selfish towards his siblings or relations. The man is likely to come to a disastrous end as no man is an island for 'the world is not owned solely by a single man', as the Yorùbá maxim, 'Ilé ayé kii se ti enikan' implies.

This is exactly true of king Adéwálé who refuses to forgive Wunmí – his estranged wife. Wunmí has an illicit affair with Adésolá – her brother-in-law, a taboo in the Yorùbá sociological set-up. A junior brother or relation younger in age can inherit a dead brother's or relation's wife and as such be free to copulate with her – but not when such a senior brother or relation is alive. All the members of the royal family and the religious leaders in Ìgògò town beg the king, but he refuses to listen. He banishes Wunmí, Adésolá and Adéfémi – the child that results from the illicit affair from the palace. When all efforts to make Adéwálé see reason fail, Bàbá Baálé, one of the residents in the palace, becomes annoyed and says:

À n bẹ́ ó, o lóò gbà
 Kí lojú ò tí, ri rí ...?
 Eni tí èyín n' pè ní bàbá yen
 Sé ó lè se ní? Èmi lè mí n' sọko fun 'yàa yín.

We are appealing to you, you are adamant.
 What is new under the sun?
 The person you call 'father', can he perform?
 It is I who sleep with your mother.

Bàbá Baálé slumps and dies as he has leaked a secret to which he had sworn to an oath. Adéwálé is shocked to know that he himself is a bastard. He could not have had any claim to the throne if not for Bàbá Baálé who had to sleep with his (Adéwálé's) mother to procreate a heir for his impotent-prince friend.

In *Ìsẹ́jú Marun*, the second track music is:

Olórún sọ mi o

Elédàá gbà mi o

Kíwà mi má kó jamba bá mi

God protect me

Let me not put myself into trouble

You creator, guard me

Let my conduct not put me into trouble

This song is a supplication to God whereby the singer is imploring Him to save her (the singer, for the benefit of the actor concerned) from self-destruction. The audience can (by this song) foresee the case of a man whose action is likely to put him into trouble. This is exactly the case of Adébáyò in the film. Adébáyò is a womanizer. He once raped Bísí – his friend's secretary. For many years after this incident, Adébáyò begins to get into one problem after the other. His only son dies and he, too, falls seriously ill. All attempts to cure him through orthodox medical means fail and he is asked by the doctor to seek after traditional assistance from native doctors. A lot of money is wasted on Adébáyò

to get him healed, but it is of no avail. Later, a native doctor asks him to cast his mind back and try to recall if he had forcefully taken anything from a woman. He remembers how he raped Bísí. He has to make atonement for his behaviour before he can have peace for Bísí had died while delivering the baby that resulted from the rape.

3.1.2.3 Scenic Songs

Scenic songs are also sung by the soloist, Tópé Àlàbí. These are songs that enhance the full meaning, interpret or pass comment on a particular scene. Since the contemporary YHV is not operatic, it is not important to lace every scene with asynchronous sound in form of music. Only important scenes wherein the acts are pointers to the major themes or important sub-themes, are usually laced with music. In such cases, the songs run parallel with the pictures. This duplicates what the scene is meant to impact, for the repetition drives home the message(s) of the film. In *Enikan ò Layé*, when Kíké – Adénikèè's shop-minder enters her (Adénikèè's) sitting room and Báyo (Adénikèè's husband) smacks his lips with his tongue in imagined ecstasy, Tópé Àlàbí sings as when a Yorùbá folk-tale is interjected with a song:

O wá dalápatà omoge
 Rántí omọ eni tí iwọ ọ se
 Ayé ò tọ bí òpá ibon
 Àlòrì layé
 Ó ní lọ síwá sééyìn ní

You are now a maidens' butcher
 Remember the child of whom you are
 The world is not straight like the stem of a (dane) gun
 This world is like a fresh shrub stem
 It dangles back and forth

When Báyò attempts to grip Kiké while she is making the bed, the latter pushes him away so vigorously that he falls to the floor. Tópé sings:

Yọkọlú yọkọlú
 Kò ha tán bí?
 Ìyàwó gbóko sánlè
 Okó yóké
 Yọkọlú yọkọlú
 Kò ha tán bí?
 Very shameful, shameful
 What's more?
 Wife floors her husband
 The husband develops a hunch
 Very shameful, shameful
 What's more?

Also in *Ìséjú Marun* (Five Minutes), when Báyò's legal wife – Agbéké – is about to die (for an action she is innocent of), Tópé sings:

Àánú ẹ mí fáya yín
 E kóbá ará ilé
 E kóbá ará oko

Jéjé nijògbòn jókòò
 È mí fà á tu
 Bómọdé bá peye
 A dá je é
 Bómọdé bá peku
 A dá je é
 Bómọdé bá peku
 A dá je é
 Ojọ tó bá pàrò gìdìgbà o
 A gbé e wálé

I pity your wives
 You endanger the people at home
 Even outsiders are not spared
 Trouble sits gently
 You are up-rooting it
 When a child kills a bird
 He eats it alone
 When he kills a rat
 He eats it alone
 The day he kills the robust (dreadful) cat fish
 He surely will bring it home.

A combination or integration of synchronous and asynchronous sounds is also possible in film music. This feature is evident in the music tracks composed by Tópé Àlàbí. In *Àràkengé*, she is the one who composed and sang the lines below, which are mimed by Moji Afoláyan:

Mo ti ròkun erémi

Mo ti ròsà rí

Mi ò rírú ẹ rí

I have been to the farthest part of the sea

I have been to the ocean before

I have never seen anyone like you

3.1.2.4 **Orchestration**

The musical accompaniment that Tópé uses when singing into films depends, according to her, largely on whether such YHV is thematically based on contemporary issues or on historical and traditional matters. For the former, this soloist uses keyboard – basically and employs professional male drummers (*àyàn*) to beat drum ensembles like *Gáangan*, *Bàtá*, *Sèkèrè*, *Kànnàngó* or *Gúdùgúdù*.² for the latter. For instance, while trumpet and keyboard are used in *Ewúro*, *Bàtá*, *Dùndún*, and *Gáangan* are used in *Aboré*, a thematically traditional YHV.

3.1.2.5.0 **Language**

Basically, Tópé Àlàbí uses the standard form of the Yorùbá language for her composition and rendition of film music. Going through her scripts, we found that what is of paramount importance to her is to put her creations into writing immediately an idea comes into her mind so that she will not forget it.

She appears less concerned about using current/operating orthography since, according to her:

Yorùbá tí èmí mò ọ́n kọ niyẹn o. Èdè Yorùbá tí wọ́n ní kọ ní school bayii tí yàtò sí èyí tí a kà nínú iwé tele. Nígbà tí mi ọ́ kúkú ní gbé orin tí mo compose fún anybody láti mark, bí ó bá tí yé èmi tí mo kọ nńkan mí ... Nńkan tí producer fẹ́ fún owó tó san ní orin film tí mo ba kọ sí cassette, tó sì bá isèlẹ́ inú film náà mu.

That is the Yoruba I know how to write. The Yoruba Language being learnt in the school now is different from what we read in the text books before. Since I am not submitting my composition to anyone to mark, as long as it is explicit to me as the writer ... All a producer requests from me for the fees I charge is a cassette containing songs that are germane to the theme of his/her film.

Inability to write with appropriate Yorùbá orthography when composing has, however, not impaired Tópé's creative ingenuity. This popular soloist makes use of traditional materials in her compositions; she also uses different stylistic devices and figurative expressions. These are easy for her to do since the basis for the currently used Yorùbá orthography is for words to be written with the tone marks as they are pronounced without consonant clusters. (Since Tope's work is verbal communication, she has violated no rule.)

3.1.2.5.1 Use of Traditional Materials

Many renowned Yorùbá literary and performing artistes like poets and musicians are known to have had their inspiration from the inexhaustible Yorùbá oral traditional literary convention. The oral materials so gathered are used as background for their work or are patterned after the literary heritage from which they derive. Three basic traditional materials which Tópé uses for composition are *Òwe* (proverbs), *Orin-Ìbílẹ̀* (traditional songs) and *Oríjì* (incantations).

3.1.2.5.2 Proverbs (Òwe)

Proverbs among the Yorùbá people reflect their world-view. Although proverbs are veiled, they are nevertheless latent with moral intent which reflects the norms and values of their society (Beier and Gbádámósí 1959:60-64). Proverbs are words of wisdom which originated from the observation of nature and human relations. Among the Yorubá people, the elders are the custodians of proverbs (Olatunji 1984:17). If a young person speaks and laces his/her discourse with many proverbs, such a youth is referred to as *omo ọ̀dọ̀ àgbà* (A child who stays in the company of elders).

Tópé is a very good example of an *omo ọ̀dọ̀ àgbà*. This is because she uses a lot of Yorùbá proverbs correctly. In some cases, she selects a Yorùbá proverb that befits the major theme of the YHV she wants to sing into. This becomes the major base of her songs, which other songs hinge on. A very good example of this is a Yorùbá proverb which states that *Adùn ní gbéyìn ewúro*

(Sweetness is the aftermath of eating bitter-leaf) and *Ewúro làgbà igi, igi gbogbo* (The bitter-leaf is the eldest among all trees; let all other trees accord bitter-leaf its due respect). Requested to sing into the film *Ewúro*, Tope capitalizes on the above proverbs and sings;

Adùn ní gbèyin ewúro
 Ewúro ò Ewúro
 Adùn ní gbèyin
 Ewúro tó korò
 Bó bá korò lówurò
 A dùn yùngbà tó bá dalé
 Oore korò losàn-án
 A dùn yùngbà tó bá dalé
 Tí a bá je kikan, a ó je didùn
 Tá a bá je kikan, a ó je didùn
 Edumàrè sayé mi bíi tewúro
 Káyé mi kó le è dùn nígbèyin
 Ní mo fé
 Ohun tó bá dùn lówùrò, inú wọn
 Ó lè má dùn tó bá dalé
 Ewúro làgbà igi o
 Ewúro làgbà igi
 Igi gbogbo bọwò féwúro
 Ewúro làgbà igi
 Àgbè tó gbinkà
 Kó ní káa lójó kan
 Á a se wáhalà kó tó kobè
 Eni tó bá se áá ní je

Adùn ní í gbèyìn ewúro
 Oore korò ọ̀sàn-án
 A dùn yùngbà tò bá dalé

Sweetness is the end-result of eating bitter-leaf
 Bitter leaf, oh bitter-leaf
 Sweetness is the end-result of eating bitter-leaf
 If it is bitter in the morning
 It will be sweet by evening
 Good deeds are bitter in the day-light
 They are usually sweet in the evening
 If we eat what is sour, we shall eat that which is sweet
 God, let my life be like that of bitter-leaf
 so that my life will be enjoyable in the end;
 That is my desire
 Whatever is sweet in the morning
 May not be sweet in the evening
 Bitter-leaf the eldest among trees
 All trees accord bitter-leaf its due respect
 The farmer who plants maize
 Will not reap the harvest in a day
 He will labour to make mounds
 He who works shall eat
 Sweetness is the end-result of eating bitter-leaf
 Good deeds are bitter in the day-light
 But sweet in the evenings.

The same thing applies to *Enikan ò Layé*. The Yorùbá people will say *Igi kan kii dàgbó se* and *Ilé ayé kii se tenikan*, meaning 'A tree does not make a forest' and 'This world is for everybody'. With this she sings:

Enikan o layé
 Sè e mò pènikan ò layé
 À bé è ò gbà pènikan ò layé?
 Àbùrò tó lówó sebí torí ègbón ni
 Ègbón tó bá dára fún o
 Torí àbùrò ni
 Bó bá ñ dára fún un yin o
 Torí ebí yín ni

This world can not be monopolised
 Don't you know that it can not?
 A junior one is made rich because of his senior
 A wealthy senior is made so for his junior ones
 If you are making it in life
 It is because of the members of your family

Apart from this pivotal use, this singer also uses proverbs during renditions to define situations, or for didactic purposes. In *Ìsẹ́jú Marun*, she warns men who run after women to desist from such acts and be contented with their wives.

She sings:

Olójú kòkòrò
 Olójú u kò-mú-ò-lo
 È je ki tilé oge
 Kó tó oge é je

You greedy one
 Who must own all he beholds
 Be contented
 With what you have

The last two lines are creative extractions from a Yorùbá proverb that;

Didùn ló dún tán nì bá òrẹ̀ jẹkọ
 Tilé oge tó oge é je

It is only friendliness that makes one
 Eat solid pap with a friend, everyone
 Has enough to eat in his/her house

Olójú kòkòrò literally means "insect eyes". It is a metaphoric tag used among the Yorùbá people for a greedy person, comparing him/her with 'kòkòrò' (insect) who must carry each speck of edible items that comes its way, for immediate or later consumption. In the same film, another proverb is evident in the song:

Àánú ẹ̀ mi fáya yín...
 Bọmọ́dé bá peye
 A dá a je
 Bọmọ́dé bá peku
 A dá a je
 Ojọ to ba pàrọ gidigbà
 A gbe e wálé

I pity your wives
 If a child kills a bird
 He eats it alone

If he kills a rat
 He eats it alone
 The day he kills the robust (dreadful) cat-fish
 He brings it home (to his parents)

In original (traditional) version, the sixth line above is sung:

Ojó tó bá pa òràn gòdògbò
 The day 'kills' a serious trouble

Tópé is being creative here. She changes *òràn gòdògbò* to *àrò gidigba* (big cat-fish) in order to be in consonance with *eye* (bird) and *eku* (rat) used in the second and fourth lines, which are also names of animals. Only the first line of this song is not a proverb. The remaining lines consist of one Yorùbá proverb which tells of youths getting away with minor exuberance without the knowledge of the parents, but will run home in the case of complicated problems. The proverb is to warn promiscuous men to desist from their act so that they may not put their wives at home in trouble.

In *Àlámú Sèniyàn* (*Àlámú* is a nice man), the Yorùbá aphorism that *Ilè ní je èniyàn* (The earth devours human beings) and *Igi tó bá tó kii pé nígbó* (The straight tree do not stay long in the forest) are creatively sung as:

Ó mà se o
 Ilè ní jèniyàn
 Igi tó dára kii pé nígbó

Èniyàn tó sunwòn
 Ojú rè a ríyọnu
 Ká pé láyé
 Kojú èni má ribi
 Eniyan a múkan

What a pity
 The earth devours human beings
 Straight trees do not stay long in the forest
 A good person
 Will experience troubles
 To live long or
 Face the travails of life
 One has to choose one.

In the same film, the proverbs; *A kii lé ọmọ burúkú fẹkùn pa je* (A child is not given to a tiger as a meal just because he misbehaves), and *Ọgèdè dúdú kò yá bù sán, ọmọ burúkú kò yá lù pa* (Unripe plantain is not appealing for eating, neither is it easy to club a naughty child to death) are composed into a song by Tópé thus;

Ọmọ kii burú titi
 Ka lé e fẹkùn kó pa á je
 Ọgèdè burúkú ò yá bùsán
 Ọmọ burúkú kò ya lù pa
 Ọbí e sówà a yin
 Ké e má pàdánù gbogbo ọmọ

A child can not be so naughty
 That we send him/her to a tiger to be eaten
 Unripe plantain is not edible eat
 A troublesome child is not easy to kill
 Parents, watch your conduct
 So that you do not forfeit the value of all your children

The two proverbs are to warn parents to be careful about the way they treat their children who are not well-behaved or who do not live up to their (the parents') expectation.

3.1.2.5.3 Folk Songs (Orin Ìbílẹ̀)

Folksongs are the indigenous or traditional songs of a people. Usually they have little or no features of foreign influence. They are in most cases used functionally for folktales, festivals, dirges, political campaigns and at other social gatherings. Clapping or banging of the feet is usually the musical accompaniment of the Yorùbá folk-songs, except in present times when sophisticated musical ensembles like drums, piano, guitar and keyboard are used, when they (the folksongs) are being used as background for pop songs or when their instrumental (modern) versions are being sung.

To know these songs, their traditional uses, and to be able to use them adaptively for situations in Yorùbá films, is another quality which makes us to refer to Tópé earlier as an *omọ ọ̀dò àgbà*. This is because at present, a great dwindling in the knowledge of and the love for the customs and traditions of the

Yorùbá race is being witnessed among the Yorùbá youths. Tópé is well known for using a lot of folksongs in her renditions. In *Àlámù Sèniyàn*, for instance, she sings:

Mo gbinlá mi sóko
 Mo gbinkà mi sóko
 Ewùré iyá fi je
 Àgùtàn iyá fi je
 Èmi ò mohun iyá pé mo se

I planted my okro in the farm
 I planted my maize in the farm
 Mother's goat ate them up
 Mother's sheep ate them up
 I do not know what mother says my offence is

The original version of the folksong above is;

Mo gbinlá mi sóko
 Mo gbinkà mi sóko
 Ewùré Àró fi je
 Àgùtàn Àró fi je
 Èmi ò mohun Àró pé mo se

I planted my okro in the farm
 I planted my maize in the farm
 Aro's goat ate them up
 Aro's sheep ate them up
 I do not know what Aro says my offence is

The song is that of a person in a state of distress or confusion. He/she feels cheated, in need of a person who can suggest a solution, for it is not easy to have toiled and laboured to plant okro and maize on the farm, only to have them consumed by another fellow's domestic animals when they are ready for harvest. The result must surely be very devastating. The song reflects Mojísolá's state of mind at the point where Tópé sings it. This is because Fadélera (Àlámú, Mojísolá and Oláiywólá's mother) is the cause of the predicaments that befall her children in *Àlámú Sèniyàn*. Due to her over-zealousness about her children's welfare, she goes to see a herbalist whose charms have negative effects on Mojísolá, Àlámú and Oláiywólá's fortunes. At this point in time, Mojísolá hears of the death of her shop-keeper on the television. The shop-keeper dies in a plane crash en route Dubai while shopping for Mojísolá. Mojísolá is sad and confused, for the money used for the shopping is a loan given to her to resuscitate her business which was collapsing. Few days back, the ship bringing her husband's vehicles from Germany into the country (for sales) was wrecked, without any body on board surviving. It is therefore very accurate for Tópé to sing such songs to highlight Mojísolá's situation. Not just this alone, in place of:

Èmi ò mọhun Àró pé mo ẹ

I do not know what Àró says my offence is

wanting to drive home the fact that it is their mother (iyá) who causes all their problems, Tópé tactically sings.

Èmi ò mọhun *iyá* pé mo se

I do not know what mother says my offence is.

This is because if Fadélera had submitted to the will of Olódúmarè (God) and allowed the *àyánmó* (destiny) of each of her children to take its natural course, it would have been well for all of them.

Another Yorubá folksong sung by Tópé can be heard in *Ewúro*. She sings thus:

Yèèpà mo ti ròkun lọ fọṣọ
 Yèèpà mo ti ròsà lọ fọṣọ
 Ìgbà mo délé mi ò bénikan
 Ojú mí mí somi gbérégbéré.

Oh! I went to the sea to wash clothes
 Pity, I went to the ocean to wash clothes
 I met nobody on my return
 Tears flow ceaselessly from my eyes.

The song is a dirge. It is peculiar to the Ègbá people of Abéòkúta in Ogun State.

When sung in the Ègbá dialect, it goes thus:

Yèèpà mo ti rògù la fọṣọ
 Ó se, ó pò odò Ògù re mo lọ
 Igbi mo délé mi ò bénikan
 Ojú mi mí somi gbérégbéré

Oh! I went to Ògù(n) river to wash clothes
 Pity, what a shame, I went to Ogu(n) river
 I met nobody on my return
 Tears flow ceaselessly from my eyes.

Linguistically, the Ègbá people do not pronounce the nasal vowel *ù* that follows the 'g' consonant in their dialect. Other examples are:

Ṣìgù (pawpaw) not Ṣìgùn
Igù (vulture) not Igùn
Oògù (medicaments) not Oògùn
Gìgù (length) not Gìgùn
Ségu (a male's name) not Ségun

This is why river Ògùn (in Abẹ̀òkùta) is referred to as *Odo Ògù* in the song. Tópé recreates the song by changing words like *Ògù* to *Òkun* (sea) and *Òsà* (lagoon) and *Ìgbì* (when) to *Ìgbà* (Standard Yorùbá form) in order to generalize the 'ownership' of the song among all Yorùba (viewers), so as to make it (the song) appealing to all. She sings the song at the point where Wálé – who had gone round the whole town in an attempt to secure a loan for Rántí (his junior sister's) surgical operation, comes back to find Rántí dead. Tears flow ceaselessly from Wálé's eyes. Rántí was the only relation he had, moreover their parents are dead. What must have pained Wálé most is that he needed to leave Rántí alone in the hospital if he is to get the money for the operation. It is not

as if he left her to go and play or enjoy frivolities, it was a call to duty. Alas, his having answered the call brings no favourable result, it is a labour in vain. The situation is exactly like that of the person in the folksong above, who dutifully takes the dirty clothes at home to the Ògùn river for washing, only to come home to meet nobody, all beloved ones dead. It is even possible that it was the soiled clothes of the beloved ones that he went to wash!

3.1.2.5.4 Incantations (Ọfọ)

Ọfọ is a verbal aspect of magical art among the Yorùbá. It has a restricted poetic form, the utterance of which is cultic and mystical in nature. These utterances date back to immemorial antiquity and underlying them is the Yorùbá belief in a dynamic vital force immanent in varying degrees in all animate and inanimate things (Olátunji 1984:140). Mere utterance, or its combination with compounding of herbal medicine made from plants and objects, is believed to have the power of making mysterious things happen.

Tópé uses Ọfọ in her filmic compositions. However, the incantations were not to make anything mysterious happen, but rather to drive home factual points by implied comparisons. In *Ewúro*, when Wálé and Rántí are going about the streets fending for themselves, Tópé sings;

Orí lejá fi ní labù já
Orí lakàn fi ní kàn 'rókò

The fish uses its head to swim through the river
 The crab uses its head to knock the mahogany tree

These lines are incantations, the type used when one desires to make a headway in life. The comparison here is between the fish and the crab's heads and the heads of Wálé and Ranti. The desire is that as the two animals' heads make way for them, such should happen to the two indigent kids. Another example can be heard in a track in *Enikan Ò Layé*, when the king is fuming with rage over his wife's illicit affair with his (the king's) junior brother, Tópé sings thus:

Èrò pèsè o láàfin ...
 Aláṣe èkejì òrìṣà
 Èrò pèsè ni tigbín

Let there be peace in the palace
 Your royal highness
 Peaceful tranquillity is the nature of the snail

In Yorùbá esoteric and traditional medical practice, the snail is usually used as an antidote for psychic and physical attacks or to seek for peace and reconciliation (Adeniji 1980:74-76). The comparison here is the peace and relief that a person formerly attacked or incurring someone else's anger experiences after good health or the desired peace is achieved, with the peaceful and calm manner of the snail, as it is desired in the palace, if only the king will calm down.

3.1.2.6.0 Stylistic Devices

Features like repetition, word-play, parallelism and tonal counter-point are very common in Tópé's renditions. Her dexterous style of using these features makes her film music unique. We found out that this is what endears her most to her fans.

3.1.2.6.1 Repetition

Repetition is a device which poets and singers use to emphasize and intensify a point or fact which they intend to stress. Tópé usually repeats some particular lines of her songs in order to emphasize the major themes of the YHV she sings into, so that the message of the film is caught by the viewers. Sometimes, she repeats a particular chorus after each of the music tracks in a film. For instance, she repeats the chorus below at the end of almost all the music tracks in *Ewúro*:

Adùn níí gbèyìn ewúro
 Ewúro tó korò
 Bó bá korò lòwúrò
 A dùn nígbèyìn tó bá dalé
 Oore korò ọsàn-án
 A dùn yùngbà to ba dalé

Sweetness is the end result of eating bitter-leaf
 Bitter-leaf which is bitter
 If it is bitter in the morning

It will be sweet at the end in the evening
 Kindness is bitter in the afternoon
 It is very sweet (rewarding) in the evening.

Again, the song below is repeated as many as five times in the film – *Àlámú Sèniyàn*:

È bá mi kí Àlámú
 Ó mà sèniyàn ò
 Àlámú o ó sèniyàn
 Ọmọ ire tá fi mi sàdúrà fọmọ
 Àlámú o ó sèniyàn

Greet Àlámú for me
 He is a nice man
 Àlámú, oh! A nice man
 A child so good that his type is desired as a child
 Oh! Àlámú is a nice man

This feature is also found to be evident in the YHV – *Ènikan Ó Layé*, where the chorus:

A gbéré aláyọ de o
 Ènikan ó layé

We have brought an interesting play
 This world can not be monopolized

is repeated several times in the course of the film.

Apart from repeating choruses, Tópé also uses full lexico-structural repetition of sentences in her music lines. For example, in *Àlámú Sèniyàn*, she sings:

Àwa o mọhun iyá pé a ẹ

Àwa ò mọhun iyá pé a ẹ

Àwa ò mọhun iyá pé a ẹ

We do not know what mother says our offence is

We do not know what mother says our offence is

We do not know what mother says our offence is

Tópé also repeats sentences with intervening lines in-between. For example, in the film mentioned above, she sings:

È bá mi kí Àlámú

Ó mà sèniyàn o

Àlámú o ó sèniyàn

Ọmọ ire ta fi mí sàdúrà fọmọ

Àlámú o ó sèniyàn

Greet Àlámú for me

He is a nice man

Àlámú, oh! A nice man

A child so good that his type is desired as a child

Oh! Àlámú, what a nice man.

The third and fifth lines above are repetitions, with lines one, two and four intervening them.

A similar type is also evident in *Abéré Alhaja* where this singer sings:

Ení su ó gbàgbé
Abéré àlàájà
 Ení ko kò gbàgbé
Abéré àlàájà
 O gbòrò sínú fògún odún
Abéré àlàájà
 Abéré tó léwu
 Má fi gún mi
 Má fi gún ọmo mi
Abéré àlàájà
 Ta bá fọmọ wómọ láyé
 O ó ro rare pin
Abéré àlàájà

He who defecates forgets easily
Alhaja's needle
 He who packs it forgets not
Alhaja's needle
 You nurse a grudge for twenty years
Alhaja's needle
 A dangerous needle
 Do not prick me with it
 Do not prick my child with it

Alhaja's needle

If one compares children's behaviour
One will be devastated

Alhaja's needle.

In this track, the sentence 'Abéré aláájà' (Alhaja's needle) is repeated five times with other lines intervening.

At other times, the repetition made by Tópé is just partial lexico-structural ones. For example, in *Àlámú Sèniyàan*, she sings

Ewùré iyá fi je

Àgùtàn iyá fi je

The mother's goat ate it

The mother's sheep ate it

A similar one is also sung in *Aboré*:

Orí adé òhun loba ní ní

Bàtà lèsè oba aládé

Ìlèkè jinwinni lórùn oba aládé

The king's head is that of a royal

Shoes on the crowned's feet

Several beads on the crowned king's neck

There are also times when the repetitions made by Tópé Alàbí are based on a semantic range. In *Aboré*, for instance, she sings:

Èèwò ní bẹ̀ nilúú
 Àsẹ̀ ọ̀ba ò débè
 Ilé ò rójú
 Ọ̀nà ò ráyè

There is a taboo in operation in the town
 The king has no diplomatic immunity against it
 The house is not at peace
 The road is not settled

The last two lines have the same meaning – 'the whole town is in distress'.

Another example is found in *Ewúró*, where she sings:

Ayè níkà o
 Aráyé burú o
 Wọ̀n tí gbàgbé ọ̀ba tó dà gbogbo wa

The world is wicked
 People of the world are very bad
 They have forgotten the Almighty King that created us all

The first and second lines mean the same thing; 'people can be very wicked'.

A similar repetition is:

Bẹ́ẹ̀ ní n dáké
 N ò ní gbó

Bée ni n̄ sinmi

N ò n̄i gbà

As sung in *Abéré Alhaja*, which means:

If you say I should keep quiet

I will not do so

If you order me to be silent

I will not agree

'Dàké' and 'sinmi' mean 'be quiet', while 'gbọ' and 'gbà' mean 'to agree or accept'.

3.1.2.6.2 Word-Play

The use of word-play is a stylistic device used by poets and musicians, whereby words with the same or similar sounds but with different meanings, are selected for use, for aesthetic purposes. *Tópé Àlàbí* also uses word-play when singing. In *Ewúro* she sings:

Àgbè tó gbinkà

Kò n̄i káa-lójò kan

The farmer who plants maize

Will not harvest it the very day

The pun here is on the syllable *ka* as it is evident in *gbinkà* (to plant maize) and *ká* (to harvest) whose sounds are similar to *kò* (will not) and *kan* (one).

Another example from *Ewúro* is the song:

Oore korò ọ̀sàn -'an ...

Orí lakàn fi ń kan ìrókò ...

Kindness is bitter in the day

The crab knocks down the Mahogany tree with its head.

The word-play here is with *lakàn* (that the crab) and *kan* (knock) against *ìrókò* (Mahogany tree).

3.1.2.6.3 Parallelism

Parallelism is another feature of Tópé's film music. In parallelism, lexical items occur in identical places in two or more sentences that are parallels. In *Abéré Alhaja*, Tópé sings as below:

Ayé	bínú	káún	wón	sọ	káún	sómi
Ayé	bínu	iyò	wón	sọ	yọ	sérùpè

People	threw	potash	into	water	in	anger
People	threw	salt	into	sand	in	anger

Another example of parallelism is in a track in the YHV film, *Àlámú Sèniyàn*. It goes thus:

Ọmọ burúkú kò yá lù pa
 Ọgèdè burúkú kò yá bù sán

A naughty child is not easy to club to death
 A bad plantain is not easy to eat.

In *Adúnni Olówò Èrú*, there is another example which is:

Ení'déerú leérú ní tò
Eléte lète ní yé

Ashes blow back to whoever blows them
Only the mischievous understands his/her mischief

3.1.2.6.4 Tonal Counterpoint

Tonal counterpoint is the deliberate selection of words that bear counter or alternating tones to form sentences (Ọlátúnjí 1984:32). While scholars like Lásebíkan (1955a, 1955b) postulate that tonal counterpoint in Yorùbá poems occurs only at line-ends like the English metre, others like Beier and Gbàdàmósi (1959:8) and Ọlátúnjí (1984:31) opine that there is no rigid rule about where the tonal counterpoint occurs in Yorùbá poems. There are three essential tones in the Yorùbá language. These are high (H), Mid (M) and Low (L) tones. They are signified as ´ (H), ` (L), and -(M) on the syllables that bear them³ when words are written. Words bearing these tones, apart from being selected deliberately, can also be coined⁴ to be at the beginning, mid-way or end of a poetic line.

Tonal counterpoint is a feature which is very prominent in Tópé's renditions. For instance, in *Ọmọ Mummy*, she sings:

Alágẹmọ ti bímọ ẹ (MHMM)
Àimòójó kù sówọ ọmọ alágẹmọ (LLLHH)

The chameleon has given birth
 Naivety in dancing is the sole burden of its child

Here, the tonal counterpoint is at the beginning of the line. In *Àlámú Sèniyàn*, tonal counterpoint in the middle of a sentence can be seen in the song below where Mid and High tones are counterpointed with Mid and Low tones thus:

A *gb̄ínlá* wa sóko (MH)

A *gb̄ínkà* wa sóko (ML)

We planted our okra in the farm
 We planted our maize in the farm

Tonal counter-point at the end-line can be heard in a song by Tópé in *Ewúro*, thus:

È ò bèrù Ọlórún (MHM)

È ò bèrù adániwáyé (MHMHH)

You do not fear God
 You do not fear the creator

3.1.2.6.5 **Similes**

In *Enikan ò Layé*, when Bábá Baalé is begging the king to forgive his wife (the king's) and allow her back into the palace and the king is adamant, and Bábá Baalé bends his head in thought as to whether he should reveal the secret of the king's true parentage or not, Tópé sings that:

Fòrò síkùn bí àgbà
 Ọbẹ́ ní mì níkùn àgbà ní?

'Swallow' the whole incident like an elder
 Does soup shake in an elder's stomach?

Another simile is evident in *Ewúro* when, in supplication, Tópé sings that 'May the Lord make her life to be like that of bitter-leaf' (which after being eaten, leaves behind the end-result of sweetness). She says:

Èdùmàrè sayé mì bí/ti ewúro

The comparison here is between the singer's life and that of bitter-leaf.

3.2.1.6.6 **Metaphor**

Metaphors are expressions where an action or situation is described or called in a terminology or name which befits another action, situation or object. Instead of referring to an object or situation to appear like another one, the object or situation is given the actual name of what it looks like (Olatúnjí 1984:51-53).

In *Enikan ò Layé*, when Báyò is being shown as a man who must hold on to any girl he sets his eyes upon, to compare Báyò with a butcher who slaughters any animal that he sets his eyes upon, Tópé says:

O wá dalápatà omoge
You are now a maidens' butcher

In *Aborè*, when Aborè volunteers to release his son as sacrifice for the progress of his town, the people are stupefied; they can not believe their ears. Tópé then interjects the story with the song;

Òrò takúwárápá bá sọ
Ará òrun ló sọ ó

Whatever an epileptic patient says is authentic
As he (the epileptic) is a regular 'visitor' to heaven

An epileptic person here is being referred to as (being as good as) dead.

In *Ilé Olórogún*, Tópé refers to a polygamous home as being bitter as bile, by singing that;

Òróhó sá layé
The world is a bile

3.1.2.6.7 Personification

Personification is a device whereby inanimate objects and non-human things are referred to of as if they possess the attributes of animate things or

human beings (Olatunji 1984:49). It is a device very much used by Yoruba poets and musicians. In *Àdúnní Olówò Erú*, when a slave is being punished for saying the truth, Tópé sings thus;

Òtító mà fiyà jẹ mí o láyè

Ó ẹe ó pò

Íkú wólé ọlá

Truth has ill-treated me

What a pity

Death has demolished a wealthy homestead

Òtító (Truth) here is being spoken of as a human being who can ill-treat another person, while *Íkú* (Death) is seen as a man who can demolish a building.

The song: *Bó tí mí ẹsẹ ọbẹ ló yé*
Bó tí mí ẹbẹ nínú ịsàsùn
E bẹrẹ lówó idáná

It is the knife who understands the yam's feeling
 The reason for the soup's behaviour in the pot
 Can only be understood by the fire-place

'Knife' and 'fire-place' are talked of as human beings who can understand their fellows' feelings, whereas they are inanimate objects used in the kitchen.

3.1.2.6.8 Hyperbole

Hyperboles are exaggerated descriptions of people or things in a way far beyond their actual state or appearance. In *Ewúro*, Tópé sings the song below when Wálé and Rántí his sister are struggling to survive:

Orí lejá fi n labú já
Orí lakàn fi n kan Ìrókò

The fish uses its head to swim through the river
The crab uses its head to knock the mahogany tree

The crab's limbs and claws may truly be proportionally smaller than its head, the head definitely can not knock down a mahogany tree! Another exaggeration is evident in the song below from *Ilé Olórogún*:

Ilé olórogún mà ro tótó
Ilé olórogún dùn ó joyin

A polygamous home is dangerous
A polygamous home can be sweeter than honey

The hyperbole here is in the second line where a polygamous home is said to be sometimes "sweeter than honey". This is an exaggeration. What is meant is that such a home may be very peaceful – more so than expected.

3.1.2.6.9 Foreign Languages

Tòpè Alàbí is also capable of composing few lines in other languages (apart from the Yorùbá language). Although this feature in particular is not as common as other ones in her renditions, we have to point out that, if need be, she can sing in other languages. Below is a song in the YHV *O Se Jé Emi* (Why me)

Why me?
 Why me?
 Ó se jé èmi?
 Ó se jé èmi?
 Kí ló dé? (Why?)
 O se jẹ emi?

Another one is:

Ìrin-àjò èdà láyé
 Olúwa ló mọ ọn o
Journey journey
 Irin àjò èdà láyééé

Human beings' movements all about in life
 Only God understands it
Journey journey
 Human beings' movements all about in life

from the YHV, *Modúpè Olúwa*.

3.1.3 Assessment of Tópé Àlàbí's Performance

The Yorùbá people's belief is that the mental capability of a woman is nowhere near that of her male counterpart. Her finer physiology has been taken for granted to imply a lesser reasoning faculty. As a result of this, she has been socially acculturated in the past to depend on her husband financially. Things are beginning to change today. Women are making waves in their different chosen careers; they have even excelled more than the males in many aspects of socio-economic life. Tópé Àlàbí is a very good example of such women. She is unparalleled among other female film singers like Salome Èkétúndé, Julie King, Tóyin Yòmi-Ògúnmólá and Ayò Ewébiyi. Apart from this, male singers like Gbénga Adéwùsi, Yèkinni Ajiléye, Dáre Àyindé, Bíódún Adékàmbí, Adémólá Àrèmu, and Dòtun Kóládé do not have to their names the number of film music credits Tópé Àlàbí has. She has excelled in her chosen career and is contributing massively to the socio-economic sphere of the nation. Tópé Àlàbí's name is a house-hold one in film music for YHV films. She has achieved self-actualization and financial independence in her profession. According to her, she finds giving financial support to her immediate and extended family members very convenient.

As impressive as we have found Tópé's film music, Taiwo Hassan (Ògògò) has a counter-opinion. To him, "Tópé's kind of music is stereotype". Ògògò believes that when Tópé sings in any film, without asking for the name of the singer, one easily knows that she is the one. For this reason he (Ògògò) will not

like the idea of employing Tópé to sing into films produced by him. We are, however, of the opinion that every one has his or her own voice pitch. This is why having been familiar with a person for some time, it is easy to identify such a person by voice, even if he or she is not physically present⁵.

Apart from this, people's perspectives about, or their reaction to issues or incidents cannot be the same. As popular as Sunny Adé, Ebenezer Obey, Felá Anikulapo-Kuti or Michael Jackson are as musicians, there will definitely be some people, who, for personal reasons, will not like them, or like to be identified with them – that does not mean they are not good.

3.2.0 Producing Yoruba Home Video Film

The producer of a film is that individual, group of persons or a corporate body, who had sourced for the money with which a (video) film was produced. This is what a producer is primarily and conventionally known for. Apart from sourcing the finances, the producer is in the overall charge of a video recording project (Angell 1999:20). He/she is the one who sources for, selects and employs the personnel needed for the film production. The personnel include the script writer, director, camera crew, art director, the artistes to act the characters of the video film, costumiers, wardrobe mistress and sound tracking professionals. More often than not, it is the producer and the employed director who jointly employ the remaining personnel. It is the producer who supervises

**ŞOLÁ ŞÓBÒWÁLÉ, TÓYÌN AFQLÁYAN AND
MURPHY RAY ÈYÍWÙNMÍ IN A SCENE FROM TENI N
TENI**

the expenditure and keeps the financiers informed about how their money is being spent, if the film project is not self-financed by the producer. A finance manager may be employed by the producer to do this. Apart from these, the producer must see to keeping the film recording within schedule and budget. He/she must take care of the general welfare of the production crew which includes their feeding and lodging at film locations. The producer must also be ready to take full responsibility for the performance or otherwise of the artistes he/she employs, because they must justify the money spent on them by the financiers. For this, he/she must endeavour to select the best of artistes within his/her financial capability.

3.2.1 The Executive Producer

In the Nigerian home video industry generally and specifically in the production of YHV films, caution must be taken in using the tag 'producer' when referring to the person who owns the copyright of a YHV. This is because while there are some YHV films that are single-handedly financed and produced by individuals, there are many more which were produced by individuals but were financed by other people or corporate bodies. For example, *Igbesè* was produced and financed solely by Modupe Johnson (Fàlì Wèrèpè). The same applies to *Omo Okunrin* by Taiwo Akinwande. However, *Ibinu Olukoso* was written and produced by late Bimpe Adékola, but was jointly financed by Qudus, Al Amin and Barakat Balogun. Others are *Koto Ayé*, written and directed by

Alhaji Yekeen Ajiléyẹ and *Jógunómi* written by Ánikẹ Bọla-Obot but financed by Akintundé Ayeni, the proprietor of Yemkem Naturalist Clinic, and *Éékú Idà* which was produced by Túnjí Bámishígbin, and financed by Rockview Productions. These financial backers are usually referred to as 'executive producers'. As can be imagined, the executive producers, more often than not, influence the modus operandi of the production. Such an influence may be on the theme, choice of artistes, locations or shooting schedule. The 'producer' will have no choice other than to oblige, for a Yorùbá maxim says:

Bí irùgbòn alágbàṣe bá gùn, kó ju apá ló
Eni tó gbóko fún un lógáa rẹ.

Let the beard of a labourer be longer than the
Arm, his employer remains the boss.

It is a case of he who pays the piper, dictates the tune.

3.2.2 The Inter-relationship of the Producer and the Director

The director of a (video) film is the one who directs and calls the shots for the different scenes of a film. In actual fact, she/he joins the producer to decide on the artistes to be used in a film, or at least her/his advice is sought for the artistes' selection. The director of a film production is its livewire. He/she can not afford to be away from the taking of any shot. If he/she must be unavoidably absent, his/her (well seasoned) assistant will have to stand in for him/her (for a short period) or the recording of such a film might be postponed.

While the producer's excuse to be absent is tolerable, that of the director is not; except for very important reasons – he/she must be on location while the shooting lasts. A director must have a wide range of experience and be unassuming. He/she must be friendly and understanding, but firm. The ability of a seasoned and experienced film director can turn a badly written script into a box office-hit film, while incompetence on the part of a director can ruin a well written script.

It is important that a very amicable relationship exist between the producer and the director. The relationship must be such that there is mutual respect for each other's views and extent of responsibilities. Their joint aim must be to produce the finest (video) film, which "will appeal to the widest audience in spite of the often irksome restriction in budget and schedule" (Angell 1999:21). We found out in the course of this study that Abíódún Olanrewájú (Abbey Lanre) and late Yòmí Ògúnmolá, are the two directors mostly employed by YHV female producers. This, according to Ídòwù Phillips, is "due to their kind and gentle disposition towards female producers and the fact that they are well experienced" perhaps more than the likes of Jidé Kòsókó, Yemí Àmódù, Rasaq Oláyíwólá, Mònsúrù Oḃádínà, Olúwolé Oyèedèjì and Tájùdeen Mobólájí.

In the past, some women like Tóyìn Afóláyan and Modúpé Johnson have amateurishly directed their own film, but according to Modúpé Johnson:⁶

Ìgbà yẹn, a ò tí ì mò ní film industry àwà Yorùbá pé ó yẹ kí producer wà lótò, kí director wà lótò, kí make-up artist wà lótò ...

We were yet to know then, in the Yorùbá film industry, that we needed specialists to handle production, direction, make-up ...

As far as specialization or professionalism in the direction of YHV is concerned, women are yet to do much. Yemi Adénúgà, who was at one time a film director with the African Independence Television (AIT) Alagbado, Lagos, has directed just one film – *Opélopé Asebi*, produced by her husband – Dèji Adénúgà. Racheal Oniga, too, directed the scenes shot in America for Sìnà Sànyàolú's *Ìlérí Ayò*, while Fémí Ògúnjòbí directed the scenes shot in Nigeria. "Sooner than later, with the rate at which learned women are joining the Yoruba film industry, many female directors will emerge" (Adébáyò Sàlámi)⁷. This is truly hopeful; after all, late Bímpè Adékólá successfully directed her own (last) film – *Ìbinú Olúkòso*.

3.2.3 Women as Yoruba Home Video Film Producers

When the folkloric *Àjàní Ògún* by Olá Balógun "opened the flood-gates" (Adesanya 1997:14) for other travelling theatre practitioners to go into film production in the mid-70s in Nigeria, the female artistes used formerly as casts on stage, readily joined their male counter-parts in acting at film locations for cinematographic productions. Only one female, Simbiat Sówólé, as mentioned

earlier dared to produce a Yoruba reversal film. The initial types of films produced at this period were witchcraft-horror thrillers like Ogunde's *Aiyé* and *Jajeyesinmi* and other almost unrealistically themed and plotted ones.

The dwindling Nigerian economy of the late 80s and early 90s made many filmmakers crash out of the business. However, some of the filmmakers were determined to stay in the business, and so, instead of using the more expensive celluloid tapes for film shooting, they made do with reversal stock. When the reversal stock got exhausted, they started shooting films on video tapes. After all a Yorùbá maxim says:

Kí ia ó jẹ làgba kí ia ó se

'What are we to eat is the drive behind 'what are we to do'

The same women used for celluloid production come readily for use in video production. In the early period of video film production, women were not producing their own films. They continued to take up feminine roles and acted as welfare officers at locations. The reasons for this delay in production are not far to seek. The socio-acculturation of females by their families (especially their mothers) and the society at large continued to make them see themselves as being inferior to their male counterparts. Apart from this, the Yorùbá culture and traditions which do not permit females to have knowledge of, or take part in cultic practices did not allow them to act in films which were in vogue then – esoteric traditional and horror films.

Thirdly, the females in theatrical and filmic practice were still very few. Most of them were spouses of demised troupe leaders and as such had no financial capability of producing video films single-handedly. Moreover, it was (still) a period in the history of film production in Nigeria when men in theatre practice were beginning to be accepted as people just better than being unemployed and the women as daring ladies, who had to do the job, having dropped out of school – just a little better than prostitutes.

Things began to change in the mid-80s when women like Tóyín Afọlayán (one of the wives of late Adeyemi Afọlayan – a theatre practitioner) decided to go into video film production, so as to immortalize her spouse's name. Others are Modúpé Johnson (Fàlí Wèrèpè) and Esther Ìdòwu Phillips (wife of late Oyèniyi Àyánfèmi Phillips of the Òsùmare Theatre Troupe). These women decided individually to hold the bull by the horns and produced video films like their male counterparts; after all it is cheaper to produce (with their small capital) than the virtually extinct celluloid films. By doing this, they acted as pacesetters and models for other women who had the wherewithal to produce films but were holding back, waiting for who would bell the cat.

TÓYÌN AFQŁÁYAN (LQŁÁ ÌDÍ JẸẸ) AND SELF

Péju Ógúnmolá (Late Kólá Ógúnmolá's daughter), Solá Sóbòwálé and Yémísí Jalyéolá are among the second generation of film producers after the cat had been belled, as said above. By the late 1980s, many female actresses began to join the Yorùbá film industry, first as actresses, and when they had reached stardom, they began to attempt video film production, with their established recognition as 'popular film stars'. Some of such females are Táiwo Akinwándé (Wùnmí), Solá Sóbòwálé (Jádesólá), Bimpé Adékólá (Ìrèti), Tóyìn Adégbolá (Aséwó tó re Mecca) and Fóláké Àrémú (Òrìṣàbùnmi).

By 1998, young ladies who more than anything saw the first and second generations of female artistes as their role models began to join the Yorùbá video film industry. Most of these ladies are quite learned. They opted for the showbiz industry either out of sheer fancy, having studied Theatre Arts or related courses in the University or Polytechnic or due to the mass school leavers' unemployment being experienced at present in the country. Some of such ladies are Late Funmi Martins, Bukky Wright, Bimbó Oṣin, Sadé Omoniyi, Opéyemí Ayéola, Rónké Òjó, Lolá Àlào, Láidé Bákàrè, Zainab Oduwole and Ayò Adèsànyá Hassan. This third generation of female Yorùbá artistes is more educated than the earlier ones. As a result of this, they are more open to foreign cultural influences and they are more aggressive in their approach. They came into the industry when the society is now not only tolerant towards female actresses, but also willing to accept them as stars and role models. Parents now readily send their daughters (and sons) to schools to read Theatre Arts and other related

courses. This wide acceptance and recognition has in no small measure influenced the production of YHV by women. This is why Opéyemí Ayéòlá^B said;

We know we are accepted, we are loved by our fans out there. For this reason we always try to put in our best efforts ...

3.2.4 Female Producers, Scripting and Language

A film script is the text form of a (feature) film. It may be based on an existing work, a book or play, or it may be an original, (Angell 1999:13). It is normally (hand or type) written in a dialogue form, whereby each cast-member speaks and responds to others' speeches in such a way that the message of the film is unfolded sequentially. Writing a script is a skill that calls for a lot of imagination. It is the script that is normally given to each member of the production crew (cast inclusive), to read and understand before proceeding to the film locations, so that each and everyone of them would have known the roles to be played. A script ought to reflect not just the characters and their roles, but also the plot, properties (props) to be used, shades of light, shades of characters' costumes and their make-up, among other things.

In the course of this study, we found out that there are some female film producers who, due to a limited educational background, can only scribble down the synopsis of the feature film they have in mind, in prose form – a document referred to by Angell (1999:13) as *treatment*. They give this out to other learned

and more experienced (male) colleagues to script for them at a fee. Táiwò Akinwándé, Modúpé Johnson, Zainab Odùwólé and Tóyìn Afọlayan more often than not, do this.

Whether a script is self-written or given out for writing (whether by a male or female producer), a panel consisting of three or more experienced artistes, producers and directors, is usually invited to meet and arrange the scenes plotted in the script in a sequential order as they may jointly deem fit to be the best for such a feature film. The outcome of their decision is referred to as the *Screen Play* in film parlance. For instance, Síkírù Balógun, Tajudeen Mobólájí, Gàni, Gàniyù Fásínà and Rísíikátù Fásínà handled the screen-play of Zainab Odùwólé's *Olómọ Ló Ma Ròjá*, while that of Tóyìn Adégbolá's *Ojó Ìdájó* was done by Fèsò Oyèwólé, Isiaka Egunbunmi, Dọlápò Olówè, Muyiwa Adémólá and the producer herself. It was Akin Ládáhùnsi and Tádé Ògidán that joined Sọlá Sóbòwálé to screen-play her *Ayòmidà*, while the screen-play for Bukky Wright's *Àgbéké* was handled by Bólájí Saheed, Túndé Benson, Rónké Benson and the producer herself.

Since the medium of expression in Yorùbá video films is basically the standard Yorùbá Language and its various dialects, one will expect that the scripts of the films be written in the Yorùbá language with few lines written in dialect(s) if and where they are to be used (for aesthetic effects). In the course of this study, we found out that while some (female) producers like Queen Olùwà have their scripts written in the Yorùbá language, others like Opeyemí

Ayéòlà, appear not to be bothered about the language in which their scripts are written, as long as the characters can read and understand their lines and act well, speaking the Yorùbá language. This is why some scripts are written in a mixture of Yorùbá and English languages. Asked why this is so, Oṣéyemí Ayéòlà has this to say:

Ti film star kán bá wà, tí a gbà pé òun ló lè act part kan dáadáa jù, tí irú ẹni bẹ̀e ò bá lè ka Yorùbá dáadáa, kò sí nńkan tí a lè se ju pé ká kọ àwọn parts irú ẹni bẹ̀e ní English. Tó bá kàá, tó dè yé e dáadáa, á á lè sọ nńkan tó ba yẹ kó sọ ni èdè Yorùbá. Sèbí èdè wa ni, wọn ò kan lè kàá ni, wọn lè sọ ó dáadáa. Nńkan tó fa gbogbo wáhálà yíi ni pé, private nursery and primary schools ni ọ̀pọ̀ nínú àwa young artistes tó wà níta báyii lọ. Sèbí ẹ̀ mò pé wọn kíí sáábà kọ Yorùbá tàbí kí wọn sọ ó ní rú àwọn schools bẹ̀e. Sèbí ẹ̀yin lè ẹ̀ ní sọ nígbà tí a wà ni location léèkan pé Yorùbá tí a kọ sínu script pàápáá kò dára tó. Gbogbo Yorùbá táwa gbó niyẹn o. (*Ó rẹ̀n-ín*).

If a particular film star is the ideal for a role, and he/she can not read Yorùbá language very well, one has no choice other than writing his/her lines in the English language. Having read and understood what is to be done, he/she can now make his/her dialogues in the Yorùbá language. After all, it is not as if they can not speak Yorùbá, it is our language. The problem is

that most young artistes these days attended private nursery and primary schools, where the Yorùbá language is virtually neither spoken nor taught. Were you not saying it a few minutes ago at the location that even the Yorùbá lines in my script need to be re-worked? That is about all the Yorùbá that we can write (*laughs*).

Although their film productions are adequate these female artistes will do better if they aspire to speak good Yorùbá language and read their lines in the language. It will make the speeches more fluent before the camera. See appendix VI for Oṣéyemí Ayéòlá scripts for *Ki í Şerù È* (the working title of *Teni N Teni*) and Queen Olùwà's script for *Rèmílékún*.

3.2.5 Female Producers and Finance

As mentioned above, the success or otherwise of a YHV pivots around finance. Financial constraints have always been the bane of most individual film producers, irrespective of gender. We found out that female producers seem to feel the constraint more than their male counterparts. In a "limited research" carried out by Tariq (1990:5) he found out that:

In Nigeria, access to credit seems to be constrained because women do not own marketable land rights, and for social and cultural reasons, seldom have the opportunity to acquire independent credit histories for credit worthiness. Although debatable, women are considered to be more risky borrowers than men.

Asked for her opinion about how easy or otherwise it is for the womenfolk in the Yorubá video industry to finance the production of their YHV, Modúpé Johnson has this to say⁹:

Wàhálà gbàà ni ríí owó se fidíò jé fún àwa òsèré, pàápàá júlò àwa obinrin. Àwọn ọkúnrin máa n tètè rí owó yá ju àwa obinrin. Òhun tí mo sí rò pé ó fàá ni pé ọpò nínú àwọn èniyàn wa kò gbà pé àwa obinrin lè dá nńkan gidí se. Yàtò sí èyí, wón tún máa n rò pé bí owó bá dówó àwa obinrin, góólù, báàgì, bàtà àti asọ ni a ó fi rà. Bí ó bá se bánki ni, mónijà lè bèrè sí ni fi ilòkulò lo olúwa rẹ.

It is always very difficult to source for money to produce video films, for us producers generally, and much more difficult for us women. Male artistes usually find it easier to procure loans than we. I feel that the reason for this is that many of our people do not believe that we women can be economically productive. Apart from this, they also believe that any money given to a woman will be spent on jewelleries, bags, shoes and clothes. If one goes to the bank, the manager may start making love advances.

Talking about banks, Ayeni (1990:29) has rightly observed that the central role of the banking industry is that of financial intermediation – to raise funds economically and ensure that funds so mobilized are deployed in the most effective and efficient manner as to enhance the growth of the various sectors of the economy. We discovered that the banks in Nigeria do not effectively and efficiently disburse money without gender bias. Even though the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1976 section 39.1, provides for the true equality for men and women, and the bank laws appear to be generally gender-neutral, in practical reality, gender discriminatory practices still go on in Nigerian Banks. Business women still find it relatively difficult to secure bank loans even after satisfying all the prerequisites for securing them. The bank officials still ask the women to bring their husbands or some other males as sureties.

Adenike Osoba (1990:13) has opined that given the low level of education that was common among female entrepreneurs in the past, it is not a surprise that accessibility to formal credit in banks was a thorny issue. The fact that formal creditors required proper documentation and accounts like balance sheets and profit and loss accounts before granting loans, meant that most female entrepreneurs were excluded from the use of such facilities. Osoba (1990) appears to be of the opinion that with improved education, women will find it easier to secure loans from banks.

Uneasy access to financial facilities by women in the film industry is not peculiar to the Yorùbá or African women alone. Evidence from around the world is quite strong that women entrepreneurs in small and medium scale business or industries have had peculiar difficulties gaining access to credit (McCarney 1990:33). It appears to be a general trend in all patriarchal societies. Shirley Clarke (1972:22) recalls her experience in Hollywood thus:

I didn't have any means of getting money. It may have to do with the fact that people with money do not talk to women about money ... Everyone said 'fantastic, do something for us. But don't expect much. Being a woman, it's going to be difficult'. So when I got out there, they had a man who was going to tell me how to make my film. Men just don't like to talk to women about money.

3.2.6 Raising Capital for Production: Táíwò Akińwándé as a Case Study

Despite the financial predicament, women continue to produce YHV films. The question to be asked now is, how have they been able to raise capital for their production? We found out that proceeds from co-starring in films by other producers, sales of scripts or synopsis of storyline, savings from other business enterprises and re-ploughing accrued profits into video production business, are ways by which female producers have been financing their productions.

Mrs Táíwo Akińwándé went into acting in 1981 with Sunday Akińolá Mógàjí of the 'Fèyíkógbón' fame on Nigerian Television Authority, Lagos. She became independent in 1992 when she made her debut YHV film, *Ayé Okúnrin*, which is in two parts. These she sold to Soars Film Marketing Company at the rate of ten thousand naira only (N10,000) for each part. With the twenty thousand naira (N20,000) realized, she was able to produce *Éré Èsè* in 1993. This she sold to another distributor for fifteen thousand naira (N15,000) each for a part of two. With additional money from co-starring in other YHV films produced by both male and female colleagues, she was able to produce *Omọ Okúnrin* in 1994 with seventy thousand naira (N70,000). This she sold to Oyèdélé Films for a whopping sum of one hundred and twenty thousand naira (N120,000). Táíwò claimed to have spent twenty thousand naira (N20,000) from

TÁÍWÒ AKÍNWÁNDÉ (A.K.A. WÙNMÍ)

the money for her personal up-keep and image improvement. She used the balance of one hundred thousand naira (N100,000) to produce *Odun Méjé*. She said¹⁰:

Bí ó ɛ di pé èmi náà bèrè sí níí ní owó okòwò tó tó mú yangàn ní yíí. Mo jiyà púpò ní ibèrè, sùgbón mo dúpé lówó Ọlórún pé lóníí, iyàtò tí n' dé ...

That was how I raised an enviable running capital. I denied myself a lot of things at the beginning, but today, I have every cause to thank God, because positive changes are taking place ...

3.2.7 Females, YHV Production, Realism and Matrimony

Women have been able to produce a sizeable number of YHV films (self-financed or otherwise) despite the societal matrimonial and financial inhibitions that come their way as they operate in a patriarchal society. These women can be grouped into four categories, viz: the prolific producers, the old-hands who have co-starred or have taken lead-roles in many films but have very few produced by themselves, up-coming mostly professionally trained (younger) producers and the non-Yorùbá.

Women in the first category include pioneers like Ídòwú Phillips, Modúpé Johnson, Tóyín Afoláyan, Yémisí Jalyéplá, Táiwò Akínwándé and Sólá Sóbówalé. Láńre Hassan-Adésinà and Íyábò Ọkò are some of the women who fall into the

second category. Some of the up-coming young prolific producers are Bukky Wright, Rónké Òjó, Opéyemí Ayéòla, Lolá Àlàó, Ayò Adégbité, Láídé Bákàrè and Fathia Balógun. Doris Simeon, Racheal Oniga, Liz Benson, Ngozi Nwosu, Grace Everly and Shan George, are some of the non-Yorùbá females who feature regularly in YHV films. However, Rachael Oniga, a Lagos born Urhobo woman, is the only one who has produced YHV films. *Aramide*, *Bibire* and *Eléyélé* were written and produced by Rachael. (See Appendix I for a list of some of the female Yorùbá home video films producers).

The women in the third category are producing at a faster rate than their models and predecessors, due to their being more educated and therefore more likely able to secure loans from the banks and to get financial assistance from their parents and relations who are now more than ever interested in their (the women's) chosen profession.

Apart from the faster rate of production, their films are more realistic. They contain less of the supernatural romantic world of witches, mermaids, and the use of native charms and incantations, which characterized Yorùbá films produced by both genders in the early period of the Yorùbá films developmental history. For instance, in Idowu Phillips' *Alamu Sèniyàn*, Fàdèrera goes to seek the help of Ewénjé the herbalist to assist her with charms in order to redirect the misfortune of Àlà mú (her first son) to Oláyíwoḷà and Mojísólá, Àlà mú's brother and sister. In *Ségilola* by Yémisí Jalyeola, too, Adérògbà beats a mad woman

and the latter curses that Adérògbà will never be able to find a woman who will agree to be his wife, and it comes to pass.

Comparatively, the up-coming stars of Ayò Adésànyà Hassan type, appear not to believe or have interest in black magic or the use of charms. In her *Gbakogboko*, rather than seek the help of a traditional medicine-man to win Solá's heart, Ifé puts on seductive wears like (bosom-revealing) body-hug blouses, mini skirts and shorts while acting as a guest in Solá and Tólání's home. She winks at Solá anytime their eyes meet and is eventually able to lure him into bed. Becoming pregnant and refusing to have an abortion, Ife becomes Solá's second wife. Another example is from Ayò Adégbité's *Oní Níkan* where rather than use charm on Juliet for snatching and getting pregnant for Yòmi-Oyinkán's husband, Oyinkán and her friend Tólání go to the highway to lay ambush for Juliet. Double-crossing her jeep with Oyinkán's car, Tólání and Oyinkán drag Juliet out and beat the day-lights out of her.

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**OPÉYEMÍ AYÉÒLA AT THE LOCATION FOR
TENI N TENI**

Grouped as widowed/divorced/separated from husbands, being in the industry or related ones with husbands and as spinsters, we noticed certain peculiarities among these female producers. We observed that while women like *Ìdòwú Phillips*, *Tóyìn Afóláyan*, *Tóyìn Adégbolá*, *Táíwo Akínwándé*, late *Bímpé Adékòlá* and late *Funmi Martins*, will employ or seek the help of crew members (in their guild system) for assistance in their production, the women in the second group involve their husbands in their production. In fact it appears as if their productions are joint efforts with their husbands, although none of them agrees with this assessment of dependency. For instance, *Saheed Balogun* is the writer and one of the editors of *Fathia Balógun* (his wife's) *Omọ Ọ̀Ṣeé Pààrò* and *Ayò Adésànyà-Hassan's Èèbù Ìkà* and *Gbọkọgbọkọ* are written, directed and financed by her husband-*Omógoriọlá Hassan*.

The women in this group are able to produce their films with greater ease than those in the first group. Firstly, they are able to pull resources together with their husbands, secondly, their being away from home (which is patriarchally viewed as where women belong) is understandable to their husbands, and as such they will be able to relax and work conscientiously. Apart from this, banks and other corporate bodies will readily give them financial assistance, with their husbands serving as sureties and guarantors. Finally, more respect is given to *obinrin tó wà nilé ọkọ* (a married woman) by their male counterparts. As a result, such women are sure of getting the total support and respect of their crew members.

There is, however, the possibility of the women of the second group not reaching their full potential capabilities. This is because they have to toe their husband's lines in relation to their themes, choice of cast or general modus operandi, for the sake of their marriage, if not for anything else. Take the case of Monsurat Omidinà, for example. She is at present the most renowned female jester in the Yorùbá home video industry. One will expect to see her play a comic role in her YHV – *Obàkan*, but she does not!

The film is themed on men's refusal to claim children born by their mistresses wherein Monsurat plays the lead-role of Àjìkẹ Olótí (Ajikẹ the drinks seller). The reason for this is not far to seek. In our own opinion, this may be due to Monsurat's husband (Babátúndé Omidinà a.k.a Bàba Sùwé's) influence. Babátúndé has produced chart-busters like *Òbẹ Lomọ*, *Baba Londoner* and *Òsomọ* wherein he has proved himself to be the best Yorùbá comedian of our time. It is possible that Babátúndé, who wrote the *Obàkan* script for his wife, does not want her to interfere or penetrate into his domain. Another possibility is for Monsurat to feel that it would be unbecoming of her to attempt to outshine or even compete with her husband in their area of specialization, for a Yorùbá proverb says:

Erin kii fọn, kómọ rẹ ó tún fọn

When the elephant finishes trumpeting, its child need not trumpet again

Another Yorùbá proverb says:

Bóbinrin bá gbón ogbón àgbónjù, pémpé laso oko won
ń mọ

If a woman is too wise, her husband's clothings will be
short.

Both proverbs mean that intellectually, a wife should not attempt to compete with her man. This is one of the ways in which men in the patriarchal societies suppress women's intellectual development.

Spinsters of the third group are free to go about their film productions the way they deem fit. Being younger and without matrimonial commitments, they are able to concentrate fully on their job and "will only get married to men who can accept and tolerate our being members of the 'Hollywood society'"¹¹. This is certainly true, for it is doubtful if Rónké Ojó's husband would have 'allowed' her to take part in her *City Girls* and *Omoge Campus*. This is because many people find it difficult to accept that these 'big gals' real life-styles are different from what they are on the screen.

The number of YHV films so far produced by females is likely to be more than what we listed in Appendix I. This is because the list contains just the titles of those YHV films that we found in the market and at video clubs. There is the likelihood of some of the films produced years back being off the shelves now. Apart from this, we were not able to get the accurate number of women's films

from the National Censors Board, for, as Báyò Adéwùsì of the Báyòwá Films and Record Company told us:

The Censors Board is only interested in telling you which films are for general viewing and which ones are to be watched by only matured viewers (above eighteen, that is). They do not want to know whether it is by a man or woman. Apart from this, there are many illegal video films in the market (which does not mean they are not good), that never went through the Board. In all, women have been pulling their weight ... like Mama Rainbow, Sọlá Sọbọwálé, Wùnmí, Pájú Ògúnmólá, Lọlá Alao, Bimbó Oşin, Ayò Adésànyà, Bukky Wright, Fathia Balógun, Tóyin-Aşéwó ... All together ... let us put their films at one hundred and twenty or thereabouts....

So far, women have come a long way as a creative force in the Yorùbá video film industry. They have excelled as film musicians-composing asynchronous sound for the films produced by both genders in order to drive home the themes and moral lessons of the films. Gone are the days when all that women contributed to the theatrical industry was playing mild roles and taking care of crew members. Women now write film scripts, produce them and even make attempts at directing. In our own opinion, it is good for women to learn on the job from their male colleagues and spouses, and as much as possible get their un-biased support. After all, womanism is all about the complementary efforts of both genders (without either suppressing or invading

the other's space) to make the society better. However, women in this field will become more self-actualized and fulfilled by and by, as the menfolk in our society and the world over understand, appreciate, accept and identify with what Womanism is all about.

NOTES ON CHAPTER THREE

- 1 She is referred to as 'Oore tí ò Common' because of her debut music album so titled.
- 2 These are drums used for the traditional music of the Yorùbá people.
- 3 In the modern Yorùbá orthography, the mid tone is never indicated on the syllable bearing it, except in linguistic descriptions or analysis like we are doing now.
- 4 Examples of such selections are ayé/àyéè (meaning human beings), iyá mi/iyà mi (meaning 'my mother'), to imply the witches.
- 5 A wife, for instance, will recognize her husband's voice on the phone, or if he hoots to her on the farm while far away.
- 6 In an interview with her at the premises of Lagos Television, Ikeja, Lagos, on October 22, 2002.
- 7 In an interview with him at the premises of Lagos Television, Ikeja, Lagos, on October, 22, 2002.
- 8 During an interview with her at New Gate Hospital, Ikorodu on March 14, 2004 while on location for her *Tení N Teni*.
- 9 In an interview with her at the premises of African Independent Television, Alagbado, Lagos on February 8, 2002.
- 10 In an interview with her at a social gathering held at 133, Palm Grove, Ikorodu Road, Lagos on January 17, 2001.
- 11 A tag used by Rónké Ojo during a chat with her while on location for Qpéyemi Ayéòlá's *Tení N Teni* on March 14, 2004.

CHAPTER FOUR

WOMEN IN THE RE-CREATIVE FORCE OF THE YORÙBÁ HOME VIDEO FILM INDUSTRY

4.1.0 Introduction

Old and original creative art works in imaginative or inventive forms can be re-created by their original creators or by other people for better or improved aesthetic values. This can be done by giving additional or new interpretations, embellishing them with more and newer ideals, or adapting them to suit new purposes other than that for or by which they were originally created. In the course of this study, we found out that women play not only creative roles in the Yorùbá home video industry, they also play re-creative roles, to a very large extent, with costumes and make-up – which are some of “the most fundamental elements of drama” production (Adinku 1999:42).

4.1.1 Costuming

Wearing clothes, like taking food or living under a shelter, is one of man’s most important needs. Clothing includes all the different garments, accessories and ornaments worn by people throughout the world (Roll et.al. 1980:540-541). The type of clothes worn by people depends largely on their geographical location, culture and religion. Clothes are worn for protection, communication and decoration (Adinku, 1999:12).

In theatrical and filmic parlance, clothes and other accessories like shoes, bags, beads, crowns or head-gears, worn during the staging of a play or the recording of film for theatrical, television, video or advertisement purposes are called 'costumes' (Ogundeji 1988:301-302). Costumes are used to portray the specific character that an artiste has to play. The characters that are possible to play in a YHV are as many as all the people in the society. This is to say, in effect, that all incidents going on in a given society can be depicted on the visuals, aided by costumes. Costuming is as old as drama itself; for the clothings worn by an artiste, be it during traditional festivals, the Eégún Aláré spectacles, clothes for opening and closing glees of the Ogunde dramatic tradition theatres or for cinematographic and video film shootings – all go a long way in encoding the message of a play.

4.1.2 Historical Survey of Costume in Yorùbá Drama

During the traditional festivals, costumes are usually made by the and/or with the instruction of the priest/priestess in charge of the rituals made to the deified hero being worshipped or celebrated. For instance, during Ògún festival in Oṅdó¹, skirts made with palm fronds are worn round the waist and red-coloured jumpers or shirts are worn on top by the priests. During the Orósùn² in Idànrè, the chief priest and other male devotees are usually clad in a white wrapper tied round their waists.

The costumes of the Egúngún Apidán, in form of *Labá*, *Èkú* or *Òkoloribá*³, were sewn specially by Alàrán Orí, using basically local materials, and the masks were made by professionals from the lineage of sculptors (Adedeji 1969).

In the Ogunde dramatic tradition, the costumes (especially those used in dancing and singing the glees) were artistically designed by the troupe leaders and given to their wives or other tailors to sew. Biódún Dúró-Ladipo (wife of late Dúró Ladipo) is known to sew beautiful costumes for her husband's troupe members (Ògúndèjí 1988). Things have changed in general and especially in the case of costuming for film production.

4.1.3 Contemporary Yorùbá Drama Costumiers

A costumier is the person who takes the responsibility of the clothing used in a theatrical or filmic production. There are now specially trained professionals who take charge of the costumes used by artistes. While some of these costumiers trained on the job (for most of them were initially actors and actresses), others are graduates from either polytechnics or universities or persons who have learnt fashion designing at sewing institutes.

It is important to state here that the tag 'costumier' as used in the list of the production crew at the end of a YHV film, means, in essence, the person or group of people who took charge of the costumes worn in the film. It does not necessarily mean that such a person or people designed or made the costumes. They might just have bought, borrowed, hired out or selected the costumes for

the film or given advice concerning them. However, there are many cases when such costumes were designed and made by them. For instance, when a Yorùbá video film is thematically historic rather than contemporary, the costume designer has to build garments with which the period of the incidents in the film can be re-created. This is because such garments are likely to be out of vogue, for designs and fabrics for clothing are dynamic – they change with time.

There are now some fashion houses who are given contracts by film producers to supply costumes for film productions. Some of these are Abikaz Fashion Plaza in Lagos (which handled the costumes used in Dèjì Adénúgà's *Opélopé Aṣebi*) and Neehas Clothing Stores, also in Lagos (prepared costumes for Ayò Adésànyà's *Èèbù Ìkà* and *Gbòkògbòkò*). For a table containing the list of some female costumiers and the names of the YHV for which they took charge of the costumes used, see Appendix II.

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4.1.4.0 Types of Costumes

There are different types of costumes used in film production. They can be classified as; Everyday types, Presentational types and the Re-presentational types.

4.1.4.1 **Everyday Types:** These are the costumes that depict the life pattern of a group of people in their day-to-day activities. They reflect the social class, mood or life-style of the characters wearing them.

4.1.4.2 **Presentational/Symbolic Types:** They are the costumes that present the particular role a character has to play in a scene/film. They symbolize the position, profession or tribe of a character. A palm-wine tapper, for instance, will be inappropriately dressed if wearing *agbádá* or a suit while at work. Rather than that, he will be clad in a tattered and weather-beaten shirt with a climbing rope across the chest. A Yorùbá traditional medicine man, too, will be better dressed in a jumper or *agbádá* with cowrie shells, gourds and other charms sewn on it than in a shirt and trousers. A Fulani character will need *Babariga* and not *Dàrísíkí*.

4.1.4.3 **Re-presentational Types:** These are the ones that depict the way of living of a people in the distant past. These are usually used in epic or historic films like *Ogun Adùbí*, *Àfònjá*, *Sàngó*, *Òrànmiyàn* and *Jógunómí*.

4.1.5 Effects of Costumes on Visual Arts

The costumes worn by the artistes make it possible for the viewers or audience to identify and distinguish each and every member of the cast in a feature (home video) film. For example, the afro hair style worn by Dòtun and other male undergraduates on the campus, their wide-end trousers⁴ and their "boogie-boogie" platform shoes in *Ó Le Kú* written by Akinwùnmí Ìsòlá, enable the viewers to know that the story dates back to between the mid-60s and the early 70s.

Costumes also make it possible to identify the position or social class of a character, and as such the role he/she has to play. In *Enikan Ó Layé*, the agbádá and cap worn by the late Adébímpé Adékólá (Ìrèti), adorned with neck beads, and her holding the horse-tail while sitting on the throne in a palace, allow the viewers to know that she is the regent after the demise of the former monarch in Ìgògó town. As it is wont of a female regent, she is the ceremonial head while the preparation for the installation of a new king lasts, after which she compulsorily hands over to the new elected king. This she does by proclaiming Prince Adéwálé (who initially dressed in a complete suit, but later changes to full native attire of agbádá, puts on a crown and holds a beaded walking stick) as the new king. The regent's and the king's costumes differentiate their status in Ìgògó community. They cannot be compared with the ones used by Bàbá-Baálé – an old peasant who lives in the palace or that of Chief Èlèsòó – a member of the king-makers' council.

Costumes also make it easy for the viewers to know the trade or profession of the characters. In *Lágidígba*, for instance, the pair of dyed shorts and short-sleeved tight-fitting tops worn by Ìdòwú Phillips, Lánre Hassan Adésinà and other women while in a thick bush, depicts them as hunters. In the YHV film, *Ewúro*, the laboratory coat worn by Yemí Sódímú and the stethoscope he has round his neck, portray him as a doctor among the other medical personnel in the hospital where Ajínáwó is admitted.

In Nigeria, where there are many ethnic and sub-ethnic groups, costumes used in the films produced in such a country will make it easy to identify the group to which a character belongs and his/her likely cultural background. In *Réré Rún* written by Oládèjò Òkédíjì, the character, Aláwode, is seen dressed in *babariga* – the northern Nigerians' type of *agbádá* (flowing gown for men) to suit the role of the Hausa money doubler he has to play.

The state of mind of a character at a particular period in a film can also be depicted by the costume he/she wears. In *Àbèké Alámàlà* by late Fúnmi Martins, when Àbèké's food selling business is booming, she dressed in expensive lace native attires with voluminous head-ties, well styled. When she becomes pre-occupied with Bòdé (her son)'s problem (Bòdé turns mad after eating at Àbèké's food canteen; a taboo by Àbèké's medicine-man), she is seen dressed in faded ànkàrà⁵ apparel with neither head-ties nor jewelleryes. In *Ìbínú Olúkòsò* by late Adèbimpé Adékòlá, Tólá – Kèmi's friend, is seen well dressed in a blouse and jeans trousers, dancing merrily at Kèmi's birthday party, but when she becomes

mad, she is seen in dirty rags, going about the street. Without her uttering a word, the viewers are able to see that Tólá is no longer in control of her mind.

Age can also be depicted through the costume worn by an artiste. Murphy Ray Éjìwùnmí is dressed like an old man in *Àlámú Sèniyàn* to play the role of Ajoké's father.

4.1.6 Women in the Art of Costuming

Although both males and females handle the costumes that artistes use for theatrical purposes, women are known to feature in this section of the film industry more than men⁶. We discovered that women have more creative and re-creative ability than they are portrayed as having in the Yorùbá patriarchal set-up. These women can be classified as the old hands who have been in theatrical/filmic business for quite some time, the lettered professionally-trained ones and female artistes who are learning on the job.

Mrs Bísí Ogunde (Làjà Ogunde's wife) who handled the costumes for *Alé Ariwa*, *Oní Nńkan* and *Tení N Tení*, Mrs Lánre Hassan Adésinà who handled those of *Aséwó To Re Mecca*, *Alàgbà Benjamin*, *Ókò* and *Ìlú Le* and Mrs Fúnmiláyò Ógúnṣolá (Late Ísòlá Ógúnṣolá's wife) who handled *Erù Ágbà* are some of the women in the first group.

In the second group, we have costumiers like Tóyin Bifárin, who handled the costumes for *Jógun Ó Mí* and *Áfónjá*.

Olúyémisí Adébòwálé of the third group handled the costumes used in *Lepa Shandy*, *Olúwèrì Magboojo*, *Elébòlò* and *Kòtò Ayé*. Tóyòsí Adésànyà, who is also in the third group, took care of the costumes used in YHV films like *Òrò Omọ Le*, *Ètò Mi*, *Enìkan Ò Layé* and *Aborè*.

The female costumiers in the third class are many because more and more youths (professionally trained for the job or otherwise) keep joining the industry and almost everyday in the last five years. Some of them have in fact done very beautiful jobs and are famous. Some of them are Mojí Oláiyá, Tóyìn Sàláwù, Tópé Fáladé, Sèyí Fiye, Mulikat Adesida, Wùnmí Olùmègbón, Kafilat Saleem and Salome Èkétúndé (See Appendix II).

Education, or professionalism, to be precise, plays a variety of roles in any human endeavour, especially as far as division of labour in an industry or establishment is concerned. If anyone excels in a field of career (although such a person may be naturally endowed for it), there will be a teacher or group of persons who taught him/her, or discovered the inherent ability in such a person. Among all the female costumiers' work that we studied, Tóyìn Bifarin and Yémisí Adébòwálé's works stand above the others. Although Láńre Hassan-Adésínà did a very good job with the costumes she handled in *Oduduwa*, for which she told us, "I read many books about Yorùbá history and life style of those days before I could do it"⁷, her work cannot be analysed in this study, for the medium of dialogue in the film is the English language and not Yorùbá. We critically studied

the works of two of these female costumiers who were willing to give us their attention – Toyin Bifarin and Yemisi Adebowale.

4.1.6.1 CASE STUDY I: Tóyin Bífárin's costumes in *Jógunómí*

The film (*Jógunómí*) is a historically themed one, based on the inter-tribal wars that were common in the Yorùbá kingdom in the past. The hero of the film is Jogunómí – Mòmòdù, the only son of a devoted mother.

Being historical, the costumes chosen by Tóyin Bífárin are very suitable, for they are of the re-presentational type to re-present the life style (by mode of dressing) of the Yorùbá people at that period – the eighteenth century. Most of the costumes used are made with hand-woven or hand-printed local fabrics and they are basically *adire* (tie and dye) and *asọ-òkè* (up-land handwoven cloth). The only two types of foreign fabrics used are woolen material and Arán (thick polyester-like soft-to-touch material), which signify that the story dates back to the slave-trade era, when human beings in Africa were exchanged for cheap things like clothing, mirror, guns, bullets and alcoholic drinks, from the West. The costumes are given to the characters in such a way that distinguishes sex, class, profession and religious status.

**A YORÙBÁ WOMAN DRESSED IN ÌRÓ,
BÙBÁ, GÈLÈ AND ÌPÈLÉ**

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**A YORÙBÁ MAN DRESSED IN
EMBROIDERED AGBÁDÁ**

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**TÓYÌN BÍFÁRÌN SELECTING BEADS FOR
ARTISTES**

While the male (actors) used different types of clothes like *dànsíkí*, *agbádá*, *gbáriyè* and *gbérí* over trousers like *sóóró*, *kámù*, *abidán* and *dígò*, the women used *bùbá*, *iró*, *gèlè*, *ipèlè* and *Ìborùn* – as these are the few traditional wears of the Yorùbá woman. As for under-garments, the men in the film have no role whatsoever to play that needs their under-garments being revealed. On the other hand, Morísólá's *Yèrì* (underskirt) made with light blue *àdirè* material, is shown while she is trying to seduce Akínrópò when Jógunómí (Morisóla's husband) is at the war front. The children's clothes vary. Few girls wear *buba* and *iró* like the women, while some just tie wrappers across their chests. All the boys have wrappers crossed round their necks and tied at the nape of their heads. These children are the ones caught as slaves.

Social stratification in Yorùbáland showing the *olówó/olólá/olórò* (the rich/influential/wealthy) like the royal family, the merchants and the war-lords and their families on one side, and the *akúùsé/tálákà/kò-là-kò-şagbe* (down trodden masses/poor/average) like the aged, peasants and petty traders, are well distinguished by the use of costumes in the film. Ọnírìşà Ọlógbénlá, the king of Ifè – the cradle of the Yorùbá, is dressed in expensive costumes like Damask and white *aşo-òkè*. Damask (a foreign fabric which must have been gotten in exchange for many slaves) is a hard fabric which is seldom laundered; as such, it is worn once in a while. It can only be owned by a royal person like Ọlógbénlá who definitely will have many other ones he can wear casually and have washed, if he so wishes. The white *aşo-òkè* that he wears on Prince

Adérinlórò's wedding day is another costume that shows affluence. A pauper – an *akúúsé* – dare not wear white expensive *aṣo-òkè* like that; it would cost a fortune. Apart from that, white gets dirty easily, if a poor man wears it often (for he will not be able to afford other ones), it will soon lose its brightness and become *aṣo-iwólè* (clothes for casual wear). Ológbérifá's wives, too, are dressed in beautiful *àláári* (red/wine coloured *aṣo-òkè*) and Adérinlórò the groom, wears red *àrán* made into *dànsíkí* and *sóóró*.

Látòósà, the Ìbàdàn leader, is also dressed in comely royal costumes of *Sányán* throughout. Although his costumes are not as expensive and expressive as those of Onirisà, he, too, is of no mean importance. Even Šitù, Látòósà's son, goes about the town with his drummers, clad in *gbáriyè* and *sóóró* sewn with *àláári*. To show his position as being different from that of other (ordinary citizen) youth, he has another big *àláári* wrapper tied round himself. He goes to Mojóyìn (a beautiful daughter of a retired war chieftain) who herself is dressed in *búbá*, *iró* and *gèlè* made with a mixture of *àláári* and *sányán*, to show off.

Ódúgbèsan, the Ìjèbú slave merchant, is another rich person as indicated by his *àrán* costume. The *àrán* is made into a beautifully designed *gbáriyè* top and *abidán* trousers. Odúkólá, his son, wears a well patterned *àdirẹ* (tie and dye) *dànsíkí* and *sóóró* when the two of them are at the slave market.

For the poor masses – the commoners and the average persons in the cast, Tóyìn Bifárin chose costumes which are within the reach of people of their class. They are made to wear weather-beaten *aṣo-òkè* and *àdirẹ* or woolen

materials that have seen better days-clothes that the royal, the affluent or merchants will wear to do dirty jobs at home. Gbólèyí's two sisters who come to tell her that they are leaving Ibadan for their home town because of the upheavals caused by Lábàlú's raids, are dressed in dark coloured *búbá* made with woolen fabric over old lighter coloured wrappers of *aşo-òkè*. Their *idikù* (headties) are of other colours and materials. Their dressings show a sombre frame of mind. They are in a sad mood, for black or dark coloured clothes portray melancholy.

While Awópetù the Ìlàrí (representative) from Ìbàdàn is dressed in Gbàriyè that is well embroideired over a *sóóró* pair of trousers and goes to Èkìtì land to collect tribute from the people on behalf of Látòòsà, the poor farmer whose farmland Awópetù covetously seized, is seen dressed in just a pair of trousers – a tattered one made with *aşo-òkè*; his bewildered wife fares no better.

The poor villagers of the Ibadan suburbs whom Gólóbà (Lábàlú) goes to raid can be seen dressed in tattered clothes with contrasting coloured tops worn over trousers or wrappers.

TÓPÉ FÁLADÉ

The costumes that Tóyin chose for the war chieftains like Jógunómí, Lábàlú (Gólobà), Ògèdèngbé and Fábùnmi, when they are not at the war fronts, are very realistic. Yorùbá war leaders were known not to be merely famous (*gbajúmò*), but also rich. This is because slaves caught during raids are shared among them after they might have given the king his own portion. These slaves and other items like domestic animals, clothes and beads, are either sold or converted to personal use. Some of the slaves are used as source of labour in the farms and the beautiful ones among the women slaves become wives. It was a period when the number of a man's wives and children (who are also sources of cheap labour on the farms) determines his wealth. These are the facts that Toyin considered before robing Jógunómí in a multi-coloured *dansiki* and *sóóró* made of *àrán*, Lábàlú in *gbániyè* and *sóóró* made with *sányán* and Ògèdèngbé the Ìjèsà warrior in *Petùjẹ* sewn into *agbádá*, *bùbá* and *sóóró*. Both Jógunómí and Ògèdèngbé had *etù* caps (*filà*) on their heads. Lábàlú had the *abeti-ajá* cap on and Àjìké (Jógunómí's wife) is dressed in *órjàwu àlàári*.

The warriors of Ìbàdàn, Ìmèsì and Ilèsà are the professionals whom Tóyin used costumes to identify in the film in such a way that will not cause disorientation in the minds of the viewers. The Ìmèsì warriors and Ìjèsà alliance are dressed in indigo coloured *aṣo-òkè* sewn into '*gbéni*' and '*dígò*'. Cowries and different types of charms are sewn on these 'uniforms'. The Ibadan warriors, on the other hand, are dressed in *àdìrè* uniforms, made into *gbéni* tops and *dígò* trousers. They also have charms sewn on their uniforms. The war leaders

(*Jógúnómí*, *Lábàlú*, *Fábùnmi*, *Abídogun* and *Ògèdèngbé*) have more charms on their own uniforms than their troop members have. This easily shows their leadership roles and their wealth of military experiences because a warrior acquires more charms almost everyday, for he sees and experiences different travails and test of power at the war fronts.

The Yorùbá people are a very religious people. Their traditional religion is polytheistic in nature and the different 'òrìsà' (gods) worshipped include tutelary ones, the patrons and guardians of the communities concerned and the ethnic and locally deified heroes and heroines (Fádípè 1970). These òrìsà, heroes and heroines, have their individual peculiarities in terms of period, mode and objects for sacrifices, ways of lives of their priests, priestesses and devotees and taboos governing their 'relationships' with human beings. Of great importance is the mode of dressing associated with these 'òrìsà', especially those worn by their priests and priestesses. This important factor is well understood and given consideration by Toyin when the costumes to be used in *Jógúnómí* were being determined. *Abòkè*, (he who worships the hill) the priest in charge of *Òkèèbàdàn* (the *Ìbàdàn* hill) is seen dressed in white costumes of *dànsíkí*, *sóóró* and *gélé* (head-tie) throughout. The same goes for the female devotees who are dressed in white *irò*, *bùbá* and *gélé* on the day of sacrifice to *Òkèèbàdàn*. White signifies peace and purity, two things that can aid victory at the battle front.

Orúnmilà, an oracle and òrìsà in its own right (Fádípè 1970:269), is of high repute in the Yorùbá traditional religion. It is consulted when decisions

about certain things are to be made or when the reason behind an occurrence has to be known. It is generally believed that *Ifá kii purò, Òrúnmilà kii sèké* (Ifá does not tell lies, Òrúnmilà does not deceive). Ifá (another name for Òrúnmilà)'s sincerity and purity is what Tóyin Bifarin is putting across to the viewers by dressing the *babaláwo* (diviner) who consults Ifá for Jógunómí's *àkòsèjáyé* (primordial horoscope), in white *dànsíkí* top and *sòpòrò* trousers, with *abeti-ajá* cap. Although Jógunómí and Onírìsà Ológbénlá also dress in white while supplicating at their individual shrines, it is not compulsory for them to do so since the film does not reflect the particular òrìsà they are propitiating. Onírìsà, for instance, is merely seeking the support of the dead kings of Ifè who reigned before him to avenge Prince Adériniórò's disgrace by the Ìbàdàn people. The Ìmèsí warriors are dressed in their war costumes while propitiating Ògún, the god of iron, before embarking on the trip to the battle front. Ògún is another popular òrìsà because it is worshipped by all in the Yorùbá traditional religion because almost everyone uses tools or household utensils made with iron. People need not wear costumes made with palmfronds and red materials like the Ògún priests before it can be worshipped or sacrificed to.

Tóyin Bifarin did a remarkable work in *Jógunómí*. The costumes used create real and precise index in the YHV film, they are really re-presentative. There is no character in the film wearing clothes made from materials like lace or Ànkàrá, which were brought into Yorùbá land years after the *Jógunómí* episode. Even the earrings (like the neck wears) used by all the women are made with

beads. The communicative visual aspect of *Jógunómí* is properly signified in the minds of the viewers. It makes it easy and interesting for the viewers to create meanings to the messages encoded in the film. However, Tóyín would have made Lábàlú wear another cap while at home, and not white *abetí-ajá*. Peter Fátómilólá who played the role, is well known in the industry to act the roles of *babaláwo* in many YHV films. A white *abetí-ajá* will suit him better as a *babaláwo* than as a war chieftain and even if he must wear it, it could have been sewn with a fabric of darker colour.

4.1.6.2 CASE STUDY II: Yémisí Adébòwálé's Costumes in *Kòtò Ayé*

Kòtò Ayé was written and produced by Alhaji Yèkínnì Ajíléyè, but financed by Chief Akíntúndé Ayèni. The film is themed on the Yorùbá belief in the evil that witches are capable of doing. The story is woven round a quarrel that ensues between Àbèní-Agbón, a witch and Adédùntán, whose food was not served to one witch at the naming ceremony of Adédùntán's twin babies. At their coven, all the witches in Ayégbègé decide to revenge.

Associations of witches are secretive and cultic, as such it is not easy to ascertain their modes of operation. Yémisí told us that her research to gain access to knowledge about the witches proved futile, since no one is ready to pronounce him/herself a wizard or witch. What she eventually did was to study previous films like late Hubert Ogunde's *Alye* and *Jaiyesinmi*. With this, she is able to reflect the belief of the Yorùbá people that there are three kinds of

witches; the 'white' ones (àjé funfun/àjé olómọ (mother-hood oriented) who are not wicked but kind and protective, so tagged because white signifies peace. There is also the 'red' type of witchcraft (àjé pupa), who will not harm anyone first, but woe betides whoever steps on their toes. Red signifies danger. If one sees the signal and does not move near it, such is safe, but if he/she decides to ignore the signal and goes ahead to foment trouble, it will be as if he/she holds live wires. The third kind is the àjé dúdú' (the black witches). Black symbolizes darkness, death, evil, mourning or sadness. The black witches are believed by the Yorùbá people to be forever going about, looking for whom to devour.

Yémisí made the witches tie wrappers that have colours that suit their typology, when they go to their covens for meetings. Each one of them ties the wrapper to her chest and uses another wrapper of the same colour as girdle to her waist. It gives them the appearance of one that is combat-ready. These costumes and the white powder dusted on their unkempt hair, gives them a weird and bizarre look.

Apart from the costumes of the witches, the clothes, which are traditional Yorùbá wears (*asọ-òkè*), that Yémisí selected for the other characters are very suitable. The king's wives like Èwàtómì and her co-wives are dressed in beautiful wrappers, beads and headties that befit wives from a royal family. Alhaji Yèkínni Ajiléyè, who played the role of 'Alfa' in the film, is suitably dressed in white *bùbá*, *sòdrò* and *agbádá* with a fez cap well turbaned on his head.

4.2.0 Make-Up

The urge to apply different types of items to parts of the body or shape them, in an attempt to make one more attractive, appears to be naturally inherent in both male and female human beings. However, females are universally known to apply cosmetics more than the males. This, in our opinion, is due to the fact that, among human beings, it is more common for men to be the ones making love advances to women. For this, a woman needs to make herself attractive to the opposite sex. This is not to say, however, that males' attention is all a woman makes up for; if well dressed and comely, a woman, or a man for that matter, will go about with confidence, for a Yorùbá maxim says:

Bí a ɣe rin, làá ko ni

One is related to by other people in accordance with one's appearance.

Traditionally, the Yorùbá woman's ways of making herself more attractive are hair weaving, braiding or plaiting in different patterns⁸. Wáji (a kind of black dye made from plants) is then applied to the hair with a soft cloth; to make the hair darker and glossier⁹. The Yorùbá woman makes her skin beautiful by having tattoo, in different shapes and designs like bird, fish or reptile, made on it. Her name or her lover's, can also be tattooed on her arms or shanks. She can also have *péle*¹⁰ made on her face to make it attractive. On the bridal night or

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during the naming ceremony of her child, the Yorùbá woman can rub *osùn* (camwood dye) on her face, arms and legs to make them smooth and shiny. She does the same to her new-born child. *Tiróó*¹¹ is also used by her (and by some men, too) to trace out the lower and upper eyelids in order to make the eyes attractive.

The use of cosmetics by men in the Yorùbá traditional set-up, as said earlier, is very minimal. They shave their heads clean¹² or trim the hair very low. Some men shape their teeth in such a way that all their canines look like incisors. Like women, some men have tattoos made on their bodies or they put *pélé* on their faces. If a man does more than these or makes up like a woman, the Yorùbá will refer to him as *Olóórayé* (A man of easy virtues).

4.2.1 Making-Up for Dramatic Purposes

People do not pay much attention to the every day kind of make-up. This is because not everybody on the street is likely to be looking at one (except if such a person is a film or television star). The case is, however, different when an artiste is appearing for a live show or film recording, wherein mass communication is evident. Such an artiste's appearance must not only be comely, but also relative to the role he/she has to play. How (well) made up (and costumed) the artistes are in a film, compensate for what they lack naturally in appearance, or highlight and boost their natural endowments; to fit in for the roles they need to play. This goes a long way in attracting the

attention of the viewers or audience to a (video) film. If, for instance, an actress is to play the role of a rich grandmother in a Yorùbá video film, she will be expected not only to wear expensive costumes, but also to be fat and jolly, for the Yorùbá will say:

Òyòkòtò yòkùn, àgbà tí ò yòkùn, ahun ló ní.

Fat and rotund, an elderly person who is not fat, is stingy.

If a naturally fat person cannot be found to act the role, a slim actress could be made up to appear fat, otherwise the viewers may find a 'slim rich grandmother' unrealistic in the Yorùbá setting and as such become disinterested in the film. Make-up is therefore an essential part of artistes' appearance. According to Folúkẹ́ Dáramólá, "it speaks to the viewers even without the artiste opening his/her mouth"¹³, like the costume. This is why Oscar Brockett (1991:380) says make-up is used to cover all the parts of the body (the artistes') that are not covered by costume.

Apart from expressing the state of being, mood, age or disposition, make-up can also be used to counteract the effect of the distance between the viewers and the artistes on the stage/screen, to compensate for the intensity of lighting effects which tend to 'wash out' the natural facial colours and it also gives

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mobility to the expressive features of the artistes and thereby allow them more facial versatility while acting¹⁴. We have also observed that if well made up to suit the apportioned role, the artiste will have confidence in him/herself, the effect of which will be gaining the full attention of the audience or viewers. Such an artiste will be at his/her best while acting, otherwise he/she might make a mess of the imitation.

While scholars like Derek Bowskill (1979:300) are of the opinion that make-up is a personal matter to an artiste, because it is only he/she that is playing the role, he/she alone has, at the particular time of acting, the thought and feelings of the character being imitated; Brockett (1991) has a counter-opinion. To Brockett, the ability of an artiste to make him/herself up for a feature film may be inadequate. Even if such an artiste looks into the mirror for assessment, the reflection of what he/she has in mind – which may be wrong, is all that will be seen. In our own opinion, making up as an important aspect in enhancing the viewer/audience – artiste's relationship, is a division of the video film industry that calls for specialization and professionalism. We found out that in the Yorùbá home video industry, the division of labour being done gives room for specialization of make-up artists.

4.2.2.0 Types of Make-Up

There are several ways by which make-up effect can be achieved on the visuals. Painting and the use of prosthetic pieces are two of the popular ways. The face and the other exposed parts of the artiste's body can be painted by applying colours, highlights, rouge and shadows. Examples of prosthetic pieces (falsies) that can be used are; false eye-lashes, nose, beards, teeth, nails, wig and artificial hair pieces (weave-on).

Taking paint as his focus, Wilson (1991:367-368) has grouped make-up into age, character, racial/ethnic and special-effect types. According to Wilson, age make-up is used when there is a difference in an artiste's actual age and the age of the character he/she is imitating. Character make-up is to make an artiste thinner or fatter to suit his/her role or to emphasize certain distinctive features¹⁵. Skin and hair colouration, according to Wilson, is done when there is a difference in the race of an artiste and that of the person being imitated. Special-type of make up, in Wilson's typology, is that used for clowns and jesters.

In the course of studying the different ways by which make-up artistes in the Yorùbá home video industry achieve make-up effects, we have classified make-up into three basic types. These are straight, character and fantastically-styled make-ups.

4.2.2.1 Straight Make-up

This is the type used in everyday life; the normal type that can be worn even by people who are not acting. It is used in realistic plays when roles about everyday life are to be played, or when an artiste naturally has the features of the character to be imitated. An old man whose hair is naturally grey, does not need to have chalk or white powder rubbed on his head to make him appear old. He might just rub talcum powder on his face to make him comely. Straight make-up is done by applying normal face powder (the shade of which depends on the artiste's natural skin colour), creams or foundation, lip colour, rouge for the cheeks, eye-brow pencils and mascara. For instance, Adébáyò Sàlámi and Rachael Oniga, who played the roles of Mr and Mrs Williams-Wonúọlá (Fathia Balógun's parents) in *Omọ Mummy* (produced by Rónké Ọjọ), did not need to make use of special make-up for their roles. Adébáyò's appearance is in order as Fathia's father, while Rachael Oniga's age, look and size befit the role of the mother. All Tóyọsí Adésànyà (the make-up artist for the YHV) did was to make them apply normal face powder to counter the effect of lights, Rachael's eyebrows were, however, trimmed and her lips lightly coloured, to give the look of the affluent, well-lettered mother she had to play. Fathia, too (a slim-figured mother of two in real life), did not need to be given any extraordinary make-up; she has the look of the young university undergraduate she was to play.

4.2.2.2 Character Make-Up

This is the type for deliberate change of an artiste's normal facial or bodily appearance to suit the appearance of the character to be imitated. This involves the use of paint make-up and prosthetic pieces, among other things. With character make-up, an artiste can be made to appear like a hunch-back palm-wine tapper. Dots made with plastercine and painted red, which Yémisí Adébòwálè applied all over Ìyá-ìbejì (twins' mother) in *Kòtò Ayé*, make her groaning and lamentations appear real – the make-up blotches look like boils.

4.2.2.3 Fantastically-Styled Make-Up

This type of make-up is the exaggerated form. It is more often than not used on clowns or jesters for comic effect. It is very common with children's shows. We discovered that clowns and jesters in the Yorùbá home movie industry have peculiar ways by which each of them applies make-up and the substance they use, that it becomes a kind of trade mark for them. If another clown or jester uses the make-up for which a particular jester is known, such is seen as a copy-cat.

Artistes like Àdimérù – Bàba Sùwé and Móládùn – Kẹ̀kẹ̀lẹ̀wù (Babatunde Omídínà and Mònsúrátù his wife) come readily to mind here. Àdimérù is well known for rubbing shining and oily black substance that looks like used engine oil on his face, neck and palms, while Móládùn is always having whitish powder –

popularly known as 'Moju' (zinc oxide) overdone on her face, and the 'pélé' on her face thickly traced out with black eye-brow pencil dipped in olive oil.

4.2.3.0 **Women As Make-Up Artists in the Yorùbá Home Video Industry**

A make-up artiste's duty is to purchase, design and apply different types of items ranging from powder, paints, and colours to falsies, on artistes at shooting locations, so that they can fit in for roles which otherwise would have been unrealistic. However, there are cases when all the make-up artist has to do is to assist or direct an artiste on the kind of make-up item to be used. This happens in a case where the make-up to be applied is the straight type or when the artiste is very familiar with the particular make-up.

The make-up designer needs to be very intelligent for the job is the kind that needs a lot of re-creativity and improvisation. He/she must be evaluative and non-assuming for the shooting scripts for a feature film must be well read and understood. A make-up artist must be ready to research into the historical and cultural back-ground of the films to be worked upon. This is to be able to differentiate the fashion trends operating in the different settings of the film, like Grace Adinku-Hassan has been able to do in *Ó Le Kú*, a YHV produced by Tundé Kélání.

As mentioned earlier, men in the Yorùbá traditional setting do not concern themselves with much making up in their mode of everyday dressing. This is why even in the movie industry of the Yorùbá, men do not normally work as

make-up artists. It is a division of the industry dominated by women and the women therein have been doing beautiful jobs. Among these women are Rose Ojinji, Yémisi Adébòwálé, Grace Adinku-Hassan (who are also costumiers), Kafilat Saleem, Fúnmi Tijání, Wúnmi Olùmègbón, Tóyòsí Adésànyà and Salome Èkétúndé. (For a more detailed list of these artists, see Appendix III). While make-up artists like Grace Adinku-Hassan, Rose Ojinji, Tóyòsí Adésànyà and Yémisi Adébòwálé went through post-secondary school education, most of the others learnt make-up on the job.

Studying their productions at locations, we found out that these make-up artists use paint make-up more than they do prosthetic ones. The paint make-up they use are usually made of items within their reach (in terms of finance and accessibility). Examples of these are powders, creams, lip colours and liners, eye shadows, plasters, bandages and food colour¹⁵. Some of the prosthetic kinds of make-up used are wigs, artificial nails, false teeth and false eyelashes. Where the thin physique of an artiste needs being made up as in character-type, these artists use items like clothes or foam materials to pad up such an artiste at different parts of his/her body where protrusion is needed.

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For example, such applications can be put at the back (near the nape of the neck to make an artiste look like a hunch-back. An example can be seen in *Ó Yátò* where Ìdòwú Afólábí had to pack soft clothes together and wrap them round Ọmọtọlá Jáládé Èkéíndé's abdomen in order to make her suitable for the character – 'pregnant Mosún'. "Were it to be in the United States of America or Britain, there are plastic-made 'pregnancies' with attached strings that can be worn round the abdomen and fastened at the back. It is neater and more comfortable"¹⁶.

4.2.3.1 CASE STUDY I: Tóyòsí Adésànyà's Make-Up Work in *Ètó Mi*

Ètó Mi was written and produced by late Fúnmi Martins. The story is about the life of Tèmiládé who is married to Adétáyò when the latter is poor. Adétáyò becomes rich with the help of his wife but forgets this when he becomes wealthy. He acquires more wives and abandons Tèmiládé. Fate intervenes, and Tèmiládé meets Fèmi who assists her financially.

At the initial stage, Tèmiládé gets pregnant and she is worried in a nightmare by a man trying to have sex with her. The 'pregnancy' looks very real, for Tóyòsí used two baby's pillows packed in a big pillow case. This she put on Tèmiládé's abdomen and used two safety pins to fasten the two edges of the

A DISPLAY OF TỌYỌSÍ ADÉSÀNYÀ'S MAKE-UP KIT

pillow case to Tèmíladé's underskirt. Wearing a free-gown on this, Tèmíladé appears like a woman who is about three months pregnant. When the man in the nightmare has his way, Tèmíladé loses the pregnancy. The blood that is trickling down her thighs is, in reality, a mixture of liquid (canned) milk and red dye. The loss of the pregnancy pains the couple and Tèmíladé is seen crying. The 'tears' on her face are actually drops of water which Tóyòsí used tearstick to drop on Tèmíladé's eyes while the camera was taken away from her (Tèmíladé).

Adétáyò is always having a serious migrainous headache in the film. Each time he is to have this ailment in a scene, Tóyòsí sprinkles water lightly on his forehead, so that he appears to be sweating profusely as a result of pain. Tèmíladé once goes to attend a party when Adétáyò is busy playing love with Bímpé, his new wife, and will not follow Tèmíladé. Due to the fact that Tèmíladé is leaving the unhappy environment of her home, to meet friends at the party, she is happy for a while. At this point, Tóyòsí makes Tèmíladé up beautifully by applying foundations, face powder, lipstick, eyebrow pencil and eyelid shadows. The happiness felt inside is thus revealed outwardly, giving the scene more colours. When the camera shows Tèmíladé's face as she enters her living room when she 'comes back from the party', her make-up is a little bit smeared and she has 'sweat' on her forehead.

There is a scene of 'heaven' in the film. It is a flashback to where Dúrójayé (Temilade's ex-husband) and his son, that Adétáyò uses for money ritual, have pity on suffering Tèmíladé and decide to help her. Heaven is

believed to be a place of peace, joy and everlasting bliss. As a result of this, Dúrójayé and his son's faces are powdered by Toyosi and their lips slightly touched with lip gloss, so as to reflect the bliss of 'heaven'.

Adétáyò returns from America with nothing, after being duped by Bímpé. He meets Fóláké who seduces him with charms. The charm used is *Tiróò* (native eye liner). For this, Tóyòsí used the real *Tiróò* for Fóláké's upper and lower eye lids. Setting eyes on Fóláké, Adétáyó is 'completely swept off his feet'.

Alhaja Àbèní hears of what Adétáyò is doing to Tèmiladé her friend; she decides to pay her a visit. Having just arrived from America herself, Alhaja Àbèní dresses smartly and Tóyòsí makes her face up heavily, by using cheek rouge, thick coatings of lipstick and eyelid colours. With her big loop-earrings, Alhaja Àbèní looks like a black American pop singer. Tèmiladé wears no make-up at all in this scene for she is unhappy. Alhaja Àbèní is surprised to hear the bad treatment that Tèmiladé is receiving from Fóláké despite the fact that Adetayo and Fóláké are living under Tèmiladé's roof. Hearing Alhaja Àbèní's voice, Fóláké comes downstairs to insult her. Alhaja Àbèní is up to the task; she sings to insult Fóláké to the extent that she (Fóláké) bursts into 'tears'. To show that the words of the song hit her very well and the tears are flowing ceaselessly, Tóyòsí uses petroleum jelly to rub Fóláké's face before applying the tear-stick. This makes the drops of water to stand out well on Folake's cheeks before dropping.

Fóláké has an accident (caused by Fémí's ghost) when she goes to collect charms from a native doctor to kill Tèmiladé. She is rushed to the hospital for

treatment. When Adétáyò learns of Fóláké's accident, he goes to the hospital to see her. Getting there, he presses Fóláké's swollen forehead and blood gushes out. The 'blood' used here is the left over from the one used on Tèmiladé's thighs when she had a miscarriage earlier.

When Tèmiladé and Adétáyò reunite, and Tèmiladé is to carry a sacrifice to the forest so that Adétáyò's headache will stop, Tóyòsí rubs petroleum jelly all over Tèmiladé's face, neck and back so that her 'sweating' from the fear of walking through the forest alone, will be pronounced as it is.

Tóyòsí did a very remarkable job in this film. It gives the film the necessary index to allow the viewers to monitor the progress of the mood and intentions of all the characters.

4.2.3.2 CASE STUDY II: Rose Ojinji's Make-Up Work in *Àfònjá*

Àfònjá is themed on the disintegration that occurred in Yorubaland after the reign of Aláàfin Aólè of Òyó and how it led to the infiltration of the Fulani into Ilorin (Johnson 1921:258-263). This film is an historical one; as such, the artistic work for it is re-presentational in nature.

The major area of Rose's focus for make-up in the film is the face, followed by the head. This is because there is no character used in the film whose physique (beyond the face) or gait had to be 'fixed'.

The make-up job that Rose did for this film can be grouped into two types; character and straight. The 'character' ones are those she did to highlight

the tribal and ethnic origin of some of the characters, while the straight ones are the everyday type used to make the face attractive and to shield it from the effect of recording lights.

A tribal mark of six vertical lines (three on each row) is made on Àfònjá's cheeks to make him look like the Ìlorin people. Rose also gave Ológóló-Àfònjá's personal assistant, a sharp slanted stroke (bàrà mú) on the left cheek-towards the nose. This is probably to distinguish him as a slave or alien who came close to the corridors of power. Álími's female relations, too, have three straight marks made at the two corners of their mouth, as seen when they are arriving in Ìlorin from Sokoto, on Àfònjá's invitation. These 'Fulani' women's noses are 'pierced' and an earring each is inserted. Rose also gave Álími (a role played by normally clean shaven Yemí Àmódù), a prosthetic side burn, moustache and beard, to make him look like a Fulani man.

Rose also used white talcum powder to achieve old age on some characters in the film. Aólè's beard and moustache, for instance, were dusted with powder to make them white. The same goes for Àfònjá's dead father who appears in a dream, to warn Àfònjá against dispersing his 'herd' so as to get new cows. To convince the viewers that the character Àfònjá is a middle-aged rather than an aged man, which accounts for his virility at the battle-fronts, Rose gave Àfònjá's moustache a paint of black colour.

Apart from the face as seen above, the head is another part of the body which Rose gave attention in this film. The women whose heads are uncovered

in the film, like Aólè's wives, Bàálè Ìwéré's wives and the female dancers, have their hair plaited in different Yorùbá traditional hair styles like *sùkùú*, *kólésè* and *ìpako-elédè*. The men, who have no caps or turbans on their heads, have their hair trimmed low or are clean shaven. Bàálè Ìwéré's head, for instance, is clean shaven as seen when he removes his cap and dares Àfònjá and his men to kill him. The two Ìlári (emissaries) sent to Àfònjá by the Òyó people about the installation of a new Aláàfin have their heads shaved clean at one side and the hair trimmed low at the other. This is to re-present the tradition by which the messengers of the Aláàfin of Òyó were identified in the Old Òyó Empire, so that they could be accorded the respect due to the Aláàfin.

Straight make-up with eye liners, face powder and lip colours was also used. For instance, Bàálè Ìwéré's wife's eye-lids were traced with eye-brow pencil and the effect is like having used the native *biròò* - it makes her face look comely. The lips of the 'Fulani' women are also coloured and a black dot is made with black eyebrow pencil on the forehead (between the two eyebrows) of each of them. This complements the 'Fulani' hairstyle on their heads, their looped earrings and the single earring fixed on their noses, to give them the Fulani-woman look. All the characters' faces were given a light layer of face powder to counter the effects of the lights used for the film shooting.

Rose's job in this film was well handled. The faces and the heads are her major areas of work here, and she did a good job on them. However, she would have done better if she had used a more permanent and darker paint for

Àfònjá's tribal mark. The mark appears too artificial and thus comic. Nevertheless, her make-up complements Tóyìn Bífárin's job of the costumes used in the film.

4.2.4 Combining Creative and Re-creative Jobs

Division of labour, which is a process whereby individual persons or sections in an establishment are given special duties to perform, is done to bring about qualitative and efficient productivity. Division of labour, therefore, calls for specialization or professionalism in chosen careers, so that each and everyone may give his or her best in their field.

We found out in the course of this study that some women in the video film industry play as many as three roles. For instance, apart from playing the role of 'Àjoké Elébòlò' in *Elébòlò*, Yémisí Adébòwálé was also in charge of the costumes and make-up for all the artistes who constituted the cast of the film. The costuming and make-up in *Òrò Omọ Le*, *Enikan Ò Laye* and *Ètọ Mi* were handled by Tóyósí Adésànyà. Dọlápọ Idris also did those (costuming and make-up) of *Ọbàkan*, while those of *Àdùnní Olówò Erú* were handled by Ìdòwú Àiná. Earlier than now, Tópé Àlàbí, apart from singing into film; did costuming and acted in Yorùbá home video films. In *Ewúro*, for instance, she handled the costumes, played the role of Ajínáwó's nurse and sang into the film. These days, she still sings into Yorùbá films but acts only in Christian films.

Another role for which these women also double, is that of wardrobe-mistress. This is the person who in the film industry collects costumes from the costumier, labels them with the name of the users, scenes, dates and time of shooting at locations. It is the duty of such a person to make the costumes readily available to the members of the cast when needed. However, this job is yet to be spelt out separately from that of the costumier in the Yorùbá home video industry – it is done by whoever prepares or handles the costumes.

We are of the belief that it is better if one specializes in handling just one division of any industry. He/she learns readily on the job by gaining more experience and as such will be able to give his/her best in terms of productivity. Ìdòwú Phillips, Sọlá Sóbòwálé, Tólá Oládòkun and Folúkẹ́ Dáramólá, for instance, have never been any other thing in the industry than actresses. Tópé Àlàbí was not as popular as she is today when she was combining acting with singing and making up in a single YHV. It is not a matter of 'knowing' how to do these things; any woman can apply face powder or lip colours and dress other people up; what we are hammering on here is specialization to bring about perfection.

We are of the opinion that most of these women may be testing their hands at the different available jobs in the movie industry, with the intention of specializing in particular ones later, and we are not saying that they have made an error in their combined duties. What we are saying, in effect, is that we would rather have each of them focusing their whole attention on one division/section of the industry, than being Jack-of-all-trades and master of none.

Discussing this issue with Adébáyò Sàlámi (Bello), the current president of the Association of Nigerian Theatre Practitioners (ANTP), he said plans are underway to ensure that no one in the industry handles more than two areas, and that, in due time, even the two areas will be reduced to one as more and more professionals join the industry. This, in our opinion, will go a long way in bringing about more qualitative productions from the industry.

NOTES ON CHAPTER FOUR

- 1 Ògún is the god of iron in the traditional religion of the Yorùbá people. It is worshipped by a large number of people as almost everyone uses items made with iron in one form or the other, either domestically or industrially. Festivals are celebrated yearly in most Yorùbá towns and villages like Ìjèbú Rémo, Òndó, Ìjerò, Adó-Èkitì and Ilésà; to honour and appease Ògún. This is different from sacrifices or propitiation made to Ògún for protection or as directed by Ifá oracle. The yearly festival comes up in Òndó town during the first few days of September.
- 2 *Orósùn* festival is celebrated by the people of Ìdànrè in Òndó State every year. This is to commemorate the deliverance of the people by *Orósùn* from their neighbourhood enemies when he was alive.
- 3 These are the different costumes worn by the *Eegún Alaré* (dramaturges) for their displays (See Adedeji 1969).
- 4 This wide-end trousers was known as "J.B." (James Brown) in those days. It was so named because James Brown, an American pop singer, was fond of wearing it then.
- 5 Àńkára is a brand of African clothing fabric. It is usually multicoloured and made of cotton. (Recently the Àńkára pattern is being printed on polyester fabric). It originated in Accra – capital of Ghana. The word 'àńkára' is loaned from 'Accra' into the Yorùbá lexicon. Àńkára has both the cheap and expensive (Wax) brands. The cheap brand is worn casually.

- 6 Some of the male costumiers in the film industry are Níyí Adékúnié, Múkálà Àríyò, Músílíù Arówóşęgbé, Gbólęga Adésànyà and Ibrahim Sanni.
- 7 Mrs Láńre Hassan-Adésínà (Ìyá Àwèró) told us this in a telephone conversation with her on the 7th of April, 2003.
- 8 See C. L Adeoye (1980:169-174) for different kinds of hair styles.
- 9 See Faleti (1972:31).
- 10 This is a horizontal or vertical short line made on both cheeks, done by both male and female, but more common among females. It is only made if one has not made other tribal marks on the face.
- 11 '*Tiroo*' is a black powdery substance usually put into a small gourd or gourd-shaped metal container (*Ilé e tìróò*). The cover of this gourd has a pointed end. To apply *tiróò*, the cover is opened and the pointed end applied to the eyelids, as the pointed end would have the black powder on it. This will make the eyelids very black and attractive.
- 12 Except if a man is an adóşù-Şàngó (a Şàngó devotee) and leaves a sizeable amount of hairstrands at the centre of his head.
- 13 In an interview with her on the shooting location of *Ádiitú* at Ìjèbú-Òde on 7th September, 2003.
- 14 The face, more than any other part of the body, is often made up for visual appearances. This is because it is an easily noticeable vehicle for expressing mood and disposition. The age (real or otherwise) of the artiste can also be read on the face.

- 15 These food colours are mixed with substances like water or milk to give effects like blood gushing out of a wound, sores or lacerations.
- 16 Tóyin Adégbolá told us this in an interview with her at the reception hall of Lagos Television Authority (LTV 8) on 6th of July, 2003.

CHAPTER FIVE

GYNOCRITICS OF YORÙBÁ HOME VIDEO FILMS

5.1.0 Introduction

Ruthven (1989:9) in his discourse about literary criticism says:

Gender is a crucial determinant in the consumption of literary discourse ... modes of representation are principal ... signifiers ...

In the Womanist theory, gendering Literature is an aspect of the constant search for African aesthetics that fosters self-knowledge in such a way that there will be no indiscriminate separation (Kọlawọle 1997:169). As mentioned earlier in this study, oral literature has been remarked by many scholars as a domain of art wherein visibility and audibility are not exclusive to the male gender. The same can be said of the production of Yorùbá home video films. This is because women do not only act the characters in scripts written by men, they, too, write, act and produce their own story-lines. This is a great improvement compared to the passive roles of women during the celluloid film era wherein Simbiat Sówólé was the only woman who produced a reversal film. The involvement of women in creative arts or writing brings about the issue of gynocritic study.

Gynocriticism is the study of woman as the producer of textual meaning. The term was first used by Elaine Showalter (1979:29-41). She anglicized the French phrase *la gynocritique* to mean a concern with women:

... as writers The history, styles, themes, genres and structures of writing by women: the psychodynamics of female creativity, the trajectory of the individual or collective female career: and the evolution and laws of female literary tradition.

5.1.1 Gendering Literature

While scholars like Suzanne Juhasz (1977(b) 96-103) are of the opinion that there is something unique about women's writing or literary products, others like Joyce Carole Oates (1988:11) believe that literary language is sexless. Scholars who share Oates' idea believe that creative literary works are 'androgynous' – a term which Nancy Bazin (1972) claims to have been interpreted by Virginia Woolf to mean 'sexlessness' as used by Coleridge in 1832. However, people like Daniel (1974:171-184) suspiciously believe that androgynism is merely males annexing females, to make them (the males) more versatile and powerful. In the same vein, Anne K. Mellor (1983:148), taking Blake's writing as her point of reference, says:

... theoretical commitment to androgyny in his prophetic books ... is undermined by his habitual equation of female with the subordinate or the perversely dominant.

In our own opinion, there could be areas of the arts where creations or productions can be androgynous, but definitely not in literary, communicative or visual art works like texts, music, poems or films. This is because the aggregate of a person's behaviour, reasoning and life-style is formed by his or her experiences from birth. It is influenced by the immediate and larger societies in which one finds himself or herself. As it is, females in a patriarchal society have been acculturated to see and accept the males as being superior. They are to be respected and looked upon for protection. This will definitely affect the reasoning and world-view of a female, in such patriarchal societies. She lives virtually in a man's world, where if she does not talk 'like a lady', she is ridiculed and subjected to criticism as being 'unfeminine', if she does learn, she is ridiculed as unable to reason or think clearly, unable to take part in serious discussion: in some sense, as less than fully human (Lakoff 1973:48). This cannot but be evident in her art work, either in accordance with her acculturation (as it was, to some extent, in her oral works), or in rejecting the subversive aspect of acculturation, as it is fast becoming visible in her recent textual and filmic literary creations. We say this because we agree with the French maxim that *le style c'est femme meme* - 'You are what you write' (Ruthven 1989:105). We have come to observe that these women's often gynocentric films (in terms of the themes of the film) were written the way they have been, not only because of what or who they are, but more especially because of where they are constrained to be operating - in a patriarchal society.

5.1.2 Themes of YHV Films Produced by Women

G. H. Lewes as quoted by Ruthven (1989:117) opines that of all the departments of Literature, fiction is the one to which by nature and circumstance women are best adapted. "This is because the domestic experiences which form the bulk of women's experiences find an appropriate form in story writing".

We have come to notice that more often than not, the major themes of most films produced by women are centred on domestic issues like husband – wife relationship, mothers and daughters-in-law, daughters and their mothers or issues that concern the welfare of women in a community. Where these gynocentric themes are not the major ones in women's films, they are either one of the sub-themes, or are implied. These themes do not only show women as transmitters and vectors of cultural, moral, spiritual and social values (of the Yorùbá), but also as means to demand for changes.

We wish to point out, however, that, since art is part and parcel of culture, if culture is dynamic, art also must change with time. As the females' struggle is at present striving hard to strike the appropriate chord in our patriarchal life-style, the themes of women's filmic works are beginning to move with the wind of change – gradually. The films they write are attestations to their creative ability and pointers to self-assertion, expression and actualization.

5.1.3 Women as Transmitters and Vectors of Societal Values

As mothers, women have been known over the ages to rock the cradle and thereby transmit the culture, morals, norms, spiritual and social values of the society. A very large percentage of the socio-acculturation going on in any society is done by women. In *Igbésè* a YHV film written and produced by Modúpé Johnson, Àláájà (Wálé's mother) and Bímpé (Wálé's wife), are seen telling Wálé the proper way to dress up traditionally. They make him realize the dignity in wearing *agbádá* on top of *bùbá* and *sóóró*, instead of putting it (the *agbádá*) neatly on his arm, when attending ceremonies. They also tell him to don a native cap (*filà*) whenever he is dressed up in *agbádá*, for the Yorubá people say:

Bá a tí rìn làá ko ni

The way one dresses determines the respect/recognition to be given him/her.

Mary Joseph in *Oba Áwúre* is out to teach young ladies who are newly married or are about to get married, the importance of good conduct in marriage. Mary is saying that a greater amount of premium is placed on the good behaviour of a wife by the members of her husband's family, rather than on her beauty. In the film, Akin takes Bukky to his mother as the girl he intends to marry. His mother is initially against it, on the grounds that Bukky already has a child and as such she is more exposed to life than Akin who has never married. When Fémí,

Akin's friend, appeals to his friend's mother, that Bukky is a nice lady, she gives her consent.

Things are going on smoothly at the initial stage of the marriage until Bukky takes to the advice of a friend that she (Bukky) should not allow her mother-in-law to live under her roof again. Bukky victimizes her mother-in-law to the extent that Akin has to go and rent an apartment for his mother. After this, Bukky is able to charm her husband to the extent that the former becomes an imbecile who not only cooks and washes his wife's undergarments, but also signs off a five million naira (N5,000,000) contract to an office clerk, so that he (Akin) can help his wife to mind her small boutique. On the long run, Bukky's secret charm is discovered by her mother-in-law (with the help of a prophet). Akin regains his senses, beats Bukky black and blue and sends her packing from his house. The maxim: *Ìwà lóba àwúre* (Good conduct is the best 'good-luck' charm) is well depicted in this film. Before a person can be referred to as an *omolúwàbí* (a complete gentleman or lady) in the Yorùbá culture, his/her conduct must be very good; he/she must be above board at all times. (Májàsán 1967; Abíódún 1983; Oyèrindé 1985; Adélékè 1986).

Fidelity is another issue raised by Mary in *Oba Awúre*. She appears to see mothers as the custodians of moral values. This sub-theme is reflected with the relationship between Fúnmi and her parents. While her mother chides her for dating several men from whom she collects money, Bàbá Lábúlé – her father, quarrels with his wife for not allowing his daughter to be free to do as she wishes.

All the mother's attempts to make Fúnmi see the danger in the way she lives her life, fall on deaf ears. Eventually, Fúnmi is diagnosed to be HIV positive and her father, too, gets infected as a result of being cut by a razor blade while trying to steal money from his daughter's bag.

5.1.4 Self-Actualization of Women

The sociological set-up of the Yorùbá puts the man as the head of the home. While alive, he owns all the property in the house, wives and children inclusive. A woman, therefore, has virtually no recognition of self-worth. Her achievements (which were determined by her husband) were viewed in the light of her being one man's daughter or wife. Her primary assignment was to produce and rear children for her husband. Hence the common question when asking about the number of children in a marriage – *Ọmọ mélòó ló bí fún ọkọ rẹ?* (How many children has she been able to produce for her husband?) Engaging in any economic venture by her is secondary and must be consented to by her husband.

The time has now come when the Yorùbá women (and other African women, too) begin to ask questions about their identity and the social space created for them in the patriarchal setting. Images of women as depicted in the stories they (the women) write, have grown from characters with naïve and passive outlook (Kóláwọlé 1997:81) to more dynamic heroines, confronting tradition and every socially constructed tool of subjugation and oppression.

Tóyin Adégbolá (Aséwó tó Re Mecca) has pointed out that we are in an age where the woman, too, can provide for her home and even for members of her extended family if the need arises. Women no longer have to be dependent for economic survival on their husbands. In *Máyòwá* – a YHV written and produced by Tóyin Adégbolá, Dèjò runs into financial problems and has no means of taking care of his wife and children. Tólání, his wife, has to travel to London to sweat it out, in order to take care of the family. She is able to get employed by Waterloo Subway Station as a cleaner. She sends money home regularly to Dèjò, with which the latter is able to pay the rent, feed their children and pay their school fees.

The Yorùbá man can marry as many wives as he wishes. He will put them under his roof and feed them. In late Fúnmi Martins' film – *Ètò Mí*, the reverse is the case. Adétáyò, Tèmiladé's husband, lives in the building belonging to Tèmiladé with his other wives, Ìyá Ifé (Ifé's mother) and Ìyàwó Kékeré (the most junior wife).

If not for the fact that Màmá Biólá (Biólá's mother) is a graduate-teacher in a secondary school, how could she and her family have fed and how could she have sent Biólá to the University, when her husband – Bàba Biólá (Biólá's father) in the YHV – *Òwò Àlè* (written and produced by Bukky Wright) retires from service after working for thirty-five years, and is not paid his gratuity and pension even after two years?

In the same vein, Martins, an unemployed graduate, has to depend on Sègìlọlá, his fiancée, for his up-keep. He goes to her in her office every time he runs short of money. Through the YHV – Sègìlọlá, Yémisí Jaiyeólá, the writer and producer, is saying that if a woman can make up in the morning and demand for feeding allowance from her husband, nothing stops Martins, too, from 'stooping low' to take feeding allowance from Sègìlọlá. Her self-actualization as a chartered accountant should earn her respect.

5.2.0 Gynocentric Films: Revolt Placards

Some of the films written and produced by (Yorùbá) women, are protestant. They have themes which are against women's denigration, oppression and marginalization, under patriarchy. Reading these films closely, one finds them to appear like placards borne by aggrieved persons during protests. The revolution through these films is sometimes subtle and peaceful like Sọlá Sóbòwálé's *Ayòmidà*, or militant like Àníké Obot's *Jógunómí*. By the virtue of their roles in the Yorùbá movie industry, these women are trying to modify, re-define or totally change some values and ethos which have earlier than now been overtly undynamic, to the disadvantage of the female gender. In this section, we shall examine gynocritically, *Ayòmidà* (Whence my joy?) and *Jógunómí* (Let there be peace) by discussing the major characters in the films and what their roles signify.

5.2.1.0 Synopsis of *Ayọmidà*

Jùmòkẹ falls head over heels in love with Lékan, a worker at a cottage water-packing industry. In protest against her parents' rejection of her association with Lékan, Jùmòkẹ leaves her parents' palatial home for Lékan's one-bedroom apartment, where she gives birth to a son – Ayọ (Joy) out of wedlock. All attempts to bring Jùmòkẹ back home by her parents are futile. She is determined to struggle with Lékan to get to the top. Ayọ dies in a swimming pool at a hotel, while Jùmòkẹ is chatting with an ex-boyfriend. This leads to her being hospitalized at a psychiatric hospital for several months. She refuses to continue living with Lékan after her discharge from the hospital, rather, she goes back home, where she learns that her parents are dead. Having no other person to turn to, she goes to Arówólò – her father's friend and business partner. Arówólò's wife, who is also the Chief Executive Officer of his company, is barren. Being in a society where a great premium is put on owning children, a society where a childless wife has no right to her spouse's estate after his demise – no matter what she might have contributed, Arówólò's wife is ready to stage a revolt against such ethos of marriage. Not minding to hurt a fellow woman, the desperate Chief Executive arranges with Arówólò to impregnate Jùmòkẹ, with the intention of making her child theirs.

5.2.1.1 Characterization in *Ayòmidà*

Solá Sóbòwálé did a very remarkable job with the characterization of *Ayòmidà*. Although the producer of the film, she takes up a less glaring role compared with that of other cast members, but then, her role is very determining in the film – very pivotal.

The characters in the YHV are of two groups - the first being the protagonists like Jùmòké, Lékan, the police officers and the judge, the second group is that of the antagonists. Here we find characters like Arówólò, Mama Nanny, the steward, the kidnappers, the sailors and the Chief Executive Officer.

5.2.1.2 Jùmòké

Jùmòké is the lead actress in the film. She represents all victimized women under patriarchy. She is an only child. Falling head over heels in love with Lékan, she leaves home in protest against parental interference, believing that she can get to the top with Lékan. The death of Ayò her son and the beatings she received from Lékan whom she feels is the best thing that can ever happen in her life, are too much for her to hold, so she loses her mind. Her devastated condition is comparable to the domestic, economic, political and legal acts of violence which many women experience under patriarchy. After Jùmòké's discharge from the psychiatric hospital, she refuses to live with Lékan for she feels betrayed. However, because of having been socially acculturated to see the male gender as being superior and stronger, she runs to Arówólò for

protection. She has no other choice anyway, for on getting home after being discharged from the psychiatric hospital, she finds out that her parents are dead. Arówólò dehumanizes her: he drugs her before raping her and denies her the ownership of her father's share in the business Arówólò runs. Jùmòké is used like a machine by Arówólò to procure a son for his barren wife. The poor woman is denied the mother-child bliss with her son by Arówólò. Men oppress her and she fares no better in the hands of fellow women. Jùmòké is even ridiculed in the court, as she appears not to be sure of how she got pregnant. At the end, Jùmòké is vindicated, and she is able to claim all her parents' property. Her kidnapped son is found and she goes back to her parents' home to start life all over again.

5.2.1.3 Arówólò

Arówólò represents most men under patriarchy. He is a very close friend and business partner of Chief Olówólàgbà – Jùmòké's father. He capitalizes on Jùmòké's loneliness and health problem to use her for his own selfish benefits like male chauvinists all over the world do to women – whom they have rendered weaker, inferior and enfeebled. Refusing his love overtures, Arówólò cunningly lies to Jùmòké that he must have made such a demand under the influence of alcohol. Determined to use Jùmòké as a baby-producing machine, he drugs his personal assistant (Jùmòké) during an official tour and rapes her. He does this several times afterwards, and each time Jùmòké confides in him about her 'wet

dreams', he cleverly tells her that this must be due to hallucination, as Jùmòké is a psychiatric patient. He readily agrees to father Jùmòké's unborn child, so as to 'remove the shame she has brought on her family name'. Apart from violating Jùmòké's right and having no respect for her person, Arówólò encourages other people like the nanny and the cook to oppress Jùmòké. He denies her the joy of being in the company of her little son and will not release her father's capital share in their joint business to her. Arówólò betrays the trust that Jùmòké has in him; he kidnaps her son. He is also ready to give a bribe of twelve million naira (for a start) to the law enforcement agents, in order to be successful in using and dumping Jùmòké. However, as rich and wise as Arówólò thinks he is, he is proved foolish. The arrangement between him and his rich wife is to fly Jùmòké's baby out of the country immediately after birth. The foolish man he is, Arówólò leaves mother and child in his house for long, to the extent that the people around come to know that he has married his friend's daughter, and that he is the father of her son. Not only this, Arówólò swallows the plain-clothes police officers' baited questions hook, line and sinker, until he confesses his wicked actions against Jùmòké and he is nabbed.

5.2.1.4 The Plain-clothes Policemen

Policemen are law enforcement agents. They are to protect the lives and properties of the citizens. In this film, they represent the creative force that created both genders, without the intention of having one sex oppressing the other. They monitor both sexes and make sure that the gender that oppresses the other, is brought to book.

The plain-clothes policemen already have Arówólò's name on their list of suspected persons in the town. During the course of the kidnap case before the court, these policemen intensify their monitoring of Arówólò. By this, they are able to find out that Arówólò keeps the supposedly kidnapped child in the care of the captain and the sailor inside his personal ship. Their baited interrogation sets the denouement of the film in motion. Foolish and unsuspecting Arówólò is trapped in the set web, they make him confess all his atrocities.

If not for these policemen, Jùmòké would have lived the rest of her life in an asylum, because she suffers a lot of trauma in the film. She may even have committed suicide, but for the fact that these men find her kidnapped son and she comes to have something in life that worths living for. It is these men who teach Lékan to plead guilty and own up to having been the one who raped Jùmòké and kidnapped her son. By this, Lékan is able to avoid being jailed innocently. These plain-clothes policemen repay each person in the story according to his/her conduct.

5.2.1.5 Lékan

Lékan represents the few men who may not agree with being referred to as feminists/womanists, but who respect the individual right of a woman. Lékan is the father of Jùmòké's drowned first son, although they are not legally married. Lékan loves Jùmòké. Although he beats her out of frustration of their drowned son, he begs her afterwards and he is ready to have her back after Jùmòké is discharged from the psychiatric hospital. Lékan is protective: even after Jùmòké leaves him for Arówólò, he still goes to visit her. He even goes to meet her at an amusement park where she takes her son, to warn Jùmòké of Arówólò's nefarious activities. Despite the fact that Jùmòké testifies against him in the court (as Arówólò asks her to do), Lékan still tells Jùmòké while he is in the cell, that he loves her and will love her for the rest of his life.

5.2.1.6 The Nanny and the Steward

These two women represent women who have been socially acculturated to believe that women are in a man's world, where women are given just a little space to exist. 'The man is the head; he is stronger and wiser and therefore must be respected and obeyed', even if it means violating the rights and freedom of a fellow woman. Mama Nanny, who claims to have "thirty-five years experience in taking care of the children of the royals and rich in London", is an accomplice to Arówólò's schemes. She follows his instructions to the letter, denying Jùmòké free access to her son. The steward, too, treats Jùmòké like a lunatic and bosses her around the house. If not for the steward's going to report

to the nanny, that Jùmòké is upstairs cuddling her baby, which makes the nanny snatch the baby from her and takes him back to his crib, may be the kidnappers would not have met the baby where Arówólò told them that he (the baby) would be, the night the baby is kidnapped.

5.2.1.7 **The Chief Executive Officer**

This is a role played by the producer of this film herself – Sólá Sòbòwálé. She, too, is like the nanny and steward. She joins hands with a man to oppress and denigrate a fellow woman in her bid to revolt against the societal ethos of marriage (among the Yorùbá) which is set to make her a loser of her husband's property just because she is barren – an estate which she has contributed so much to, that she has even risen to being its (the estate's) chief executive officer. Initially, she sees no justifiable reason why Arówólò her husband should offer Jùmòké a salary of one hundred and eighty thousand naira (N180,000) monthly as his personal secretary. She later co-operates with Arówólò, and they both agree that Arówólò should impregnate Jùmòké so that the baby may become hers (the executive officer's), since she is barren and age is not in her favour. This woman is an evil genius. Had it been that Arówólò followed her instruction, to let them take the baby from Jùmòké immediately after birth and run away abroad, Jùmòké would have found it difficult, if not impossible, to ever set eyes on her kidnapped child again. This executive officer is so devilish and cunning that the viewer does not suspect that she is Arówólò's wife until towards

the end of the film – she gives Arówólò a free hand to visit Jùmòké in the apartment in which he keeps her (Jùmòké) while she herself steps aside.

5.2.1.8 Conclusion

Conclusively, Şolá Şóbòwálé did a remarkable job of *Ayòmidà* (Whence my joy). The film would have been better titled *Ètò Mi Dà* (Where are my rights?). We guess this is not possible because late Fúnmi Martins had already produced a YHV titled *Ètò Mi* (My Rights). After highlighting the facts that the woman is oppressed, Şolá Şóbòwálé then gives a clarion call to the men, that the African (Yorùbá) woman recognizes the home as an important factor in the social set-up of her society and she is willing to run the home with her husband, if she is treated and related to without oppression, marginalization and denigration. This is why Jùmòké says:

Mi ò mò bóyá Lékan şì lè gbà mí padà, torí mo şì nífèé
rè ...

I do not know if Lékan will be willing to take me back,
because I still love him...

However, in a telephone conversation with Şolá Şóbòwálé on whether she is interested in feminists'/womanists' affairs, she said:

Ewò niyẹn kẹ? Èyin alákadá lẹ niyẹn. Èmí wo nńkan
tó ní lọ lówùjọ ni o, mo dẹ şe fiimù lé e lóri, kí gbogbo
ayé lè mò pé mewaàá n şelè láàárin lókọ-láya.

What is that supposed to mean? That is for you people in the academic. I just look at what is going on in the society, and I made a film about it, so that everybody will know that a lot happens between husbands and their wives, between men and women.

5.2.2.0 *Synopsis of Jógunómí*

Ìbàdàn town, headed by Ààrẹ̀ Látòòsà ("Ààrẹ̀" is a military title equivalent to Field Marshall in modern day military hierarchy), has a very formidable army under the leadership of Jógunómí. Ìbàdàn's military strength makes it possible for her to be a threat to other Yorùbá towns and villages from whom she collects tributes. However, some of these neighbouring towns are kidnapping children from Ìbàdàn to sell as slaves to white people at sea ports. Ìbàdàn women, under the leadership of Gbéléyí, go to Látòòsà's courtyard to protest. Látòòsà gives his word to see to the end of the slave raiders. At a point, Látòòsà calls his army leaders and tells them to stop all inter-tribal and ethnic wars, so that peace may reign in Yorubaland. War leaders like Jógunómí, Abídogun and Babalọ́jà agree to let peace reign, but Lábàlú goes on to raid towns and villages around Ìbàdàn, terrorizing the people, calling himself "Gólòbà".

Women come to Gbéléyí – Jógunómí's wife, to report Gólòbà's nefarious activities around Ìbàdàn. Gbéléyí leads the women to Látòòsà to protest. Once more, Látòòsà promises Gbéléyí that 'Gólòbà' will be brought to book. Ìbàdàn warriors find "Gólòbà" to be Lábàlú, and they kill him and his men. After this,

Awópetù, Látòósà's representative at Ìmèsí-Èkìtì, is killed by Fábùnmi – an Ìmèsí-Èkìtì war leader, for raping his (Fábùnmi's) wife. Initially, Látòósà sends just a handful of warriors to Ìmèsí-Èkìtì. Most of the warriors are killed; so Látòósà now declares real battle against Fábùnmi. Till the end of the film, Ìbàdàn is not able to defeat the coalition forces of the Èkìtì-Parapò (Ekitiland as a whole) and the Ìjèsà warriors. Látòósà, the Ìbàdàn head, has to leave home to join his men at the battlefield. Jógunómí, the Ìbàdàn war leader, dies mysteriously on his way home from the battle front.

5.2.2.1 Characterization in *Jógunómí*

The characterization of the YHV film depicts a societal hierarchy of the royals, the wealthy and the awesome warlords and members of their families as the most distinguished and respected class. The representatives and personal aides of the people in the first class, forms the second class. They, too, are given a lot of respect, because of the people they represent. The third class comprises the peasants, farmers and petty traders – people who are neither famous nor have blue blood running in their veins.

In the first class we have people like Onírìsà Ológbénlá the king of Ilé-Ifè, Látòósà the Ìbàdàn head, Òdúgbèsan the rich slave merchant and warlords like Jógunómí, Ògèdèngbé, Fábùnmi, Lábàlú and Abídogun. The Ifè emissaries and Awópetù-Látòósà's representative among the Èkìtì people are examples of people in the second class. Some of the commoners of the third class are the market

women, the slaves and Gbólèyí's two sisters who come to report to her that they are leaving Ibadan town.

In this section, we shall discuss only the key characters whose roles are signifiers in the film. These are Látòósà, Jógunómí, Láleètán, Lábàlú and Gbólèyí.

5.2.2.2 Látòósà

He is used to represent men in patriarchal societies. Látòósà has power over Ìbàdàn and other Yorùbá towns, like men have over women. He oppresses the towns and villages under him by sending his representatives (fellow oppressors) to collect tributes from them. Látòósà, however, fears women who know how to stand for their right. He quickly agrees to please the Ìbàdàn women under the leadership of Gbólèyí, when they protest against Látòósà's docility towards the Ìjèbú slave raiders and Gólóbà's terrorism around Ìbàdàn. Látòósà has forgotten the Yorùbá maxim that:

Igi tá à fojú réénà, ní gbé ni şubú

The tree stem that one least expects, can cause one's fall.

He dissuades Jógunómí from declaring total war on the people of Ìmèsí-Èkítì when Fábùnmi kills Awópètù. This is comparable to men who refer to women and matters concerning them as "minor issues". Látòósà tells Jógunómí:

O fèè lè sígun saáyàn ... Ìmèsí? Ìlúbinnín? Àtìmèsí Òkè àtì
Ìmèsí-Ìé, èwo ló san ninú wọn ... Èkítì wọ? Èkítì họra bùè-

bùè kán lùgbé wò! Èkìtì tí ò níṣé tí ò lǎbò ... Nígba tó bá jiyán tán, loó máa gbò ìṣokúṣọ nígboro ẹnu rẹ. "Kó ọ ti wí? Kó ọ ti sù? Úwọ ni mẹ fòó sí ...

You can even descend too low as declaring war against cockroaches ... Ìmèsí? A town as weak as women? Both up-land Ìmèsí and the Ìmèsí homestead, is either of them worth serious consideration? Who are the Èkìtì people? People that scratch their body all about their bushy land. People who are virtually jobless and feckless ... When an Èkìtì man devours a bowlful of pounded yam, you start hearing him blab nonsense. "What did you say?" "What are you talking about?" "You are the one I am talking to"

...

Only one warrior comes back to report that the Ìmèsí-Èkìtì warriors were underestimated. He says:

Òjò peégún lóde
 Òde ò dá a
 Igi tá a fojú réená ...

It rained on the masquerade
 The outing was terrible
 A tree stem that we least expect ...

Hearing this, Látòósà becomes terrified, he comes to realize that "Ìmèsí-ìlúbinrun" (Ìmèsí – the town that is a weakling like a woman) is a force to be

reckoned with. He and his men are not able to defeat the "weaklings" even by the end of the film.

5.2.2.3 Jógunómí

He stands for men who do not see anything wrong in oppressing the opposite sex, but who are ready to be enlightened about the rights of women. Such men are ready to work hand in hand with women if enough strength is put into convincing them about the advancement that can result from the cooperation with the female gender. At the same time, Jógunómí is used to highlight the fact that if a man thinks he is too strong to be faced by any woman, just a little opposition from the woman can cause such a man's fall.

Jógunómí is an only child of an aged but supportive mother. With his mother's support, he becomes a respected and famous warrior. When Látòósà bans the military men from further wars, Jógunómí accepts to stop fighting, face his farms and devote more time to family matters. Jógunómí realizes that the fact that the tiger walks slowly does not mean that it is a coward – it is just being calculating. To him, the Ìmèsí-Èkítì people who Látòósà refers to as "women", can wreak havoc, and he is proved right.

In this film, Àniké Obot is saying that as strong as Jógunómí is, his strength and fate is in the hands of women. If not for Láleètán, Jógunómí's mother, he would have been killed by Ọnírìsà Ọlógbénlá (the King of Ifè)'s psychic attack. Apart from this, Jógunómí dies without struggling with Death at

all, like warriors are wont to do. He dies just too easily; immediately *Àsáké* (his cousin) accidentally knocks down the earthen-pot that contains the *gbékúde* (Tie down Death) that *Láleètan* has the medicine-man make for him.

5.2.2.4 *Láleètan*

She is *Jógunómí's* mother. Though kind-hearted, she is stoic in character. *Láleètan* represents women who are gentle but strong-willed. Women who work, though gently, but are persevering enough to see what they lay their hands on to a conclusive end. She does everything within her means to fortify *Jógunómí*, her only child, against attacks, physical or spiritual. She stands in as the head of the home for her many daughters-in-law each time her son goes to war. She loses her sight so that her son *Jógunómí* may survive her. The loss of *Láleètan's* sight here is pregnant with meaning. *Àníké Obot* is saying that accepting the leadership of the man as the head in the Womanist theory, the woman will have to close her eyes to so many things, but like *Láleètan* does, she has to forge ahead, to ensure that her supportive role brings about peace, harmony, love and progress in her home and in her society as a whole.

Jógunómí dies immediately the earthen-pot hanged breaks. When the news is broken to *Láleètan*, she handles the loss "like a man". One will expect her to weep, roll on the floor and refuse to be consoled, but she does not shed more than a few tears.

5.2.2.5 Gbólẹ̀yí

She is Jógunómí's wife. She is a strong woman to be reckoned with in Ìbàdàn. Gbólẹ̀yí is the militant type, a character acted by Àniké Obot herself. Gbólẹ̀yí tolerates no cheating and oppression. She leads Ìbàdàn people to Látòósà's court when the Ìjẹ̀bù slave raiders are kidnapping children from Ìbàdàn as slaves to be sold abroad at the sea-ports. Gbólẹ̀yí also tells Látòósà that it is the women (of Ìbàdàn) who bear the brunt of the wars. They became widows and women without children, who are never catered for after the death of their husbands, sons and other bread-winners at the battle-fronts. This is one of the reasons why Látòósà bans his men from fighting again. Gbólẹ̀yí feels insulted when Àjilé her co-wife, asks her and other co-wives to share out Arínkeré's firewood among them, so that the newest (and youngest) pregnant wife, may not need to haul firewood home from the farm. She makes Àjilé realize that being pregnant is not an ailment, as she, too, Gbólẹ̀yí, is a mother of many children. She comes home without carrying any firewood. Gbólẹ̀yí again leads Ìbàdàn (and its environs) women to Látòósà's court to protest Gólóbà's terrorism. It is a militant action that leads to Látòósà's order to his army that, whoever "Gólóbà" is, he must be captured, dead or alive. Gbólẹ̀yí acts as a kind of opposition leader to check the 'reign' of Látòósà. When Látòósà and his chiefs pacify Gbólẹ̀yí each time she leads a protest, she accepts and shows her readiness to co-operate with Látòósà. For instance, she leads the song:

Látòósà o ti gbàbòdè o

Dide wá á gbèjà wa ...

Látòósà you have been bribed

Stand and come to our rescue ...

when going to Látòósà's court for a protest against the kidnapping of children as slaves by Ijebu people. When Látòósà agrees to find a solution to the problem, Gbélèyí changes tune. She sings;

Ta ló sọ pé a ò ní baba?

Kàì a ní baba

Látòósà baba wa

Who says we do not have a father?

Stop it, we do have a father

Látòósà is our father ...

Gbélèyí is a very daring character. She goes to Ahójo (her husband, Jógunómí's friend) to accuse him of attempting to pry into her matrimonial affairs. She dares Ahójo to a physical attack by tearing the latter's clothes into shreds. Ahójo is so stunned that he is unable to do anything to Gbélèyí.

In the Womanist theory, physical confrontation or violence are things which women would want to avoid as much as possible in their struggles against oppression. However, the Yorùbá people say:

Ẹní máa bẹ̀şù ẓeun, şíbí ẓe á gun

He who must dine with the Devil, must have a long spoon

Also that:

Olóògùn ló lè şokọ àbíkú

It is the man who is well versed in native medicines that suits a born-to-die as a husband.

and;

Nítorí wèrè òde la şe ní ní tilé

We retain the mad persons at home in case of threats from the mad persons outside.

All these maxims, in essence, mean that there could be few occasions in the struggle against patriarchal denigration and oppression of women, when force may be needed to meet force. This does not mean that such women are non-conformists to societal orders, norms and ethos, but rather, they are giving the values of the society that are undynamic the force needed to change them. Such women, we noticed, are kind-hearted and peace-loving. For instance, the revolts that Gbólẹ̀yí leads in *Jógunómí* are not for her personal gains; they are for the benefit of all the Ìbàdàn people. When *Jógunómí* dies, she is very sad. In fact, she is the one that leads the dirge to mourn the death of the departed "hero".

5.2.2.6 Lábàlú

He is one of the war-chiefs. When Látòósà bans the warriors from going to wars, it is only Lábàlú who sees nothing good in allowing peace to reign in Ìbàdàn and other Yorùbà towns. To him, Látòósà does not want the warriors to be popular as he is, so that they will not be threats to his authority. Lábàlú can not declare war on any town of his own accord, so he starts to go round the suburbs of Ìbàdàn, to terrorize the people, and forcefully take their belongings. When the news about this gets to Ìbàdàn, nobody thinks it is Lábàlú that is doing such a thing, because he operates under the name; "Gólóbà". Lábàlú is eventually killed by Abídogun in a war declared against him by Látòósà, led by Jógunómí.

In this film, Lábàlú represents males who do not want peace to reign between genders. All attempts to make him see the advantages in the warriors' abandoning the war front, to face their farms and families, fails. Violence is the only language that Lábàlú understands. Womanists, as said earlier, want peace, equity and justice, if anyone refuses to identify with these, he will be seen as a cog in the wheel of a dynamic, vibrant and progressive society. This is why Lábàlú is found and shot by Abídogun, one of his military associates. Obot appears to be saying that any male who refuses to stop the oppression against the female gender will be swept away by the wind of change.

5.2.2.7 Conclusion

Aniké Obot's *Jógunómí* is a remarkable landmark in the Yorùbá woman's resistance against the marginalization, denigration and oppression of her patriarchal society through the film. A superficial view of the film may give one the impression that the YHV is a mere historical re-enactment. An in-depth critical analysis will, however, reveal that *Jógunómí* means more than what meets the eye, if such an analysis is via the Womanist theory. When writing the script, the gender issues in the patriarchal Yorùbá society/culture must have subconsciously (or otherwise) influenced her to refer to Ìmèsí-Èkìtì as "Ìlúbinrin" - a town comparable to a cockroach which with just a light foot-mashing, can be crushed. A town comparable also to women, whom La Bruyère (1688:92), as cited by Reiss (1989:13), has referred to as "ornamental objects existing for men's titillation". However, Obot wants the viewers to realize that "Ìlúbinrin" can not be easily silenced. One basic thing which makes their captivity impossible is the strength they have in "one voice", which is signified by the coalition of all Èkìtì towns and the support of the Ìjèsà people led by Ògèdèngbé.

5.3.0 Metafiction in Gynocentric Yorùbá Home Video Films

Literature in its aesthetic form creates a fictional universe where there is possible verification of reality at the experimental level of man living in the society ... imaginative literature is a re-construction of the world seen from a particular point of view ... of the author or hero ... unconscious re-working of

experience, fused with his own definition of a situation and his own values, that produce the fictional universe ...

(Bamidele 2000:4)

Metafiction as a literary device has become popular with women playwrights. It gives these women a mode to recreate the way certain values have been deployed to delimit the roles and importance of the female gender. Toni Morrison (as quoted by Cheryl Wall 1991:1) is therefore right to refer to women as being the subjects of their own narratives, witnesses to and participants in their own experience, and in no way coincidental, in the experiences of those with whom they have come in contact. To read the imaginative literature by and about women, is to learn about what they stand to present or represent. Patricia Waugh (1984:61) observes that metafiction unveils "how the meanings and values of the world have been constructed and how, therefore, they can be changed or challenged". To Gayle Green (1991:293), it (metafiction) is a powerful tool for a feminist critique, for to draw attention to the structures of fiction is also to draw attention to the conventionality of the codes that govern human behaviour.

The themes in the YHV films produced by women tend to say a lot about them and their immediate society. These women consciously or otherwise write fiction and sometimes real-life experiences in such a way that reality is recreated. Studying their films, we have come to realize that there is a direct

correlation between fiction and reality in the themes. The metafiction in their stories may be at personal or communal levels.

5.3.1 Personal Metafiction

Personal metafictional themed stories are those that tell about the life story or some incidents that have happened in the life of an author of a book or the producer of a film, or that has happened to their close associates. *Ètò Mí* (My rights) is a good example of such films. *Tèmíladé* (Mine is the crown) – a character acted by the producer herself (Fúnmi Martins) – is a gentle and humble housewife who will not quarrel with her rude and arrogant junior co-wives. She never quarrels with her husband Adetáyò, who, not minding that he lives under *Tèmíladé's* roof with his other wives, ill-treats her. *Tèmíladé* knows her right, but will not go for it. She leaves things in God's hands.

In real life, the late Fúnmi Martins was the gentle, homely and forgiving type. We once met, in the course of this study. It is no longer a grapevine rumour that Fúnmi has a baby for Sir Shínà Peters – a popular afro-juju musician (Olumide-Funmí's first child, confirmed this)¹. However, Shina Peters' wife (Sammy) did not allow him to bring Fúnmi into their home as a second wife. A Yorùbá maxim says,

Obinrin tó bá tì bímọ́ fún ni, ó tì kúrò lálẹ̀ eni

A woman who gives birth to one's child is not just a concubine (but a wife).

Such a woman has some right (*ètò*) to the property belonging to the father of her child. Fúnmi Martins was not ready to fight anybody. Olúmidé said:

My mother was a very gentle woman even to a fault. She would not hurt anybody ... she would not struggle for anything with anybody. She believed that whatever was hers, would definitely come to her. She never quarrelled with Sammy (Shina's wife) ... after all, they were both mothers of Shina Peters' children.

We feel, however, that while it is lady-like to be gentle, it is stupid to be too passive when cheating from another person stares one directly in the face. Force was needed to meet force; this is what Queen – Tèmiladé's friend, does when Adétáyò insults Tèmiladé in Queen's presence. This step is able to check the younger wife's exuberance and Adetáyò's arrogance, towards Tèmiladé. This is because Queen dresses him down, and asks him what he has to show for travelling to London for so many years. In as much as the womanist theory of the feminists' struggle does not favour the African woman being unsubmitive to her husband, the theory does welcome a challenge to a woman's subjugation by the male gender.

An example of metafiction at the personal level which is not directly personal to its producer (or author, as in the case of texts) is *Òrò Qmó Le*, written and produced by Táíwò Akínwándé (Wùnmí). Táíwò had a neighbour², Bólájí³, who carried a pregnancy for over three years without delivering it. All

attempts to get Bólájí to deliver through orthodox medication proved abortive. She was continuously blamed by her in-laws for rendering their son (Jídé)¹ childless. After much persuasion, Jídé heeded the advice that he should seek for traditional assistance to Bólájí's predicament. A native doctor told Jídé to ask his wife to confess a secret she had been keeping from him for over four years. Initially, Bólájí claimed not to keep any secret from Jídé, but when it appeared as if there would be no other solution, she confessed that she had a child (out of wedlock) while in the secondary school and that the child was with her mother. Jide was highly disappointed by Bólájí's deceit, but forgave her. It was only after this that Bólájí was able to deliver her pregnancy. It is this real life story that Táiwò reconstructed and produced as *Òrò Omọ Le*.

In the YHV film, "Bólájí" – a role played by Táiwò herself becomes "Wúràolá" and "Jídé" is replaced with "Olumide". The circumstances surrounding the controversial child in the film are that Wúràolá delivers a daughter for her former husband – Kúnlé, only to know a few days after delivery that Kúnlé had died in a road accident. She single-handedly continues to take care of the baby. Later, Wúràolá meets Olumide – an eligible bachelor. In order to marry Olumide, Wúràolá takes the baby to a day-care centre one morning, pretending that she will come for her after the day's work, only to abandon her there. The circumstances of the girl's whereabouts after being abandoned are reconstructed by Táiwò to the effect that the girl is being taken care of by Yèyé Òsun (Òsun priestess) rather than "Bólájí's" mother in the real-life story. As it was in the

real-life story, Wúràọlá does not deliver her two-year old pregnancy until she confesses to Olumide about her life before they got married.

To Táiwò Akinwándé, her neighbour's problem is not peculiar. It is a common occurrence among young men and women who, either by intention or mistake, have children for/by other persons before going into real wedlock. This is why Táiwò produced *Órò Ọmọ Le* as a warning to the inherent dangers that can result from this deceptive behaviour.

5.3.2 Communal Metafiction

Ìbínú Olúkòsò by late Bímpé Adékóíá is an example of metafiction at the communal level. In a discussion with Rẹmí Akínrẹmí (Kánran) after Bímpé's death⁵, he told us that the YHV film is based on the story of a couple who attended the same gospel church with the producer when the latter was alive. The couple had a child who was always convulsing. Many deliverance sessions were held in the church on the little girl, but the convulsion did not cease, until the couple went to seek traditional help. They were told that unless they make sacrifice to Sàngó the god of thunder in a shrine which had long been abandoned in the father's family house, the girl's convulsion would not cease. When the sacrifice was performed, the little girl's convulsion ceased. In the film version, Bímpé does not include prayer sessions in the Church at all. According to Rẹmí, this can tarnish the reputation of the church, as the story was not made an open knowledge to members of the church. In the film, it is Sàngókẹmí's

mother that is a staunch Christian. When "Kémi's" problem starts, the mother refuses to cooperate with the father to take 'Kémi to their village for consultation with Sàngó priests. 'Kémi's father reminds his wife of how happy she was when Sàngó eventually gave her a child after many years of barrenness. Mama 'Kémi (Kémi's mother) refuses to do such a thing. However, when it gets to a stage that Kémi's convulsion is disgracing her all over the town, the mother has to give in. Kémi is then taken to the village where her parents are told that her ('Kémi's) problem will continue if she does not start her duty as a Sàngó priestess earnestly. So Sàngókémi becomes a (part-time) Sàngó priestess. She is thus healed from her convulsive fits.

5.4.0 Men's Films and Women's Films: A Comparison

A proper analysis of a drama text or film will necessitate exploring into its characterization, setting, language, theme and plot, among other things. In this section, we attempt a comparative examination of the areas of analytical probe mentioned above, in YHV films produced by both male and female genders. Our aim is to bring to the fore the fact that films written and produced by females are no less qualitative in terms of literary worth, if compared with those of males, although there are few areas where cultural inhibitions and a 'late entry' into the YHV industry limit women's scope.

5.4.1 Characterization

The mode of characterization employed by virtually all the producers of the YHV films is basically hinged on the Yorùbá worldview about virtues and vices whereby moralization is the objective.

The star-system (Jeyifo 1984:14; Adélékè 1995:27) is a system whereby a particular artiste who is best known for particular role(s), is used as such for a (video) film. As a result of this, there is no significant difference between characterization in films by males and females. For instance, Şolá Şóbòwálé usually plays the role of the vituperous, nagging, temperamental, possessive, jealous and elegant wife of rich and influential husbands, while Saheed Balógun is known for being the trendy, sweet-tongued, scheming casanova boyfriend or husband Yemí Şóladé is known for playing the role of a loving, condoling, gentle, caring and devoted husband or lover. Fóláké Àrèmú, Fúnmiláyò Ògúnşolá, Òjó Arówóşafé and Peter Fátómilólá are more often than not used as diviners, priests and priestesses in YHV films.

As a result of the star system, therefore, both genders (in their guild manner) invite artistes that are most suitable and available (for many of the YHV film artistes are always busy going from one film location to the other) for the various characters to be acted in their films. Usually, there is no discrimination among the artistes about the gender of who invites who to act in a film. Thus, Idówú Phillips, who is popular on the screen as a doting mother, pleasant and caring mother-in-law and reliable female family member, is seen playing the role

of 'Màmá Àjoké' (Àjoké's mother) - Akin's reliable mother-in-law in Dòtun Emmanuel (a male producer)'s *Èniyàn Kó*. She is also 'Fadélera' in Racheal Oniga's *Eléyelé*.

5.4.2 Setting

Things happen all around us in real life. In human inter-relationships, there are actions and reactions going on among different people, for various reasons. Some occurrences happen in proper places while some happen at inappropriate places depending on the norms and values of a given society. It is very rare to come about a drama piece written as text or as a script for film production, wherein all the incidents happen in just one place. This will make the film monotonous and, as such, boring. It means, in essence, therefore, that films shot at different locations, bring about the different scenes in a (video) film.

Film locations can be realistic, abstractive or romantic, and it is possible for these to be depicted in a video film. For a romantic or abstractive setting to be well depicted, the producer relies a lot on the use of properties (props) and complex technical devices. Apart from these, costumes and make-up are also largely made use of. An example of this is the witches' coven in *Kòtò Ayé* and *Eran Íyá Osogbo* written by Ajiléye. These type of Video films are, however, more rare nowadays than before. These days, YHV producers produce more of realistic or authentic and empirically dynamic films.

For realistic films, producers use immediate and far-away locations as their settings. In the course of this study, we find out that both males and females use these locations. For instance, all the scenes in Rótímí Mákindé's *Enikan Ò Layé*, Rasheed Yusuf's *Èrù Àgbà*, Yòmí Ògúnmolá's *Elébòlò* and Şolá Şòbòwálé's *Ayòmídà*, Táíwò Akínwándé's *Òrò Omọ Le* and Ìdòwú Phillips' *Àlà mú Şèniyàn* were shot at different locations in Yorùbá towns.

The vogue now is for Yorùbá video film producers to shoot a substantial part (if not all) of the scenes of their video films off-shore. This boosts their ego as internationally acclaimed and recognized film stars and producers. However, as Baálé (the head of the home), male producers find it easier to leave their spouses and children for months, to produce a 'foreign' film. This is not easy for a woman whose primary assignment is to cook, launder, tidy up and shop for her husband and children at home. Thus, while there are many films shot outside Nigeria like Babátúndé Omídínà's *Baba Londoner*, *Ilérí Ayò* by Şínà Sànyaolú and *Wón Ní Wá Mi Lá mé* by Dèjọ, the only YHV by women with some scenes shot abroad in recent times, is Tóyìn Adégbolá's *Máyòwá*.

5.4.3 Language

More often than not, gynocritical study of language in literary genres aims at "revealing androcentric bias in linguistic practices" (Ruthven 1989:95), as the focus is often on specificity of women's language. However, our aim in this section is not particularly to examine linguistic differences in language used by

each gender, but rather to take a cursory look at speech manners of females as compared to those of the males with particular attention to the use of slangs and open discussion about sexual intercourse.

A few years back, female artistes shied away from taking roles that involve making vulgar remarks. This is due to the Yorùbá etiquette which does not permit speaking openly about things like nudity, sexual organs and coitus (sex). If vulgar remarks are to be made at all, it is tolerable for men, as it may show macho socialibility. It is, however, offensive and unbecoming of a woman to do the same. Things appear to be changing now, for this is a period when women are more daring in their striving to prove their worth and capabilities in rubbing shoulders with the male gender. Such females are those from the younger, more educated, career-minded and elegant group. Thus, if Babátúndé Omídínà in *Obèlòmò* could say:

Máá fi pákò mi sí ẹ ní bàdíí

Wà á dá a mò ...

meaning;

I will thrust my chewing stick (penis) into your rear

You will know the stuff I am made of ...

Opéyemí Ayéòlà does not see it as being out of place or unbecoming for her to say:

Kíí ẹ pé kò fowọ kan mi ...

Ó ti dé Ìgbàrà òkè, titi de Òkehò,

Tó fi de Òndó gan-an ...

in her *Ògèdè Dídun* (Sweet Banana).

Ìgbàrà Òkè, Òkeho and Ondo are towns in Yorùbáland. However, the way the words are used by Ọpéyemi Ayéòla above connotes parts of the body – 'òkè' (upper part), 'Okehò' (tip of the hole) and 'dó' (from Ondo) to mean sexual intercourse. Thus, the above statement as meant by Ọpéyemi is:

It is not the fact that he does not touch me ...
 He cuddles my breasts, has carnal sex with me,
 In fact we have had it even the conventional way ...

Rónké Òjó, too, is fond of using slangs like "Wàá dá a mọ" (You will be surprised), "Etí ẹ á nà" (your ears will tingle), "Gbe é si mi létí" (Give a gist of the matter) and "Sóo da mò?" (Have you tried it before?/Are you interested?). She throws away all caution in *Omoge Campus* when she threatens to go nude before the gateman whom she catches peeping while dressing up. She says;

Hèn-én? Kí lo rí?... só o ri, tí n bá tú kàsàlà ẹ silẹ fún ẹ,
 wò ó ẹrù á bà ẹ, àyà ẹ á já ...

Whaaat? What did you see?... If I bare it (her breasts)
 for you to behold, you will tremble with fear ...

5.4.4 Themes

The basic reason behind producing a film (apart from making profit), is a producer having issues to raise for the society to ponder on about a matter or more. Such issues can be highlighted as a propaganda or a protest (Ezejideaku 2004). The major issue so raised is the theme of such a film. Other issues usually stem from the major theme, these, in literary parlance, are the 'sub-themes'.

A (video) film producer usually attempts to conceal its major theme at the beginning, allowing the viewers to unravel it, as the plot unfolds gradually.

Experiences from life (which may be personal or communal, as implied earlier), social status, political, economic, religious ambitions and inclinations and the use of existing literary works, are some of the factors which influence the theme of a (YHV) producer.

In the course of this study, we realize that the themes of YHV films range from family issues romance, lust after money, power and women, contemporary issues, traditional history of legendary heroes and heroines, and few ones on economics, politics and religion – all based on the Yorùbá world-view.

Both genders have produced video films themed on family issues. Examples of these are *Ilé Olá* (Wealthy Homestead) by Ayò Olúyemí, *Alé Ariwo* (Noisy Night) by Wèmímó Paul, *Omọ Olómọ* (Another man's child) by Táiwò Hassan and *Òrò Omọ Le* (Issues about offspring are delicate) by Táiwò Akinwande, *Gbokogbo* (Husband snatcher) by Tóyòsí Adesanya-Hassan, *Oní*

Ninkan (The Owner) by Opéyemi Ayéola and *Ayòmidá* (Whence my joy?) by Solá Sóbòwálé

Films by men like Yemi Ayébò's *Yemi My lover*, Femi Davies' *Tèmi Ni Nkem* (Nkem is mine) and those by women like Fathia Balogun's *Ifé* (Love), Racheal Oniga's *Eléyelé* (Love like that of pigeons) and *Ìmùlẹ̀ Ifé* (Love Oath) are examples of Yorùbá Video film on romance.

Tundé Kèláńí's *Agogo Èèwò* (The taboo bell), *Ìsẹ́jú Márań-ún* (Five minutes) and *Àbèké Alámàlá* by Fúnmi Martins are examples of YHV themed on the lust for power, women and money respectively by genders in the YHV industry.

While there are many historical and legendary films about Yorùbá heroes and heroines like *Èfúnsetán Aníwúra* by Akinwúnmi Ìsòlà, *Àfòńjá* written by Blódún Ìbitólá for Remdel Productions (owned by Rẹmí Odutòla), *Oníkòyí* by Lẹrẹ Pàimọ and *Basòrun Gáà* (Gaa, the the war chieftain) written and produced by Adébáyọ Fálẹ́tí, *Jógunómí* appears to be the only historical epic produced by a woman – Àńíké Obot. It was bank-rolled by Akintúndé Ayeni of the Yem-Kem tradomedical fame. The reason for women's paucity in this area is due to the fact that this type of films are usually filled with war scenes and chanting of incantations – areas which an average Yorùbá will want to shy away from.

Another area where there is difference in men and women's Yorùbá video film, is that of films with themes adapted from existing texts. While male producers have produced YHV of their own written texts or those of others,

women appear not to have ever ventured into such waters. Some of such males' adapted YHV are *Basòrun Gáà* by Adébáyò Fàlétí Owo *Éjẹ* by Kóla Akínládé and *Efunsetán Aníwúrà* by Akínwùnmi Ìsòla.

We are of the opinion that women's late start with text writing and the fear of/or the refusal of male authors to cooperate with women by giving them permission to produce films on/about their (the males') texts is one of the factors responsible for their lack in the area of text adaptation to film. Apart from this, acquiring western education much later than males, coupled with their late entry into the (video) film industry, are other possible reasons.

5.4.5 Plot

Although there were mimetic and operatic Yorùbá plays before the advent of Yorùbá (video) films, the use of dialogues is virtually employed in all modern day Yorùbá video Films. Artistes' actions are complemented with dialogues in such a way that the story unfolds sequentially. However, the unfolding is not always sequential. Prologues, Epilogues, Flash-backs and the use of Autobiographical Narration are some of the other methods.

Both genders use the above mentioned methods of narration. Straight or sequential plottal device whereby the story unfolds by gradual sequential scenes, is employed by males like Yemí Adénúgà in *Opélopé Asebi*, Sunday Sóyinká in *Ewúro*, Táíwò Hassan in *Òkànsoṣo* and by Muka Ray in *Ọmọ Empire*. Modúpé

Johnson employs this method, too, in her *Ìgbésè*, Bukky Wrights in *Owò Àlè* and Tóyin Adégbolá in *Máyòwá*, did the same.

Another common method of narration among producers of YHV films is the use of flash-back. This is a process whereby scenes from the past which were not shown earlier (at the points at which they sequentially belong), are brought to focus so as to explain or give reasons for present occurrences. Flash-backs may be short or long, but if too long, they render (video) films boring.

We discovered that having longer experiences than women in the YHV industry, men appear to make better use of flash-backs than women. However, women who have been in the industry for long and have learnt on-the-job, appear to us to make better use of this technique than the new comers, especially those who were not institutionally trained for film production.

In *Alé Ariwo* by Wènímó Paul (a three-part movie), for instance, the viewers are kept in suspense as to how Déólá, Emmanuel's wife, is able to retrieve her goods that were confiscated by customs officers at the Ìdí-Ìròkò-Ìgòlò border, until the third part of the YHV is watched. It is also in the third part that one realizes why Déólá descends so low as to allow Àtílà the driver to sleep with her. This is because the third part of the film contains a lot of flash-backs of scenes of Déólá's life style as an undergraduate in the university and her escapades with custom officers.

In *Gbèwúdání* by another male – Síkírù Adésínà, the viewers may not know until towards the end of the film, how Níkèé is able to subdue Jibádé, her

wicked and overbearing husband, to the extent that he (Jibádé) descends so low as an African (Yorùbá) man, who not only does the shopping, cooking and washing for his wife, but also carries their baby on his back. In a flash-back, Nikèé and Mosún her friend, whose husband ill-treats her, too, are shown at a native doctor's house, collecting charms, with which they were able to turn their husbands to fools who are easily controlled.

We are not saying that women do not try their hands on this technique, the point we are making is that men appear to be better at it. For instance, realizing her mistakes in *Seven O'clock* which make the turn over very low, Bukky Wrights employed the use of flash-backs in her *Àgbéké*. *Àgbéké* has a beautiful theme (that of retribution and forgiveness), but the flash-backs therein are marred by inappropriate use of costumes. For instance, Abbey in the film is seen wearing a blue-black outfit in a scene in the office. He is made to wear the same clothes on another day in a flash-back shot in the same place – the office. This brings about dis-orientation in the minds of the viewers. The reason for this is not far to seek: apart from being the star-actress in the film, Bukky Wright is also the costumier. This makes it impossible for her to have the time to select appropriate costumes, as at when due, for members of her cast.

Tóyin Afoláyan – a female producer who has been in the Yorùbá film industry right from its earliest period, surely has a wider experience. Although not institutionally trained, Tóyin has learnt a great deal on the job. In her *Kàyéfi* *Nlá*, she is able to conceal why Simisólá makes love advances to Victor, her cook,

and sleeps with him several times while Adéoyè, her husband, is away. Simisóla also has to sleep with her husband's driver to keep him from leaking her affair with the cook to her husband. The viewers are most likely to pity Simisóla when with flash-backs they are able to realize that it was Victor the cook who made a charm to make Adéoyè like him and increase his salary. Unfortunately, it is Simisóla whom Victor sees first after using the charm, and she falls for him.

Autobiographical narration, which is more used in novels, is a technique also used in drama. It is, however, not usually employed wholly for a film, but used alongside other techniques. With *Ayòmidà* (Whence my joy?), Sólá Sobòwálé, like Liz Benson did with *Yesterday* (an Igbo/English Film), proved that, if well used, the autobiographical method of plotting can be found refreshing as a narrative technique, even if employed throughout. In the YHV, Sólá makes Jùmòké, the star actress of the video film, sit on the floor resting her back on a sofa, with a pillow held to her chest in pensive mood, while narrating her ordeal in the hands of Arówólò – who is not only her father's friend and business associate, but also the father of her son – Ayò. In between the narration, scenes of the incidents are shown while she appears to pause.

Sólá has been in the film industry for close to fifteen years and has worked with experienced hands like Túnjí Oyelana and Richard Mofé Dámijó. Apart from this, she has taken part in English soap operas on television. Some of these are 'Sura the Tailor', 'Mirror in the Sun', 'Jagua Nana's Daughter', 'Super Story', 'The Honourables', 'Family Circle' and 'Everyday People'. All these have

groomed her and influence her productions. During the course of this study, we did not come about a male production which rivals Soḷa Soḅowálé's use of the autobiographical technique.

Altogether, we are able to see that YHV films produced by females are equally of good quality like those of their male counterparts. Both genders, however, still have room for better performance.

5.5 Conclusion

We have highlighted the fact that literary works, unlike other aspects of the arts, are not androgynous, as some scholars would have us believe. Women's filmic works, we have found, are gynocentric. Gynocritically examining these works, we found that they are avenues for women's self-appraisal and for the retrieval of their dignity and self-esteem. They present how these women are viewed and portrayed, their actual places in the society and the representation of how they would like to be related to. All these the women do, with their culture forming the bedrock of their ideology. This is why the background stories which serve as the major themes and sub-themes of films are metafictional in nature. These metafictional stories can be personal or communal in nature. These (Yorùbá) women's films are not only didactic in nature, but they are also questing, self-defining and dialogically suggestive.

NOTES ON CHAPTER FIVE

1 In an interview with him at the premises of Lagos State Broadcasting Station - Eko 89.75FM Station, Ikeja, Lagos on 20 July, 2004.

2 Madam Şaję said this on 20 October, 2002 while advertising *Órò Omó Le* produced by Táiwò Akínwándé on a Lagos Weekend Television (LWT) programme. She said the story is a real-life experience. She said initially that the person concerned was against the production of the film initially, but later gave her consent when the advantages of the film to other people were explained to her.

3 Not the real name.

4 Not the real name.

5 In an interview which we had with Rẹmí Akínrẹmí (Kánran) at the premises of Lagos Television Authority (LTV 8), Ikeja Lagos on 20 October, 2003.

CHAPTER SIX

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

6.0 Introduction

In this Chapter, we attempt to sum up our findings and to delineate what we consider the contribution of the thesis to knowledge in the field of the Yorùbá home video in particular and of the Nigerian home video in general. Our emphasis is on the contribution of women to the development of the home video industry and on future prospects based on a realistic assessment of recent successes.

6.1 Summary of Findings

The Yorùbá video film industry is a relatively new one, employing many Nigerians who would have otherwise joined the teeming number of people roaming the streets or engaging in robbery, prostitution and other vices in order to eke out their livelihood.

We have studied these women in both the creative and the recreative spheres of the industry, finding out that they have shifted from their former position of semi-literate actresses who play mild roles and clichés on stages. They have also shifted from playing just improved ones (roles) in celluloid films (when compared with their stage acts). Furthermore, these women are no

longer mere welfare officers among the production crew; they compete with their colleagues as producers, musicians, make-up and costuming artists.

It has been established in this study that these women are able to forge ahead in the Yorùbá video film industry, because of their improved education and also on account of the acceptance and recognition now accorded female artistes. The poor economic condition of the country which has rendered many school leavers unemployed is basically what has brought about the said recognition and acceptance. This is because female artistes who are working in the industry are definitely not liabilities to their families and the country as a whole. Other implied reasons are improved and sophisticated kitchen gadgets which make women's 'primary' assignments less tasking. Being married to spouses who work in the same or related industries (in some cases), who understand the make-believe world of (video) films, and the commitment it requires, is another reason why women in recent times are able to make vital contributions to the industry. Being married to such men, however, has its own setback for these women, for they may possibly not attain their full potentials in the industry. This is because they may be forced to toe the line of their husbands' wishes and dare not strive to scale greater heights than their husbands in order to keep their homes.

In the creative sector of the YHV industry, it has come to the fore that womenfolk are film musicians and producers. The value of the music rests on its ability to help the viewers adjust psychologically and aesthetically to the flow of

images on the screen, synchronise and complement the action of the performers. Using Tópé Àlàbí's film music as an example, it is confirmed that the women-folks input in the sector has been great. The women document their songs as soon as the inspiration comes, revising them several times before recording them into audio cassettes or discs for onward transfer to the producer who must have requested for their services, before the music is eventually laced into the tracks of concluded feature video films. These songs are aesthetically commentative and thematic. The orchestration used for these songs depends largely on whether the theme of the YHV film is historical or contemporaneous. For the former, traditional ensembles are used while the keyboard suffices for the latter.

The medium of expression for these women's film music is basically the Yorùbá language, although, if need be, they have been found to have the potentials of singing in other languages like English. They also make use of the popular and no less captivating stylistic features of Yorùbá oral poetry like repetition, word-play, parallelism and tonal counterpoints. Tópé Àlàbí, for instance, also uses figurative expressions like similes, metaphors, personifications and hyperboles.

In this study, it has been established that, as producers of YHV, the womenfolk have come a long way. They have produced a sizeable number of YHV films, and like their male counterparts, they have become great employers of labour. They employ production and art directors, camera crew, artists, performers and sound track professionals. It has been revealed in this study

that women find it more difficult to finance their production than their male colleagues. This stems from the bias against them in the capital market. However, these women have remained in business virtually by self-effort. The stipend received from co-starring or taking (lead) roles in films produced by colleagues, gifts and loans from relations and profits made from other business activities, are usually lumped together to produce debuts. Sometimes, an executive producer may finance films for some of these women, royalties received from such arrangements can also be used to produce a self-financed video film.

While there are prolific producers like *Ṣolá Ṣóbòwálé*, *Táiwò Akínwándé*, *Modúpé Johnson* and *Tóyìn Afoláyan*, there are also upcoming artistes and producers like *Ọpéyemí Ayéòla*, *Ayò Adégbité* and *Bukky Wright*. This second set of producers is well-lettered, sophisticated, ambitious and more determined than the earlier set to reach the top and survive; Nigeria's hard times.

Thematically, the contents of YHV produced by these women show them as transmitters and vectors of societal values, they portray them as a formidable force in socio-acculturation. Through their films, they are seen as being self-actualized, for they play roles like chief executives of companies, rich business tycoons and elites like lawyers, doctors and engineers. Their self-actualization is portrayed in YHV films like *Máyòwá*, *Ètó Mi*, *Òwò Àlè* and *Ṣégìlólá*. In this study, we discovered that the contents of these films show that their themes are like placards. While some are appeals against women's oppression and denigration

(like *Ètò Mì* and *Ayé Okúnrin*), few ones do challenge the space given to women in the society. Examples of these are *Jógunómí* and *Ayòmidà*. However, these somewhat vehement protests, on close examination, seem to have at their roots, dialogic suggestions from the women to the men for recognition and corporate existence where one's role complements that of the other.

We have also studied the womenfolk as workers in the re-creative sector of the Yorùbá home video film industry. We found out that they are at the forefront in costuming and make-up, just as they have been in earlier Yorùbá dramatic developmental stages. This is because naturally, a (Yorùbá) woman shows more concern about her facial appearance and clothes worn than the man. As a result of this, more women are employees in these sectors. We have identified everyday type, presentational or symbolic and representational types, as the three basic types of costumes used to clothe artistes in order to make them suitable for the roles they have to play. The women in this sector are largely professionals who have studied in Polytechnics and Universities like Grace Adinku-Hassan, Tóyìn Bífárin and Yémisí Adebówale, while a few have gained a lot of experience from training on the job, such as Láńre Hassan-Adésànyà, and Bísí Ogunde. These women have to carry out market surveys, to determine the cost of costumes to be produced, sewn, hired, bought, mended or laundered before they can bill a producer who has requested for their services. Their job is very much more tasking if they are to costume for an epic or historical film. This will necessitate their having to carry out research which may involve seeking oral

interviews, reading wide, visiting museums and archives and some sort of archeological probing like Tóyin Bifarin did for the costumes she provided for *Jógunómi*.

In this work, the quest into the job of make-up artists shows that their work complements that of the costumiers. They both come together to determine the mood, age, state of being, disposition or social class of a character. The use of make-up goes a step further by the fact that with it, these women are able to counter-act the effect of the distance between the viewers and the artistes. Make-up compensates for the intensity of light effect and it gives mobility to the expressive features of an artiste. In order to bring about facial versatility, straight make-up, character make-up and fantastically styled make-up types have been identified in the study as those used by the women make-up artists in the YHV industry. It has also come to the fore that while the make-up artists make up the faces of most of the artistes, there are few artistes, especially those who use peculiar fantastically-styled make-up such as Babátúndé Omídínà, Monsurat Omídínà, Rasaq Olayiwolá and Olúfúnké Oládèjì who more often than not, make up their faces themselves.

From this study, it is revealed that working within a patriarchal societal set-up, the women in the YHV film industry have been able to prove that their gender is by no means that to play second fiddle, parasites who cannot contribute to the sociological development of the society. On the contrary they have proved that they are able to rub shoulders with their male counterparts in

the industry, though there are few areas where women are yet to prove their worth in the industry. Film directing is one of such areas. It is necessary to say that few women have directed their own films earlier than now, and only very few women have directed other colleagues' films as professionals, as the importance of specialization of the work force has come to be realized. The fact remains, however, that with proper institutional and on-the-job training, women have demonstrated that they could direct films, take care of continuity, shot takings and lighting. This can be achieved if their present pace of contribution is maintained and improved. If women can also come together, directing, recording, providing lights and editing one another's films for a start, the future would be brighter. At this juncture attention may be drawn to the work of the Women's Liberation Cinema in Hollywood. The body produced Kate Millet's *Three Lives* (Laura Mulvey 1979:184).

We have found that the women's physiology and intellect (which have been severely argued against by chauvinists), their financial capability and above all their interest in their chosen careers, will sustain their employment in this industry as long as it continues to exist. This is because the wherewithals needed are of 'soft wares', demanding creativity and being capital intensive.

6.2 Implications of the Findings, and Recommendations

This work has broken new grounds in the study of Yorùbá home video films. It is the first thesis that has looked into the places, roles, contribution and

messages behind the themes of the womenfolk in the Yorùbá home video film industry. It is apt material for further research, not only in the Yorùbá video films milieu, but for Nigerian video films generally. This is because a study of creative and re-creative contribution of women to the industry has merely begun. Other issues related to women in films, like a wholly comparative analysis of their works with those of men and an examination of their remunerations are some of such areas for further research.

Though this study has focused essentially on womenfolk in Yorùbá video film production, it has far reaching implications for the contribution of women generally to social advancement. Through the positions occupied by these women in the Yorùbá video film industry and their contributions thereof, they have proved to be a force to be reckoned with. It will therefore be of great benefit to the society if the traditional view about women being 'a little better than ornamented materials' be changed as far as film production is concerned. This will augur for positive collaboration between individual women and corporate women organizations in film production and the government, non-governmental agencies, banks and other financial institutions, corporate bodies and individual men. These women's contribution would thus more fully complement the efforts of their male counterparts than has been the case hitherto.

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APPENDIX I
ROLL-CALL OF FEMALE YHV FILM PRODUCERS

S/N	NAMES	ALSO KNOWN AS	PRODUCTION
1	Adégbité Ayò	Oyíndà	<i>Ta ni Elerii Mi, Babá Aláànú</i> and <i>Oni Nrikan</i> .
2	Adégbolá, Tóyin	Aṣẹwó Tó Re Mecca	<i>Ojò Idájó, Màyòwá, Ibi Ayé Bá Mi Dé</i> and <i>Olórí Oko</i>
3	Adésànyà, Tóyòsí		<i>Gongo Sọ</i> and <i>Esè Mefà</i>
4	Adésànyà-Hassan, Ayo	Gbòkògbòkò	<i>Eébù Ikà, Gbòkògbòkò</i> and <i>Òtelémúyè.</i>
5	Adékòlá, Bimpe	Ìrètí	<i>Ìmùlè Ifé, Tòmíwá, Ibínú Olúkòso</i> and <i>Ayé Àwa Obinnin</i>
6	Adéyèmi, Àdùké		<i>Òrìṣà</i>
7	Afoláyan, Tóyin	Lolá Ídí Je é	<i>Làbáké, Lady Terror, Eléko Òrun, Asàmámò</i> and <i>Kàyéfi Nlá.</i>
8	Akínwándé, Táiwò	Wùnmí	<i>Ayé Okúnrin, Omọ Okúnrin, Odún Méjo, Nnkan Íní, Òrò Omó Le, Òpá Àjobí</i> and <i>Jáwon Láyà.</i>
9	Akínwùní, Lolá		<i>Bísólá Debe Déèbè</i>
10	Àrèmú, Fóláké	Òrìṣábùnmi	<i>Àtùpà</i>
11	Ayéòla, Opéyemí		<i>Ògèdè Dídùn</i> and <i>Teni N Teni</i>
12	Bákàrè, Láidé		<i>Ewé Ojú Omi</i>
13	Balógun, Fathia		<i>Omọ Ò See Pààrò</i> and <i>Ifé</i>
14	Fúnmi-Martins, Mide		<i>Omọ Okú Òrun</i>
15	Gboyè, Nike		<i>Ìyálója</i>
16	Hassan-Adésinà, Láńre	Ìyá Àwèró	<i>Aàyò Okàn</i> and <i>Àdasi</i>

17	Jaiyeola, Yémisí	Adesqueen	<i>Ojo Ibi, Sègìlòlò, Iyalòde, Bóore Pò, Oyerónké and Ìjà Ifé.</i>
18	Johnson, Modúpé	Fàlì Wèrèpè	<i>Omọ Òkú Òrun, Aláànú Mì, Nnikan Oni Nnikan, Kòsálájobí, Àntí Àdúgbò, Anti Akadá and Orogún Méta.</i>
19	Joseph, Mary		<i>Ọba Àwúre</i>
20	Káfìdìpè, Aisha		<i>Ọgà</i>
21	Lawal, Ayódùn		<i>Itọ Funfun</i>
22	Martins, Funmi		<i>Pèlú Mì, Erù Elèrù, Àbèké Alámàlà and Ètọ Mì.</i>
23	Obot, Bọla		<i>Àniké Ọgò and Jógunómí.</i>
24	Oduwólé, Zainab	Sisí Alágbo	<i>Olómo Ló Maa Rọjá and Agbálẹ Ọjà.</i>
25	Ọgúnmólá, Funke Sóróyè		<i>Èbùn</i>
26	Ọgúnmólá, Péjú		<i>Ìjà Àgbà Méjì and Ahọn</i>
27	Ọjó, Rónké	Oşòdì Òkè	<i>Owó Ni Kókó, Omọ Mummy, City Girls (Sisí Èkó) and Omọge Campus.</i>
28	Olúbò, Bọsè		<i>Omọ Anifowoşé</i>
29	Òlùwà, Serifat, Temitope	Queen	<i>Ètọ Ilú, Işé Ti Yàtò and Rèmìlẹkún</i>
30	Omídínà, Monsurat	Móládùn	<i>Ọbàkan</i>
31	Oniga, Rachael		<i>Aramide, Bibiire and Eléyelé.</i>
32	Oşin, Bimbó		<i>Işé Olúwa and Ọwú Iyá</i>
33	Oşin, Jùmòké		<i>Àşírí Mì</i>
34	Òtúsànyà, Jọké		<i>Orò Mǎ Sòkò</i>

35	Òkò, Iyábò		<i>Ajùmòbí</i>
36	Phillips, Esther Idowu	Ìyá Rainbow	<i>Àsikò Orò, Tinúadé, Ojo, Rábiátù Alágbaja, Àlà mú Sèniyàn, Modúpé Oluwa and Ta Ní Fẹ́ Á Ní</i>
37	Sangókéyè, Bósè		<i>Omólèyè</i>
38	Sóbòwálé, Sólá	Jádesólá	<i>Jókóotadé, Ípinnu, Èwù Àbùkù, Èyí Ga, Aṣẹwó Kano and Ayòmídà</i>
39	Wright, Bukky		<i>Òwò Àlè, Seven O'clock, Àgbéké and Dùgbè Dùgbè Tó Ní Bọ</i>

APPENDIX II

FEMALE COSTUMIERS AND SOME OF THEIR WORKS

	COSTUMIER'S NAME	YORUBA HOME VIDEOS COSTUMED FOR
1	Abel, Elizabeth	<i>Sikirátú Sindódó</i>
2	Abíólá, Macgreola	<i>Ókan Soṣo</i>
3	Adébòwálé, Yémisi	<i>Kòtò Ayé, Lepa Shandy, Elébòlò and Olúweri Mągbóòjò</i>
4	Adégboyè, Rónké	<i>Íyálójá</i>
5	Adésànyà, Tóyòsi	<i>Òrò Omọ Le, Enikan Ò Layé, Ètò Mi Aborè and O Sé Mąámi</i>
6	Adésidà, Mulikat	<i>Olábisi Omọ Lògbàlògbà</i>
7	Adinku-Hassan, Grace	<i>Èjiogbè and Ayò Ni Mo Fé</i>
8	Adió, Basirat	<i>Ike Owó</i>
9	Ainá, Ìdówú	<i>Adúnni Olówò Erú</i>
10	Alàbí, Tópé	<i>Ewúro</i>
11	Alàbí, Tóyin	<i>Igbésè</i>
12	Atándá, Abíólá	<i>Ilé Olórogún</i>
13	Balógun, Yínká	<i>Adé Orí</i>
14	Bífárin, Tóyin	<i>Áfònjá and Jogunoni</i>
15	Coker, Şewà	<i>Ó Yatò and Omijé Ayò</i>
16	Èkétúndé, Salome	<i>Omọ Mummy, Ibi Ayé Bą Mi Dé, Awénibákú and Ohun Afónise</i>
17	Fáladé, Tópé	<i>Ayé Akámará</i>
18	Fiye, Şeyi	<i>Ọba Awúre</i>
19	Hassan-Adésínà, Láńre	<i>Eni Olórun Dá, Èjiogbè, Moróláyò Ajifá, Eni Afé, Èyí Ga, Òkò, Ilú Le, Aşéwó Tó Re Mecca</i>

		and <i>Alàgbà Benjamin</i> .
20	Idris, Dolápò	<i>Obàkan</i>
21	Obasi,	<i>Ògidán</i>
22	Ogunde, Bisi	<i>Alé Ariwo, Oní Nrikan, Bísólá Debedébè, Tèni N Tèni, Ifé, Ayòmida and Àbisínwin</i>
23	Ògúnṣolá, Fúnmiláyò	<i>Èrù Àgbà</i>
24	Ojinji, Rose	<i>Ilè Rìkà</i>
25	Òjó, Dámilólá	<i>Aríkúyerí</i>
26	Olùmègbòn, Wùnmi	<i>Modúpé Olúwa, Ìbinú Èléwòn, Aborè, Àlàmu Sèniyàn and Ọmọ Ọ Se é Pààrò</i>
27	Okunadé, Kòfó	<i>Àdéhùn kan</i>
28	Oláiyá, Mojí	<i>Kòsòrogún and 7 O'clock</i>
29	Sàlāwù, Tóyìn	<i>Alága Kánsù</i>
30	Wright, Bukky	<i>Tèmi Ni Nkem</i>

APPENDIX III

MAKE-UP ARTISTS AND SOME OF THEIR WORKS

	ARTISTS	YORUBA HOME VIDEO FILMS
1	Yémisí Adébowálé	<i>Kòtò Ayé, Obè Lomo, Olúwèrì, Màngbòòjò, Elébòlò, Àtòrundòrun, Sekésekekè, Sùrùtù.</i>
2	Rose Ojinji	<i>7 O'clock, Èyí Ga, Ojò Ìbí, Kàyéfi Nlá, Aşo Àgbà, Àfònjá, Jògunómi</i>
3	Tóyòsí Adésànyà	<i>Àlà mú Şèniyàn, Òrò Omó Le, Ètò Mi, Owónikókó, Ènikan Ò Layé</i>
4	Fúnmi Tijání	<i>Tani Elèrìi Mi, Ìbínú Eléwòn, Àgbà Tó Ròfó Ìkà, Ewé Ojú Omi.</i>
5	Tópé Fáladé	<i>Aborè, Sòkúdaàyè, Òjá Àbíyè, Ire Ákárí.</i>
6	Bukky Òşádàre	<i>Gbélépawó, Why Me/O se je emi, Omọ Empire</i>
7	Grace Adinku-Hassan	<i>Ó le kú, Èjìogbè</i>
8	Ìdòwú Afólábí	<i>Aşo Àgbà, Kòsórogún</i>
9	Wùnmí Olúmègbòn	<i>Ìbínú Olúkòso</i>
10	Kafilat Saleem	<i>Lárinlòdù</i>

- | | | |
|----|--------------------|------------------------------------|
| 11 | Tópé Ògúngbè | <i>Ìgbésè</i> |
| 12 | Abósèdé Adéolá | <i>Ọba Áwùre</i> |
| 13 | Ìdòwú Àiná | <i>Àdúnní Olówò Erú</i> |
| 14 | Tóyìn Elebute | <i>Kó dùn kó pò kó pé (K.K.K.)</i> |
| 15 | Olúbánkẹ̀ Àdió | <i>Iké Owó</i> |
| 16 | Bólá Okùnúgà | <i>Ìhòhò Èdà</i> |
| 17 | Bùnmi Ọlátiléwà | <i>Àsírí Ológbò</i> |
| 18 | Tópé Oyegoke Àlàbí | <i>Ewúro</i> |
| 19 | Kafayat Èlèsòó | <i>Ọlómọ Ló Ma Rọ́já</i> |
| 20 | Dọ́lápò Idris | <i>Obàkan</i> |

APPENDIX IV

INTERVIEWS

A **TÓPÉ ALABI** (Conducted in her residence; 26, Alhaji Tijani Street, Off AIT Road, Alagbado, Lagos, on the 17th of June, 2002)

Self: Good day madam.

Tópé: Good day. Please feel at home.

Self: I am Fadékémi Adágbádá from the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan. I am working on women who work in the Yorúbá home video industry. I will like to know you better.

Tópé: I was born Tèmitópé Obáyomí about thirty-three years ago. I was married to Oyegoke, but I have since remarried; I am now Tópé Àlàbí. I have two kids Ayòmide Oyegoke and Deborah Àlàbí.

Self: Can I know your educational background?

Tópé: Sure. I attended Queen of Apostles Primary School, Oluyoro, Ibadan. Then (sic) I was at Oba Akínyelé Memorial High School, Başòrun, Ibadan. After this, I went to The Polytechnic Ibadan where I studied for the National Diploma in Mass Communication.

Self: How and when did you start singing into films?

Tópé: I was initially an actress, later I was discovered on location when *Agogo Èèwò* was being recorded in 1993. I was requested to sing into the film, that was how it all started.

Self: What gave you the inspiration to start singing?

Tópé: The inspiration comes (sic) from my mother. My mother, Mrs. Kéhindé Ọbáyọmí sings very well. In fact she was the leader of the dance-drama group while studying at the Textile Training Institute, Òkè-Ọwa, Ìjẹbú-Òde about thirty-five years ago. She goes about the house singing while doing household chores. When I am composing for Yorùbá films, I may just remember some of such songs and they will become the nuclei of my own songs. Take *Ewúro*, for example; mother used to sing;

Ewúro ò Ewúro, (2ce)

Ewúro làgbà igi

Igi gbogbo bọwò féwúro

Ewúro làgbà igi

Bitter-leaf, oh Bitter-leaf (2ce)

Bitter-leaf, elder among trees

All trees accord bitter-leaf its due respect

Bitter-leaf; elder among trees.

I re-composed the song, added my own lines and that is what you have in *Ewuro* – produced by Korede Films.

Self: Listening to some of your film music, I discovered that you use a lot of proverbs. Is this trait from your mother, too?

Tópé: No. It is from my father – Mr J. O. Ọbayọmí. He is a very jovial man. He seldom talks without adding one or two proverbs to a sentence. There are many times he gave me instructions using only proverbs. As a result of this, I have come to know many Yorùbá proverbs and words of wisdom and when to use them.

Self: How many Yorùbá home video films have you sung into?

Tópé: You said 'how many?' If I start counting them one by one, you will not finish this interview today. Anyway they cannot be less than a hundred and fifty.

Self: Can you mention just a few of them?

Tópé: *Agogo Íkilò, Ènikan Ò Layé, Ewúro, Aborè, Aşégun, Ilè Ríkà, Ariwo Olá, Iyán Ogùn Qdùn, Qjó Íbí, Oore Pé, Opélopé Aşebi, Why Me, Àlà mú Sèniyàn, Ísèjú Marun, Gbólé pawo, Ojúbá nírè, Àdúnní Olówò Èrú, Modúpé Olúwa, Qmọ Mummy, Olómọ Lo Mára Ròjá, Ayé Áwa Obinrin and Ilé Olórogún.* Those are the ones I can remember for now.

Self: Thank you. You have come a long way. Have you ever tried your hands at other divisions of the Yorùbá home video industry?

Tópé: Yes, I played the role of 'Ìyàwó Àkúdàáyà' in *Rémilékún*, Deji's wife in *Òpómúléro* and I was the nurse that took care of Ajínówó in *Ewúro*. Apart from those, I also handled the costumes and make-up in *Ewúro*.

Self: Do you still do all these?

Tópé: Music is my focus now. I sing into Yorùbá films and I sing Christian songs, too. I have produced a gospel record called "Oore tí ò common". When you hear people calling me "Tópé, oore ti o common", you now know why (*Laughs*). I have stopped acting in secular films. I have given my life to Christ, so I live my life for him. I have produced a Christian film too – *Qwó Agbára*.

Self: How do you negotiate deals with the Yorùbá film producers before you sing for them?

Tópé: They either give me their master-tape to study, or give me the shooting scripts. It is with this that I compose music. I charge about ten thousand naira for a track. After composing the songs, I will go to a record studio

to have it recorded into tapes. It is these tapes that I give to the producers. Some of the recording studios that I have patronized in the past are **Carvas, De Cross** and **Real Music**. To God be the glory, I have my own recording studio now – Rose of Sharon Studios, Alagbado, Lagos.

Self: Are there other women who sing into films like you?

Tópé: Yes, there are. Ámíná Èlèhàà sings, too. She sang into *Lágídígba*. Tópé Lawal is another person, she sang into *K.K.K.* and she sings for advertisement of Yorùbá video films. Rónkẹ̀ Òjó has a beautiful voice too. I have heard her singing many times, but she is yet to start singing into films. You know she is a film star, as a result of which she has to be at locations all the time. She is doing what is best for her.

Self: We have women as producers, musicians, costumiers, make-up artists, continuity specialists and welfare officers in the Yorùbá home video industry. It appears there are no women who can direct films. Why?

Tópé: Women are not doing badly at all in the industry. See, you have counted about six or more divisions of the industry where they are visible; it is just in the aspect of directing that we are lacking. That is a pass mark (laughs). It is not that there are no capable hands, but there are certain things about directing that serve as constraints on their part. Take Lọlá Fàní-Káyòdé, for instance, she directs very well, but it appears as if she is not interested in Yorùbá video films. Another problem is that while an actress can leave location for home after playing her role, a director must be at all the locations of film recording. It is the director who calls shots, and he can be away from home for weeks or months. Do you think a man will take kindly to his wife being absent from home for weeks or months? There lies the problem. Another reason is that Yorùbá men, like most other African men, do not like taking instructions from a woman. If

a woman directs a (Yorùbá Video) film, she will definitely give orders. Having been on locations several times, I believe I can direct a film successfully.

Self: You think your husband will take kindly to that?

Tópé: My husband is liberal. He is also in the show-biz. We met at a recording studio, so he knows about all these things.

Self: In all, will you say singing into films is rewarding?

Tópé: Well, I find financial responsibility towards my home and extended family relatively easy; glory be to God.

Self: Madam, it has been a great pleasure talking with you. I appreciate your co-operation. Thank you.

Tópé: You are welcome.

B GRACE ADINKU-HASSAN (Conducted in her office at the Theatre Arts Department, University of Ibadan on March 21, 2002)

Self: Good morning madam. I am Fadekemi Adagbada, a research student from the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.

Grace: Good morning, Mrs. Adagbada. Make yourself comfortable.

Self: Please I will like to know you better

Grace: I am Grace Adinku-Hassan. I am thirty-four years old. I am from Delta State and I am married to a Yorùbá man. We have two kids. I am a lecturer in the Theatre Arts Department, Faculty of Arts, University of Ibadan and I teach costuming and the art of making-up.

Self: Can I know your educational background?

Grace: Yes. After Secondary School, I did a certificate course in Dramatic Arts at Obafemi Awolowo University. That was between 1987 and 1988. I studied for a Diploma in Theatre Arts in 1989. I graduated with a bachelor's degree in Theatre Arts from University of Ibadan in 1995. I did the master, too, at Ibadan, in 1999.

Self: You appear to have a great interest in Theatre Arts, why?

Grace: Yes, it has been theatre all my life. I became interested while at Ifẹ. Obafemi Awólówò University has a professional performing theatre: it is a kind of laboratory for us students. It was there that I became interested in costuming and make-up. There was a man whom we called "Baba Textile" in our Department; he made àdirẹ (tie and dye)

and sewed. Dr. Kémi Ilórí was the lecturer handling costume and make-up then. They both aroused my interest.

Self: What was your experience at the University of Ibadan as a student?

Grace: There, I met late Ms. Iquo Offiong. She was in charge of Wardrobe. She trained as a seamstress before joining the University of Ibadan, so she trained as a costumier on the job. Late Ms. Iquo Offiong really put me through, concerning cutting and sewing cloths. At the University of Ibadan, there is no performing professional theatre; the students do all. This I have found very challenging.

Self: In all, in how many Yorùbá home video films have you handled the costume and make-up?

Grace: I assisted Mrs. Hassan (Ìyá Àwèró) with the costumes for *Oduduwa*, but I solely took charge of the make up like I did for *Ejiogbe*, *Ayò Ni Mo Fé* and *Ó Le Kú*.

Self: How do you go about doing these jobs?

Grace: There are a lot of technicalities involved. One must read, understand and get familiar with the shooting scripts. The roles, ages, mood and gaits of all the characters and the period of the incidents in the film, have to be well understood. I will carry out researches, if need be, and then make sketch designs of the costumes or make-up to be used. I will take these to the producers and directors of the films. We have to reach an agreement on what to use and the financial implications. After the financial negotiations, I will now settle down for the job.

Self: How do you get materials for the jobs?

Grace: I either buy, borrow or improvise. Things are easier if the (video) film to be shot is based on contemporary issues – here one can get almost all the things needed in the market. In a case where the film is themed on events of past years like *Ó Le Kú* or epic films like *Odùdùwà*, *Sàngó* or *Àfònjá*, one needs to borrow, hire or improvise the costumes. With make-up, there is no problem. Items for making up in Yorùbá movies are not so much complicated. We use the normal things like powder, dyes, food colours, creams, ointment and the like. In Nigeria generally, prosthetic pieces (like false nose, buttocks, arms, masks and the likes) are not so popular, but we use wigs, weave-ons, false beards or false dread-locks.

Self: Don't you test these things on the artistes before the real day of shooting?

Grace: Yes, we do. There is a day called 'Dress and Tech day'. This is the day set aside while preparing for locations; to test the light designs, props, set, costumes and make-ups. We do this to know if amendments need to be made. However, in shooting Yorùbá home videos, things are easier. This is because the artistes in most cases bring along their own costumes (in a guild manner) as a kind of assistance for the producer; to cut down on cost. I will ask them to bring two or three costumes, (in relation to their roles), then I will select the one that is best for their roles. In a case where they do not have suitable costumes (in relation to their roles) the producer has no choice other than to tell us to provide one.

Self: What is your impression about the arts of costuming and make up in the Yorùbá home movie industry.

Grace: We still have a long way to go. A large percentage of the people at present handling these arts are not trained. You cannot compare a

costumier or make up artist who went to the university for a degree or diploma, with somebody who did not. The difference will be clear. You can imagine – a woman in the role of a house-wife or whatever, sitting down on a chair in her bedroom, wearing a night gown, with high-heeled slippers on, necklace, ear rings, wrist watch and make up on. ... this is not realistic. Or, take, for instance, a poor palm wine tapper going about his business in shirt and jeans – in a Yorùbá setting! That is how bad it is. I know that, with time, things will straighten out themselves – all these quacks will find jobs in other sectors of the film industry and leave the professionals to handle things.

Self: Who are the other professionals in these fields?

Grace: Toyin Bifarin at the Theatre Arts Department of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife is one. She is great. You go and watch *Àfònjá* and *Jógunómí*, the costumes used go well with the period of the incidents. Tóyìn has been able to re-present how life was during Afonja's time in Ilorin, with costumes.

Self: Did Tóyìn handle the make-up too?

Grace: No, Rose did that. Rose Ojinji. Those are professionals. Don't you see how Rose gave Peter Fatomilola those tribal marks? These girls are doing marvellous jobs. We are quite different from the 'quacks'. Yémisí Adébòwálé is another good make-up artist. She works for Gbénga Adéwùsì – **Bayowa Films and Records Company**, Lagos. She has a diploma.

Self: How financially rewarding are these jobs?

Grace: Waow! Money?

Self: Yes

Grace: We are not doing badly, but I can not give figures.

Self: Thank you very much. I will still want to meet you again...at locations.

Grace: Oh! Sure, why not? You are always welcome.

SET

Enikan Olaye...

1 Ada ori o tafimmesa

2 Uleke oran nfin mo jayi o

3 Ema fori ade polo o...

gereji. Sou lami bagba

1 Eru pese pese o laafi

otoleto o niyeu o

alasa etaji erisa

eru pese ni tigin o

2. Lau bari oba ni...

edo sifun firi o...

jiwa erisa to...

lori oba ni...

3 Iru ku so ni...

ta o in ba...

fira sikun bi...

oke nni ni...

1. Rastari am...

2. Ajele...

3. Pasa...

1. Ma...

2. Mase...

3. Pate...

1. Omo...

2. Kase...

3. Kosi...

1. Pasa...

2. Eru...

3. Eru...

1. Eru...

2. Eru...

3. Eru...

1. Eru...

2. Eru...

3. Eru...

1. Eru...

2. Eru...

3. Eru...

English traditional

Apakala ze Kehatanbi ligwa foko sanle
oko yoke - pholu ze Kehatan bi
omo foko ole ya loke
alahato ti hoo bo elegbo nio qepto
rel

Qua to Se Sawo ti Se Sisi

o baya la's sise
Oro yi Se Sisi lewa obayo si
ho asa pata lya ase to danu
Qradh kogi r amunna
Sariji tati rapa qabo taran

Sejaka ri
Oro Ki Sisi ti Si Sisi Supan
Ami ni kuru/apa

~~g...~~
~~...~~
~~...~~

Apakala Ze Kehatan bi
ligwa foko sanle oko yoke
Apakala Ze Kehatan bi

Captain (Dikimorasi)

3 * 2 Bata Sasi Obe - lya
batimi Seyisi - qoko 2 lomo
batimi: Sasi nnu Kasiu
ebere - lya obagim lomo

ura
to qo
Ere awokpoko ofede o
qke lankin de
Chow
ni civa tala keweran qye qye ho
Abere lomo de o Eri ka oba
Samp panikan oba
abas qe panikan oba

akura to lomo Sasi niteri qan
ni Eadi jagan o Sasi niteri
lomo ni bewandere lomo
Sasi ebi yin ni

2 * 2 qepto eritio lomo kapa Sisi fun
bi abe Sasi fun owo ase lomo
fun o, amigun a gargata
ho Sisi bi war Sisi Se
wani kogi tomiamu
elaps owo abe nibale qye taran

baye baye oroda so
efeti silu aboro m.
Eni tani olayis oiba
baba dara furi or. Sox qoc
Ipo nla amunig gaga
batiba so. Aniwag sinwahu
Ipetipo to le wa
Kamas. Sowa hu
ami tarani tojunile
awon yemama boro furi
ni idi eyi eri amaguu

②

Agulo opul si g. karo
eda e so e pepe mawasa
Katagi mitu lo songing memohi
Iri. olajin hia nitawitigi. lre
Ki sebi taye de doro ee
Clarus Ewora se
bi eba lous koro keni ssozaku
Kori luu mi maba tode miya

① Bi e ba lous e gao ee se jek
~~ama hawis kama mas mumi~~
toni olajin luu maw nitawisi

①

~~Amo~~ Araye emopere soro
unqbaye. wani m-huwo hibi e nipe
won laye ni koro
ero koro tomba ni qamba lode
aye

②

Amo daw eri. kofunio lo
Kii Se taye ori
esoro koro feni dila emu soro dase
oflor kori vnu yomawo lode miya

Elere eme - Mafali em o...
 ems peri mi ni...
 kinmasse bason...
 ti o momi kinto mo o...
 oah elere eme...
 Onemo kemo ni kemserimo...
 Kiya fofota...
 Emis ofu emo emigun...
 mafimide; akoyin si elere eme...
 apola igi ni...
 Emi ofe mi apun...
 mi apunko ni si tadpen...
 tigi o moduro...
 elase mama...
 emase kurson emagun...
~~leisi~~ ~~ap~~ ~~urson~~ ~~osa~~ ~~sa~~
 Eniya sevon afmudariz...
 Oya palaba ya...
 bibe sa ~~sa~~ fason...
 teq...
 etiri palaba ya...
 qbere emon...

Kelim...
 Orisa to...
 emu offer...
 emi ti...
 emi to...
 beran ti...
 Soemo...
 emu...
 kelanu...
 emu...
 emu...
 emu...
 emu...
 emu...

fere o otutu
 mafi kani mi eli dadi mi
 fere lya kebere lya alalaba
 mi o fe kankanda oyo oke
 Suga nanyi Suga o rora si
 1 kokunru mi a dogbe koda
 kokunru mi a laga sade
 ku Sewan re
 2. lya ndogbe koya Olurin
 biya kati de ke ya pavi
 ema Soma - laka kina Soma o se wo
 alafiki lona nda tobi awotitaw
 troya re egiro

Rru tibi dacele
 lirinon amasa jagun agaji
 tona ka daraju niaw ama
 Kr: amia qbare kado obi
 gogbo rayen ta tind - Obinri bi
 lomo lagu Obi non
 Suga = ama gido sugu tibi o
 Kereba Kale fekun paje
 Komos lu mare - Ebami ki alamu o - Oseanjan
 Ras Alamu o Oseanjan
 kend Amo ire banini Sadura dmo
 Oseanjan amo obama paje re
 lya lya - lya lya lya
 Ri - lami - lya - Oseanjan
 lya lya lya gogbo lya amadu
 gogbo amo nafa kemo pe lya
 Fi aban Suga se jagun asura fura
 eni lya lya lya lya lya lya
 Obi o - ase amol per u ta dana le u
 lu wai mada ase amol per u ta
 lya lya - Suga lya lya lya lya
 alamo Obi

MAKE VP'S COPY

(A) OPEYEMI AYEOLA PRODUCTIONS

PRESENTS

A HOME VIDEO MOVIE

TITLE

KU SE ERU E

(IT'S NOT YOUR PROPERTY)

STORY

OPEYEMI AYEOLA

SCREENPLAY

ABIOLA HUGHES

DIRECTOR

ABIODUN OLANREWaju

© 2004

375/12
187/13

47-238
127-500
121-500
121-500
121-500
Nike Pelle
150

4500

500.0
2800
2500
3200

ANNA DIPS

SYNOPSIS

CHIEF OLAWUNMI, a disciplinarian, and his wife, BISI, are blessed with children but FOLAKE is their only female child. During FOLAKE'S first year in the university, she is having a love affair with KUNLE.

In the course of this love affair, FOLAKE becomes pregnant. And knowing fully well that if her father should hear of it, heavens will fall, FOLAKE goes to have an abortion from a bricklayer.

And the result, she'll never be able to conceive and bear a child. What a pity. Many years later, FOLAKE'S parents are no more and the result of the abortion continues to hunt her despite that fact that she is now a very rich and successful woman.

She gets married to SEGUN, but after six years of bareness they go their separate ways.

Next it's GBADEBO. After seven years, he also couldn't stand it any longer. And so, the marriage hit the rocks.

Now, FOLAKE meets BAYO who is ten years younger than her and decides to win her love. At least, for her, to have a companion. When it becomes increasingly clear to FOLAKE that for her to gain the attention of BAYO; YEMISI who is BAYO'S fiancée has to go out of the way.

Through metaphysical means, FOLAKE realizes her aim, but for a short while. Because she'll have to live with the blunder she committed till the end of her life.

This is electrifying.

CAMERA ESTABLISHES A BEAUTIFUL BUILDING.

CUT.

PROLOGUE

GBADEBO'S HOUSE (INT) LIVINGROOM (DAY)

CHARACTER GBADEBO AND FOLAKE

A richly furnished and expansive livingroom.

Camera takes a gradual pan to reveal a beautiful dining table set for meal and GBADEBO on the sofa reading a news magazine. Moments afterwards, his wife; FOLAKE comes on from the kitchen.

FOLAKE My dear, ki lo de ti o jeun?

GBADEBO IS MUTE. HE CONCENTRATE ON THE NEWS MAGAZINE.

FOLAKE Iwo ni mo ma nba wi.

GBADEBO TAKES A DERISIVE LOOK AT FOLAKE AND HISSES AT HER.

GBADEBO Iwo nbeere wipe se emi o jeun ni?

FOLAKE Bee ni.

GBADEBO Se iwo kii romu ni?

FOLAKE *(Surprised)* Se emi ki romu ni?

GBADEBO Bee ni mo so.

FOLAKE Ki lo fa iru oro yi sini?

GBADEBO *(Stands)* Ti o ba fe mo, ma' so fun e. Lati bi odun meje, emi ati e ti se igbeyawo ni a ti jo ngbe inu ile yi. Se iyen ko to ironu fun e? Nkan to je o logun ni ki o lo si ibi ise ki o de ni ale. Oro ise re ka e lara ju ki o bi omo lo. Sugbon temi ko ri bee o. Ti o ba wa ku tan, ta lo ma jogun gbogho nkan ti o nko ja yi? Ni temi o, emi ko wa ile aye wa se lasan. Nitori na, mo fun e ni odun yi ki o li tun ero ara re pa. Bi beeko, onikaluku wa yi o lo ni ona tire ni o. Nko ni nkankan lati so fun e-ju iyen lo.

GBADEBO LEAVES FOR THE BEDROOM. FOLAKE TAKES A SEAT ON THE SOFA AND BURST INTO TEARS.

FADE.

OPENING CAPTION ROLLS

AFTER OPENING CAPTION, CAMERA ESTABLISHES A UNIVERSITY CAMPUS.

CUT.

SCENE ONE

HOSTEL (INT) DAY

CHARACTER YEMISI, SOLA AND YETUNDE

A realism setting.

Shot opens with YEMISI in bed. She is critically ill. She is underneath the sheets shivering with cold. Moments afterwards, her roommate, SOLA and another colleague, YETUNDE come on the scene.

- SOLA YETUNDE, abi o ri bayi. Nse ni aisan na ma nburu si lara YEMISI.
- YETUNDE Lati bi ose kan abo nisinyi. Oro na ma su emi o. Gbogbo ogun ti won fun ni clinic nko?
- SOLA Gbogbo ogun na lo ti fe lo tan sugbon ko san.
- YETUNDE Kimi o wa to wipe a le se bayi?
- SOLA Ko ye emi na ni mo se pe e.
- YETUNDE Se ki a ranse si aunty re nile?
- SOLA Emi na ti so be, sugbon o ni asiko yi kii se igba ti ohun tun ma yo aunty na lenu fun owo rara.
- YETUNDE *(Surprise)* Ah! Kimi a ma wa se si? O je yara ki a gbe lo si ile iwosan ki a si lo so fun aunty re nile.
- SOLA Emi na fara mo nkan ti o so yen.

SOLA AND YETUNDE MAKES TO TAKE YEMISI TO THE HOSPITAL.

CUT.

CAMERA ESTABLISHES A HOSPITAL BUILDING.

CUT.

SCENE TWO

JOY HOSPITAL (INT) WARD (DAY)

CHARACTER FOLAKE AND BIDEMI

BIDEMI is here to pay her elder sister, FOLAKE, a visit. FOLAKE has been here on admission for almost two weeks. She is being treated for typhoid fever.

BIDEMI How are you now?

FOLAKE I am very much better. I am thankful to God.

BIDEMI When will you be discharged?

FOLAKE I don't know yet. The doctor is to decide. But from my discussion with the doctor yesterday, I may have to be here for another two weeks.

BIDEMI *(Surprised)* Another two weeks?

FOLAKE That's what he said.

BIDEMI Anyway, the time you are discharged is not what matters. What matters is, you are in a good state of health by the time you leave here.

FOLAKE Of course.

CUT.

SCENE THREEJOY HOSPITAL (INT) RECEPTION (DAY)

CHARACTER DOCTOR, YEMISI, SOLA, YETUNDE,
NURSES (2), FOLAKE, BIDEMI AND EXTRAS

YEMISI sits on a bench at the hospital reception. And sitting on her both sides are SOLA and YETUNDE. A nurse is also with them. Moments afterwards, a doctor, and a nurse come on.

DOCTOR Is this the lady?

NURSE Yes.

DOCTOR Let her pay a deposit of ten thousand naira (N10,000.00) and place her on admission.

SOLA Excuse me sir, we are here with just three thousand naira (N3,000.00). Please, assist us.

DOCTOR Lady, I am very sorry. There is nothing I can do to assist you. That's the procedure here.

AT THIS POINT, FOLAKE AND BIDEMI COME ON THE SCENE. FOLAKE SEE BIDEMI OFF AFTER A VISIT. THEY WALK THROUGH.

YETUNDE Please doctor, get her admitted. We promise to pay the remaining amount before she is eventually discharged.

DOCTOR And if you don't pay, what happens?

SOLA That won't happen by the grace of God.

DOCTOR God has nothing to do with this. I just want you to understand my position. I don't own this place and that's the procedure laid down by the hospital's management.

NOW, FOLAKE RETURNS. SHE SIGHT YEMISI ON THE BENCH AND OVERHEAD THE DISCUSSION BETWEEN THE DOCTOR, SOLA AND YETUNDE. FOLAKE TELLS THE DOCTOR TO ATTEND TO YEMISI IMMEDIATELY WHILE ONE OF THE NURSES AROUND COME TO HER UPSTAIRS FOR THE TEN THOUSAND NAIRA. SOLA AND

LITTLE QUEEN
Productions

Presents

A NEW YORUBA FILM

Starring

AREMILEXUN

Written & Produced By:

Queen Oluwa

Directed By:

Rasheed Yusuff

Script Developed By

Adebayo Tijani

Queen Oluwa

Olusola Olujimi

Kunle Makinde

Olawole Cole

Scored By

Adebayo Tijani

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SCENE 1

IYA AJIKE'S HOUSE

EXT/DAY

Camera open from an establishment shot of a city, revolves round to pick some houses. Lastly rest on Iya Ajike's building to reveal the happening there. Where little Ajike is troubling them with heavy cry. Old Mama and their relatives try to pet her but she refuse.

- LARA : (she is singing for Ajike) Ajike o, ko roko, Ajike o, ko rodo, bo baji, agbobe rana, ajebe tan, a sekun rondo, omo oloro ti i jeyin awo. He e: tin j'eyin awo, omo oloro ti i jeyin awo.
- OLD MAMA : (she try to give Ajike cold pop but she refuse) Wo o! Ma f'oko mi sala, ijokan l'eyan nko. Ti Asabi bati de, ko ma gbe omo re lo, ha lataro.
- LARA : O to, omo oloju lami boro, elekeke ghengbe, mo f'ekun re jami layaa. Ki lo tun fe kin se, o mo gbe o, mo re o. E ni la gbe mo pin (Iya Ajike returns in from the office)
- ASABI — *Saye* : E ku le o, oko mi tin ke. Ki le se fun (rush to her baby)
- OLD MAMA : Iya bo ti nsin lomo njalo, oun ti o da wa po ko ni da kowa tu wa ka a. Ti o ba ti n lo ibise ma gbomo e. Igbadun kan enikan oni ninu ile yi, loni lati igba to ti gbe wahala e de (Ajike still crying). Bo se nke bi aje ni yen
- LARA : O to, omo oloju lami boro, elekeke gbenbe, mo f'ekun re jami layaa. Ki lo tun fe se fun o mo gbe o, mo re

CAM DISSOLVES

CAST : Ajike, Lara, Old Mama & Asabi

PROPS : Cold Pop

SCENE 2

YAKOYO FOOD CANTEEN

EXT/DAY

Camera reveals Yakoyo Food Canteen, where series of activities is taking place, but Ajike is using her crying to disturb her mother.

- CUSTOMER : (calling) Yakoyo
- YAKOYO : Ki le fe
- CUSTOMER : E so fun Iya aburo yi kan da omo won loun, ariwo yen po

- YAKOYO : E se o. (calls) Asabi 278
- ASABI : Ma a
- YAKOYO : Ewo ni iwa Asabi ti npomo rele iwe ti iwona nwu bayi. Se ni gbogbo ile yin ko si eni ti o le f'omo so, lon fi se asiru e bo wa ibise. Nigba ti se o ka e l'ara
- ASABI : Beeko, ko gba na ni, na fi ni kin gbe wa. Owo ana ni kan ti mo gbe kaale o fe yo ile aye lemi won nile. Ni Iya Agba fi ni kin maa gbe le mo.
- YAKOYO : Wa a wa maa lo to ju e nile, ma so mi di okuroro. Nigba tawon customers ba nri o t'omo nke leyin e, to tun nsise pelu e, ki lo fe ki won maa so. Ile ya
- ASABI : E jo o Ma
- YAKOYO : Ma be mi o, ori e o ni be e lebe 'ya a

(Asabi exit) A len le

CAM FADE

- CAST : • Yakoyo, Asabi, Ajike & Others
- PROPS : • Canteen Utensils

CAPTION ROLLS

SCENE 3

AJIKE'S SHOP

EXT/DAY

Camera establishes big shop which belong to Ajike. Sade, one of Ajike sales girls is calculating market for her.

- SADE - *Toni* : Gbogbo owo oja naa je N150,000.00?
- AJIKE - *Redeal* : Mo riyen, owo toni Iya Mela isale Eko kowa nko N200,000.00?
- SADE : Inu drawer ni mo koyen si
- AJIKE : De lo kowa a, ka kapoo

(Sade stand up to open the drawer but the money was not there)

- SADE : Mi o ma ba owo nbe e
- AJIKE : O ba N200,000 nbe, to nsoro bi eni f'Olorun ti gba fun. Se edi oma di e saa?
- SADE : *(she face Mosun her colleague)* Mosun, se o bami r'owo nibi bayi?
- AJIKE : Semi ti mo lo ibi ti Mummy ran mi lataro o to je wipe mo nse se bo ni.
- SADE : He e *(laugh)* loro kan, N200,000.00 ti ra mo yin lowo. Sade, dami loun, omo toni kawon omo mi maa jere mi, oun ni o ni jere omo. Omo toba ni wahala loun fe kin ma se, gbogbo ere mi loun ma ma danu, oun naa oni jere. *(to Sade)* Lo pe 'ya e wa, e maa r'owo eleyi san ni *(Sade exit)*

CAM DISSOLVES

- CAST : Ajike, Sade & Mosun
- PROPS : Money

SCENE 4

AJIKE'S SHOP

EXT/DAY

Camera shows Sade and her mother (Iya Ijebu) are already with Ajike in the shop.

- IYA IJEBU *Ijebu* : O ni Inu drawer naa loun k'owo si. E e, bawo wa lowo se rin?
- AJIKE : Ewo Iya, kin se ikinni, kin se ekeji, koda, eleyi o kin se eketa. Awon olori buruku, omo o si, ti won o ni jere, tan so pe emi o ni jere laiye, to je pe wahala lo maa ba ku laye won. Ko s'oro o Mama, won maa pin owo naa san ni
- (Folake - Ajike's first daughter emerge)*
- FOLAKE *Maji* : E ka san o Mummy, kilo sele?
- AJIKE : Awon cfo emi yi maa ti ko mi lowo ni. N200,000.00 lo ko lo te yi
- FOLAKE : Ha a! Mummy, won k'owo yin, emi ni mo ya, oun naa ni mo ni kin wa salaye fun yin
- AJIKE : Nibo ni gbogbo won wa nigbato wa ko?

FOLAKE

Sade nikan ni mo ba, mo de ran nse bi mo se de, loun ba lo titi ni ko ba tete de o, bi mo se ti shop pa niyen ti mo lo ni temi o

AJIKE

(face her staff) E wo, Olorun yo yin ti mo ri. Iya, eku oro omo, Olorun a je ke jere won. Eku irin, e maa lo ile, o ti ni iyanju

IYA IJEBU

Ha! A se omo mi o k'owo lo paro mo. Wo, e sese bere ni. Leyin epe kabiti kabiti te ti gbe awon omo se tan, akoko f'ewure ba b'uju wehin, a f'epe f'elepe. Bi won o se ni jere omo, bi wahala se maa je ti won lori owo ti won o gbe, abi? Enu e lo wa yen. Maa fi ye e pe ogbologbo omo Ijebu ni mi.

CAM FADE

CAST

Ajike, Folake, Mosun, Sade & Iya Ijebu

SCENE 5

RIVER SIDE

EXT/DAY

Camera establish both Folake & her sister -Mopelola, sitting at the bank of the river, opposite each other with their baskets in their front. Their mother Ajike, fetching water with a bucket from the river into their baskets.

CAM DISSOLVES

CAST

Ajike, Mopelola & Folake

Queen

PROPS

Two Baskets & A Bucket

SCENE 6

AJIKE'S BEDROOM

INT/NIGHT

Camera pullout from Ajike's face, lying on her bed, to accomodate her sleeping. Suddenly, she woke up from her night-mare, pick her Bible and start praying.

AJIKE

Oluwa ni Oluso Aguntan mi . . . (camera zoom to her face)

CAM DISSOLVES

CAST

Ajike

PROPS

Bible

SCENE 7

CHURCH

INT/DAY

Camera pullout from Ajike's face to accomodate her on her kneel, praying with her Pastor standing beside her, praying along with her.

- PASTOR : (after prayer) E ke Halleluya
- AJIKE : Halleluya
- PASTOR : E yin Oluwa logo
- AJIKE : Ogo
- PASTOR : Bi a se ngbadura lo, a fi han mi ninu iran pe, e ti fi ipase iwa ijangbon ati agidi f'ori gba epe ni ibi kan, ni eyi ti o si l'ewu pupo. Sugbon ti o ba kun fun adura daradara, ti o si gba awe, o l'ewu lehin wa ola.
- AJIKE : (with mix feeling) Ha a! A se looto ni nkan t'lya n so pe maa ri. Oro kekere lasan ni mo pe e.
- PASTOR : Ko si nkan to kekere ninu epe o, k'Olorun maa fi ja wa ni, k'Oluwa ko wa yo ninu e, k'Olorun de wa pelu wa.
- AJIKE : Amin o

CAM FADE

CAST : Ajike & Pastor
 PROSP : Bible

ABA OBE

SCENE 8

IYA TUNJI'S PARLOUR

INT/DAY

Camera open on both Tunji (Folake's husband) and his mother in deep discussion.

IYA TUNJI

Iya awero:

Won ni ta ba fe j'egun, ka toju ojulowo ata, a si toju ojulowo ata. Won ni t'eyan ba fe j'akalamagbo, ko toju opolopo e, e gbiyanju a wa opo iyo. Won ni ka di'ju otun, a di to'tun, won ni ka ta wara ka ka'ese asi kan ro, a se be. Adigun, b'eye buruku o ba dun je, e je k'omo eiye o pada s'iju. Wo, wahala Orifolake yi po o, oun nikan ko lobirin, ko l'oyun ataro d'ale ri. Ogun idile wa lori e, fe 'yawo imi o

TUNJI

Tomi fash:

Iba s'emi, iba s'awon ni o ni je a na iyawo eni. Oun to sele yi, ko s'eni

ti o le sele si. Ko sa le wun Folake naa, ko loun o ni b'omo laisye. Sebi k'iyawo gb'omo jo lere ile oko, paapa, ta lo m'eni ti nkan se ninu awa mejeji?

IYA TUNJI

: Gb'enu e lo, o ti f'ogun mu e. Emi mo pe Folake ns'ogun, (*she mimick him*) eni ti nkan se ninu awa mejeji. Se iwo o m'oriki ile yin ni, imodun elerin mo sa, abato omo yeriyeri lona erin. Eni imodun ba ba sun ti o l'oyun, omo lo tan lara oluwa re. Nkankan o s'awon Baba e ri d'ibe, oun lo l'ogun lara.

CAM CUT

CAST

: Iya Tunji & Tunji

SCENE 9

IYA TUNJI'S HOUSE

EXT/DAY

Camera reveals Tunji's car, park in front of their house. Folake and one of Tunji's uncle are discussing beside the car.

UNCLE OKO

: Isebo ns'ogun la fin b'omo laye, igbagbo la fin wo. E gbiyanju ke jade, Olorun Oba o ko aajo o. Sebi oun lo da ewe at'egbo si igbo. Eda to ba ko aajo, kini o ni ka maa fi se, sebi itoju ara wa naa lo-wa fun. Akojopo igbala at'isese la fi nraiye gbe, se o gbo?

FOLAKE

: Mo gbo Baba

UNCLE OKO

: Ko to di 'pe e lo, tun ba Oko re naa soro

(*one of Iya Tunji's goat and her kins, try to eat Folake's lugages*)

FOLAKE

: Ka i, Ewure buruku wo ni yi

IYA TUNJI

: (*interrupt from the entrance of the house*) Ewure t'emi o kin s'Ewure bunuku o, se bi o r'omo leyin e, mi o kuku ba o wi, eni ti o ni iru eni, ko le mo iyi eni.

FOLAKE

: Ha a Mama! Se nitori mo l'Ewure lasan

UNCLE OKO

: Iya Tunji, oro eyi un o da, oro yi ab'oro imi. Akini nje akini, afini han nje afini han, ewo ni ara lbadan ton lo lojude Ogunmola, Oro un opo

IYA TUNJI

: Un mo pe o da lyawo, maa binu, Olorun yio w'ola Ewure mi, yio s'omo tie fun e

CAM FADE

CAST : Folake, Uncle Oko & Iya Tunji

PROPS : Lugage, Car, She Goat & Kins

SCENE 10

AJIKE'S SITTING ROOM

INT/DAY

Camera establish the exterior surface of Ajike's house, and later dissolves into her sitting room to reveal Mopelola, resting on her mother's lap on the chair. She seems not okay, while Folake sits beside her mother, narrating her encounter with her mother-in-law.

AJIKE : Ki wa l'oko so si?

FOLAKE : Nibi Feyan o si, Olorun wa nbe. Ko fi bun won, koda ibinu e ni o je ko fun won ni kobo tafi kuro nibe.

AJIKE : Olorun olojo oni, a le wi le se, Oba awimayewun, ki wa lese mi, kini mo se, ti mo wa b'omo meji pere, to wa nfi won bami ninu je? Mopelola ni yi ni ile, foni ku fola dide ni, Folake eghon re tun ni yi o, ko l'oyun ataro d'ale ri ni ile oko. Oro ta maa n pe lowe maa ti fe maa laro ninu, iro ni, oto ni, bi ere bi ere, igimu elede maa tin wo ogba lo. Tani mo se (she shed tears) Folake, ta wa la se?

MOPELOLA : (in a dull mood) Mummy, e se je ka lo be Iya Sade, te so pe o l'eri si yin

FOLAKE : Oto ni Mope so o, e je ka lo be won.

AJIKE : Hun! Mo gbo o, a maa lo

CAM FADE

CAST : Folake, Mopelola & Ajike

SCENE 11

IYA IJEBU'S PARLOUR

INT/DAY

Camera shows Ajike in Iya Ijebu's house, pleading with her.

- AJIKE** : Iya, Olorun o ni je ke mo sa re omo, olori aso yin o ni faya, ejo e sanu mi, e f'ori jin mi
- IYA IJEBU** : Duro naa o, se e lo sile alayewo won l'emi ni mon se yin?
- AJIKE** : Won o so be o, amo gbogbo oro ti a fin sere lojo naa, bi ere bi ere, aiti ko'fa nle, ifa tin se bi ala. Mo tin ri wahala omo bayi, e dakun e maa je ntun lojo mo, e sa fori jin mi
- IYA IJEBU** : Emi o ni ki t'omo eni kan maa da o, eyin ni ke ye kolofin okan yin wo. Eyin ni ke moju to iwa owo yin, eda kan o le gbin alubosa, ko ka igba layelaye, oun to ba gbin ni yio ka. Emi o bayin ja mo o, eyin ni ki e kiyesi ara yin.
- AJIKE** : E se o. Ijo wo wa ni Sade maa bere shop pada?
- IYA IJEBU** : Bere kini pada? Olorun ti gbadura ti wa naa, Sade tin kiri oja, koda on mura ati kiri lowo ninu ile ni (*she call on Sade*) Sade o!.
- SADE** : [*answers from off shot*] Ma a, mo nbo
- IYA IJEBU** : B'ede o l'eeni laye, enikan o le pe a sare. B'eda o ba de sare, ko le tete de ibi ton lo.
- (Sade comes out with her market)*
- SADE** : (*she greets*) Eku ijoko Ma a (*face her mother*) Emi ni yi
- IYA IJEBU** : Oga e naa ni mo ni ko wa ki
- AJIKE** : O ti ki mi, bawo ni my dear, eku ijo meta, pele s'alafia ni
- SADE** : Awon Aunty Folake ati Aunty Mope nko?
- AJIKE** : Gbogbo won lo wa
- SADE** : Mo tin kiri Ma
- AJIKE & IYA IJEBU**: Wa ta o
- (Sade exit)*
- AJIKE** : Emi naa ti fe maa lo Ma